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Phase Equilibria and Phase Transformations of Ti–Al–X (X=Nb, Mo, W) Alloys for High-Temperature Structural Applications between 700 and 1300 °C

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Never give up on your dreams!

Abstract

The ever-growing awareness of climate change, environmental concerns, and the drive to make the future of travel more sustainable have increased the demand for new lightweight high-temperature materials for structural applications in recent years. Due to their very high specific strength up to 700 °C, TiAl-based alloys are used as a substitute for Ni-based alloys in certain parts of turbine jet engines and are already industrially established. To further exploit the energy-saving potential of such alloys, it is necessary to increase the application temperature of these alloys up to 900 °C. Along other elements, the alloys currently in use rely mainly on the addition of so-called (β Ti)-stabilizing elements to achieve the necessary material properties required for their use as structural materials at high temperatures. The transition metals Nb and Mo are among the most important elements in the alloys currently in use, and W is very promising for making a significant contribution to the envisaged increase in application temperature.

In order to achieve these ambitious goals, precise knowledge of the phase equilibria in the three Ti–Al–X systems (X = Nb, Mo, W) is of utmost importance. Therefore, series of ternary alloys and solid-solid as well as liquid-solid diffusion couples were produced and heat-treated in the temperature range between 700 and 1300 °C. These heat-treated alloys were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), electron probe micro analyses (EPMA), X-ray and high-energy X-ray diffraction (HE)XRD, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and differential thermal analysis (DTA) to determine the phase equilibria, phase transformation temperatures and kinetics, isothermal sections and reaction schemes.

The initial portion of the work focusses on the Ti–Al–Nb system, which is by far the most complex of the three investigated systems. As a result of the two ternary intermetallic compounds ω_0 (“Ti₄NbAl₃”) and O (“Ti₂NbAl”), which form during cooling and decompose upon heating in solid-solid phase transformations, the phase equilibria below 1000 °C are quite complex. The ω_0 phase field is split into a Nb-poor and Nb-rich part by a (β Ti,Nb)₀ phase field due to a complex reaction sequence. From its crystal structure type and measured phase compositions, a new formula (Ti,Nb)₂Al is suggested for the ω_0 phase. The (β Ti,Nb)₀ phase that splits the ω_0 phase field exists in an isolated composition range alongside the Ti-richer (β Ti,Nb) solid solution at 800 to 1100 °C. These two single-phase fields merge at higher

temperatures and the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ phase loses its *B2*-order at a maximum temperature of about 1250 °C as determined by DTA measurements.

Another aspect investigated are the solid-solid phase transformations and their kinetics in the Ti–Al–Nb system. A systematic DTA investigation with 4-5 different heating rates (0.8 to 10 °C/min) gives insights into the occurring phase transformations. Two-types of transformations were identified: i) the second-order type disordering transformation of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$; ii) the first-order type transformations of Ti_3Al to (αTi) and O/ω_o to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$. The first-order type transformation shows different degrees of a continuous but non-linear heating rate dependence, which can be described by a model developed by Zhu and Devletian. This allows the determination of the equilibrium transformation temperatures (corresponding to a heating rate of 0 °C/min) for these transformations, which facilitates the determination of the complex phase equilibria especially below 1000 °C. The obtained phase equilibria and equilibrium transformation temperatures were used to establish a reaction scheme of the Ti–Al–Nb system.

Impurities, such as oxygen, are known to have a high solubility in the hexagonal phases (αTi) and Ti_3Al . By comparing own results and data available in the literature, this is found to affect the solubility of Nb in the (αTi) phase at high temperatures shifting phase equilibria to higher Nb contents. The presence of Ti_6 octahedral voids in (αTi) and Ti_3Al is discussed as a cause for this behaviour.

Less complicated, but still complex, phase equilibria are observed in the Ti–Al–Mo system. In contrast to the Ti–Al–Nb system, only one ternary intermetallic phase exists here. This is the σ phase (“ $\text{Ti}_3\text{Mo}_3\text{Al}_4$ ”), which is stable up to above 1100 °C. With respect to the σ phase, contradicting phase equilibria are reported in the literature. Based on the presented results, it is clarified that a three-phase equilibrium $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o + \text{TiAl}_3 + \sigma$ occurs at 1000 °C and below. In addition, the disordering behaviour of $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o$ was studied by DTA measurements and a maximum disordering temperature of ~1420 °C at a composition Ti-25Al-25Mo was confirmed. Based on the presented results, a revised reaction scheme for the Ti–Al–Mo system is presented.

In the final part of the present thesis, the Ti–Al–W system is investigated. In this ternary system, no ternary intermetallic phase and no *B2*-order in the $(\beta\text{Ti,W})$ phase was experimentally observed. Phase equilibria between TiAl and the (W) solid solution were established by TEM

investigations, leading to significantly different phase equilibria as observed in the other two systems.

The phase equilibria, phase transformation temperatures and kinetics reported in this thesis aim to facilitate an increase in application temperature of current and future TiAl-based alloy generations. This will enable more sustainable mobility in the future.

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Contents

Abstract	iv
Acknowledgements.....	vii
List of Tables	xiii
List of Figures.....	xvi
1 Introduction and Motivation.....	1
2 Fundamentals of TiAl-based alloys for high-temperature structural applications.....	4
2.1 The Ti–Al phase diagram	5
2.2 Manufacturing and alloying concept.....	7
3 Materials and experimental methods	10
3.1 Materials preparation.....	10
3.1.1 Alloy synthesis	10
3.1.2 Heat treatments	13
3.1.2.1 Bulk alloys	13
3.1.2.2 Diffusion couples	16
3.2 Materials characterization.....	17
3.2.1 Chemical analysis	17
3.2.2 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)	17
3.2.3 Electron probe micro analysis (EPMA).....	18
3.2.3.1 Bulk alloys	18
3.2.3.2 Diffusion couples	19
3.2.4 Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA)	20
3.2.5 X-ray diffraction.....	21
3.2.5.1 Conventional X-ray diffraction (XRD)	21
3.2.5.2 <i>In situ</i> and <i>ex situ</i> high-energy X-ray diffraction (HEXRD)	21
3.2.6 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM).....	22

4 Phase equilibria, microstructure, phase stability and phase transformation kinetics in Ti–Al–Nb alloys	23
4.1 Low-temperature phase equilibria between 700 and 900 °C.....	24
4.1.1 Literature review.....	24
4.1.2 Results.....	25
4.1.3 Isothermal sections, phase fields, solubility and phase formation between 700 and 900 °C.....	42
4.1.3.1 The two-phase field $Ti_3Al + TiAl$	44
4.1.3.2 Phase equilibria and homogeneity range of the ω_o phase.....	45
4.1.3.2.1 The Nb-poor limit ($Ti_3Al + TiAl + \omega_o$).....	45
4.1.3.2.2 The Nb-rich limit ($TiAl + \omega_o + Nb_2Al$)	46
4.1.3.2.3 Equilibria on the Al-rich side – Formation of the $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ phase from ω_o	46
4.1.3.2.4 Equilibria on the Ti-Nb-rich side	48
4.1.3.2.5 Splitting of the ω_o phase field.....	49
4.1.3.2.6 Stoichiometry of the ω_o phase – revised formula	51
4.1.3.3 Phase equilibria and homogeneity range of the O phase.....	52
4.1.3.4 Solubility of ternary elements in the boundary phases (αTi), $(\beta Ti,Nb)$, Ti_3Al , and Nb_2Al	55
4.2 High-temperature phase equilibria between 1000 and 1300 °C	57
4.2.1 Literature review.....	57
4.2.2 Results.....	60
4.2.3 Isothermal sections, phase fields, solubility and phase formation between 1000 and 1300 °C	71
4.2.3.1 Phase fields and solubility limits of $(\beta Ti,Nb)$	74
4.2.3.1.1 Isolated $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ phase field	74
4.2.3.1.2 $(\beta Ti,Nb)$ solid-solution	77
4.2.3.2 The (αTi) and Ti_3Al phase fields.....	78
4.2.3.2.1 The Ti_3Al phase field.....	78
4.2.3.2.2 The (αTi) solid solution	80
4.3 Thermal analysis of solid-solid phase transformations	82
4.3.1 Heating rate independent transition $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ to $(\beta Ti,Nb)$	84
4.3.1.1 Stability range of $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$	86
4.3.2 Heating rate dependent transformations	89

4.3.2.1	The Ti_3Al to (αTi) transformation.....	89
4.3.2.2.1	Influence of Nb on the Ti_3Al to (αTi) transformation temperature.....	91
4.3.2.2	The ω_o to ($\beta Ti,Nb$) $_o$ transformation.....	92
4.3.2.3	The O phase to ($\beta Ti,Nb$) $_o$ transformation.....	95
4.4	Effect of oxygen on phase equilibria	98
4.4.1	Results and comparison of the Nb solubility in (αTi) with the literature	99
4.4.2	Discussion: Octahedral voids	101
4.5	Reaction scheme	104
5	Phase equilibria, microstructure, and solubility limits in Ti–Al–Mo alloys.....	108
5.1	Literature review	109
5.2	Results	111
5.3	Isothermal sections, phase fields, solubility and phase formation.....	124
5.3.1	Phase equilibria with the σ phase	127
5.3.2	Ordering behaviour of ($\beta Ti,Mo$).....	128
5.3.3	Solubility of ternary elements in the boundary phases (αTi), ($\beta Ti,Nb$), and Ti_3Al	130
5.4	Reaction Scheme.....	131
6	Phase equilibria, microstructure, and phase stability in Ti–Al–W alloys.....	136
6.1	Literature review	137
6.2	Results	137
6.3	Isothermal sections, phase fields, solubility and phase formation.....	147
6.3.1	Phase equilibria with the (W) solid solution	150
6.3.2	Solubility of ternary elements in the boundary phases (αTi), ($\beta Ti,W$), Ti_3Al , $TiAl$, and (W)	154
7	Conclusions	157
	References	162
	Curriculum Vitae	177
	Publications, Oral Talks, and Poster.....	178

List of Tables

Table 1 Crystallographic information for all phases of the binary Ti–Al system (Figure 1) with their crystal system, Pearson symbol, space group, and Strukturbericht designation.....	7
Table 2 Synthesized ternary Ti–Al–Nb (TAN1 to TAN17), Ti–Al–Mo (TAM1 to TAM13), Ti–Al–W (TAW1 to TAW10), and binary Ti–Al (TA1 and TA2) and Ti–Nb (TN2 to TN4) alloys with their nominal and measured compositions (ICP-AES) as well as their contents of impurity elements (O and C). The N contents were also analysed, the values were all below the detection limit of 50 wt. ppm and are therefore not listed here.	11
Table 3 Overview of the heat-treated ternary alloys showing heat treatment temperature and time.	14
Table 4 Overview of investigated diffusion couples specifying the combination, type, temperature, and time.	17
Table 5 Crystallographic information (crystal system, Pearson symbol, space group, and Strukturbericht designation) of the additional phases present in the Ti–Al–Nb system. These phases are observed in the microstructure, the isothermal sections, and reaction scheme as a result of the addition of Nb.	23
Table 6 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 700 °C for 1500 h (accuracy of the lattice parameters is $\pm 0.001 \text{ \AA}$, n.d.: not determined).....	27
Table 7 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 800 °C for 1000 h (accuracy of the lattice parameters is $\pm 0.001 \text{ \AA}$, n.d.: not determined).....	28
Table 8 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 900 °C for 650 h (1000 h in case of TAN5, TAN6, and TAN10) (accuracy of the lattice parameters is $\pm 0.001 \text{ \AA}$, n.d.: not determined).	30
Table 9 Extrapolated equilibrium compositions as obtained from the diffusion couples 700 °C/1150 h, 800 °C/750 h, and 900 °C/400 h.	32
Table 10 Lattice parameters (accuracy of the lattice parameters is $\pm 0.001 \text{ \AA}$) of the O phase as function of the Nb content measured in quenched samples (Tables 6-8).....	54
Table 11 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 1000 °C for 400 h (accuracy of the lattice parameters is $\pm 0.001 \text{ \AA}$, n.d.: not determined).....	60
Table 12 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 1100 °C for 200 h (accuracy of the lattice parameters is $\pm 0.001 \text{ \AA}$, n.d.: not determined).....	61
Table 13 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 1200 °C for 20 h (accuracy of the lattice parameters is $\pm 0.001 \text{ \AA}$, n.d.: not determined).....	63

Table 14 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 1300 °C for 30 h (accuracy of the lattice parameters is $\pm 0.001 \text{ \AA}$, n.d.: not determined).....	64
Table 15 Types of phase transformations that occur in the various alloys studied are marked with “x” (for simplicity, only the phases that transform into each other are mentioned, although other phases may be involved whose phase fraction and composition also change).83	83
Table 16 Disorder temperature of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ as measured with constant heating rate of 10 °C/min for differently heat-treated samples of the alloys TAN9 (Ti-36.4Al-9.7Nb) and TAN15 (Ti-44.5Al-11.7Nb).....	85
Table 17 Equilibrium disordering temperatures of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ for alloys TAN4-12 and TAN15-17 with the respective composition of the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ phase.....	85
Table 18 Transformation temperatures for the Ti_3Al to (αTi) transformation in different alloys as determined from DTA heating curves. The extrapolated equilibrium transformation temperatures (corresponding to 0 °C/min heating rate) are given in the last row.....	90
Table 19 Equilibrium phase transformation temperatures for the phase transformation ω_o to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ determined by applying the approach of Zhu et al. [131, 132].....	94
Table 20 Transformation temperatures for the O to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ transformations in different alloys upon heating as determined by DTA. The extrapolated equilibrium transformation temperatures are given in the last row.....	96
Table 21 Comparison of oxygen contents measured with inert gas fusion of alloys TAN8, 9, 11, and 13-15 in as-cast and heat-treated (1300 °C for 20 h) samples (n.d.: not determined). 99	99
Table 22 Crystallographic information (crystal system, Pearson symbol, space group, and Strukturbericht designation) of the additional phases present in the Ti–Al–Mo system. These phases are observed in the microstructure, the isothermal sections, and reaction scheme as a result of the addition of Mo.	109
Table 23 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–Mo alloys heat-treated at 800 °C for 1000 h. (n.d.: not determined).	112
Table 24 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–Mo alloys heat-treated at 900 °C for 650 h. (n.d.: not determined).	113
Table 25 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–Mo alloys heat-treated at 1000 °C for 400 h. (n.d.: not determined).	114
Table 26 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–Mo alloys heat-treated at 1100 °C for 200 h. (n.d.: not determined).	115
Table 27 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–Mo alloys heat-treated at 1200 °C for 30 h. (n.d.: not determined).	115
Table 28 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–Mo alloys heat-treated at 1300 °C for 20 h. (n.d.: not determined).	116
Table 29 Disorder temperatures determined by DTA measurements for alloys TAM8, TAM9, TAM10, and TAM13 with the composition of the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ phase. For alloy TAM13 the nominal composition is give, for the other alloys the composition determined in the quenched sample for 1300 °C.	129

Table 30 Crystallographic information (crystal system, Pearson symbol, space group, and Strukturbericht designation) of the additional phases present in the Ti–Al–W system and observed in the present investigations.	136
Table 31 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–W alloys heat-treated at 800 and 900 °C for 2000 h. (n.d.: not determined).....	139
Table 32 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–W alloys heat-treated at 1000 and 1100 °C for 650 and 400 h, respectively. (n.d.: not determined).	140
Table 33 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–W alloys heat-treated at 1200 °C for 30 h (n.d.: not determined).....	141
Table 34 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–W alloys heat-treated at 1300 C for 20 h (n.d.: not determined).	142

List of Figures

- Figure 1** Binary Ti–Al phase diagram assessed by Schuster and Palm [28] modified with the information summarized by Palm [29].5
- Figure 2** Binary Ti–Al phase diagram (dashed grey lines) from 30-60 at.% Al overlaid with quasibinary section from Chen et al. [49] at 8 at.% Nb (dark lines). The blue dashed lines indicate the Al content range (42-48 at.%) of the currently used TiAl-based alloys.8
- Figure 3** Schematic setup of the sample encapsulation (on the left) for heat treatments at 700 to 1100 °C and the double crucible technique (on the right) for heat treatments above 1100 °C.13
- Figure 4** Schematic setup for solid-solid (top) and liquid-solid (bottom) diffusion couples. On the top right side, the solid-solid diffusion couple is shown before encapsulation (piece 1 is TN1 (Ti-20Nb), piece 2 is TA2 (Ti-50Al), and piece 3 is TN2 (Ti-30Nb)). A solidified liquid-solid diffusion couple after heat treatment is displayed on the bottom right side. Figure from Ref. [53].16
- Figure 5** EPMA grid measurement data of a three-phase sample plotted in a composition triangle to determine the equilibrium phase compositions (red dots).19
- Figure 6** a) Typical concentration profile of a (β Ti,Nb)/TiAl diffusion couple; b) magnified view of the concentration profile, with extrapolated equilibrium phase compositions marked, showing a composition jump corresponding to the (β Ti,Nb)/Ti₃Al interface in the diffusion couple.....20
- Figure 7** As-cast alloy composition (Table 2) of the ternary bulk alloys (TAN1-TAN15, black stars) and the compositions of the binary single-phase alloys (TA2 and TN1-TN3; grey circles), for diffusion-couple investigations, plotted in the ternary composition triangle.26
- Figure 8** Back-scattered electron (BSE) images of alloy TAN1 (Ti-17.4Al-4.8Nb) heat-treated at a) 700 °C/1500 h, b) 800 °C/1000 h, c) 900 °C/650 h showing a three-phase microstructure of (α Ti) (grey), (β Ti,Nb) (bright), and Ti₃Al (dark).33
- Figure 9** BSE images of the microstructure of alloy TAN2 (Ti-17.5Al-10Nb) heat-treated at a) 700 °C for 1500 h and b) 900 °C for 650 h with (β Ti,Nb) (bright) and Ti₃Al (dark).34
- Figure 10** a) BSE image of alloy TAN4 (Ti-24.6Al-14.9Nb) heat-treated at 900 °C/650 h with (β Ti,Nb)_o (bright), Ti₃Al (dark), and O phase (grey) and; b) Bright field TEM image of the matrix of alloy TAN4 showing plate-like Ti₃Al in an O phase matrix.35
- Figure 11** BSE images of alloy TAN6 (Ti-30Al-25Nb) heat-treated at 900 °C/1000 h. The sample consists of two parts representing (a) the two-phase field O + Nb₂Al and b) the three-phase field Ti₃Al + O + Nb₂Al.35
- Figure 12** a) BSE image of alloy TAN7 (Ti-32.8Al-12.2Nb) heat-treated at 900 °C with large ω_o grains (bright) as matrix phase and Ti₃Al (dark) as grain boundary phase and inside the grains as precipitates (the contrast differences appearing in the ω_o matrix are not due to chemical differences, which was verified by EPMA spot analyses at different positions resulting in identical compositions); b) BSE images of alloy TAN9 (Ti-37.2Al-10.0Nb) and c) alloy TAN11 (Ti-39.6Al-10.0Nb) heat-treated at 900 °C for 650 h lying in the same three-phase field composed of Ti₃Al (grey), TiAl (dark), and ω_o (bright), d) respective HEXRD pattern of B11 (with logarithmic intensity scale) confirming the microstructural results.....37

Figure 13 BSE images of alloy TAN9 (Ti-37.2Al-10.0Nb) at a) 700 °C heat-treated for 1500 h and b) 800 °C heat-treated for 1000 h; both showing a three-phase microstructure between ω_o (grey) as matrix phase with fine TiAl precipitates and Ti_3Al at the grain boundaries; c) bright field TEM image of the ω_o matrix with twinned TiAl precipitates identified by SAED.	38
Figure 14 a) X-ray diffractogram of alloy TAN10 (Ti-37Al-13.5Nb) after heat-treatment at 900 °C and quenching showing the presence of $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$, TiAl as well as some ω_o phase; b) DTA heating curves of the same sample. The upper curve shows the heat flow signal during first heating (up to 1350 °C) of the quenched sample, and the lower curve is the result of a second heating of the same sample after cooling from 1350 °C. The exothermic effects during first heating reveal the metastability of the sample quenched from 900 °C (the dashed gray line is to indicate the course of the hypothetical baseline).	39
Figure 15 BSE image of alloy TAN12 (Ti-39.8Al-19.9Nb) a) heat-treated at 900 °C for 650 h showing a two-phase microstructure consisting of TiAl (dark) and Nb_2Al (bright), and b) heat-treated at 800 °C for 1000 h revealing the three-phase equilibrium $TiAl + \omega_o + Nb_2Al$	40
Figure 16 BSE images of alloy TAN13 (Ti-43.5Al-4.9Nb) showing coarse- and fine-lamellar Ti_3Al (bright) + TiAl (dark) two-phase microstructures after heat treatment at a) 700 °C, b) 800 °C, and c) 900 °C.	42
Figure 17 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 700 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Tables 6 and 9. The measured overall compositions of the samples are indicated by black stars, the yellow lines mark the three-phase equilibria, grey symbols and lines indicate the data from the diffusion couples, and blue symbols and lines mark the results from bulk alloys and the resulting phase boundaries.	43
Figure 18 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 800 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Tables 7 and 9 (symbols as in Figure 17).	43
Figure 19 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 900 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Tables 8 and 9 (symbols as in Figure 17, unfilled stars: nominal alloy composition).	44
Figure 20 DTA heat flow curve of alloy TAN10 (heat-treated at 1000 °C for 400 h, heating rate 5 °C/min) showing the ω_o -to- $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ transformation.	48
Figure 21 Schematic partial isothermal sections a) at 850 ± 45 °C just above the (unknown) temperature where the growing $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ phase has split the ω_o phase field into two parts resulting in the two new ternary triangles marked in violet, and b) at 898 °C after the transition-type reaction $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o + Ti_3Al \rightleftharpoons O + \omega_o$ on the Nb-poor and $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o + Nb_2Al \rightleftharpoons O + \omega_o$ on the Nb-rich side.	50
Figure 22 Lattice parameters of a “pseudo”-orthorhombic Ti_3Al and the O phase plotted as function of Nb content superimposed with the results from Kestner-Weykamp [77] (unfilled triangles) showing the continuous change of the lattice parameters (a = blue dots; b = red dots; c = green dots) from the “pseudo”-orthorhombic to the orthorhombic unit cell with increasing Nb content.	55
Figure 23 As-cast alloy composition (Table 2) of the ternary bulk alloys (TAN1-TAN15, black stars/TAN16 and TAN17, blue stars) plotted in the ternary composition triangle.	57
Figure 24 Isothermal section at 1100 °C from Li et al. [102] (black dots; grey and red lines) superimposed with experimental results from Eckert et al. [105] (orange diamonds and violet lines) and summarized results by Kattner et al. [83] (blue stars and green lines) showing several contradicting phase equilibria.	58

Figure 25 BSE image of a) alloy TAN1 (Ti-17.4Al-4.8Nb) quenched from 1000 °C showing a two-phase microstructure (martensitic decomposed (β Ti,Nb) + Ti_3Al) and b) alloy TAN3 (Ti-20.0Al-17.5Nb) quenched from 1100 °C being single-phase (β Ti,Nb).....	65
Figure 26 DTA heat flow curve of alloys TAN2 and TAN3 showing the dissolution of Ti_3Al at 985 °C (TAN3) and 995 °C (TAN2). The grey dashed line indicates the baseline.	65
Figure 27 BSE image of alloy TAN4 (Ti-24.6Al-14.9Nb) heat treated at 1000 °C with a two-phase microstructure consisting of (β Ti,Nb) _o (bright) and Ti_3Al (dark); b) respective HEXRD pattern (with logarithmic intensity scale) confirming the microstructural results; c) BSE image of alloy TAN6 (Ti-30.0Al-25.0Nb) heat treated at 1000 °C showing a three-phase microstructure consisting of Nb_2Al (bright), Ti_3Al (dark) and (β Ti,Nb) _o (grey); d) respective HEXRD pattern (with logarithmic intensity scale) confirming the microstructural results.	66
Figure 28 BSE images of a) alloy TAN7 (Ti-32.8Al-12.2Nb) and b) alloy TAN8 (Ti-32.4Al-17.3Nb) heat treated at 1000 °C showing a two-phase microstructure between (β Ti,Nb) _o (bright) and Ti_3Al (dark).....	67
Figure 29 BSE images of a) alloy TAN9 (Ti-37.2Al-10.0Nb) and b) alloy TAN11 (Ti-39.6Al-10.0Nb) heat treated at 1100 °C showing a three-phase microstructure composed (β Ti,Nb) _o (matrix), Ti_3Al (grey), and TiAl (dark); c) alloy TAN11 heat-treated at 1300 °C with single-phase (β Ti,Nb) microstructure.	68
Figure 30 Intensity over temperature plot of a) the (001) and (110) peak of TiAl, showing the dissolution of TiAl at about 1150 °C in alloy TAN9 (Ti-37.2Al-10.0Nb); b) the (001) superstructure reflection of (β Ti,Nb) _o showing the disordering of (β Ti,Nb) _o at 1222 °C (data obtained by <i>in situ</i> HEXRD measurements).....	69
Figure 31 Plot of the <i>in situ</i> HEXRD measurement (heating rate 2 °C/min) of alloy TAN11 (Ti-39.6Al-10.0Nb) in the Temperature range between 1000 and 1200°C showing the presence of (β Ti,Nb) _o + Ti_3Al + TiAl above 1000 °C. The (100) and (101) superstructure reflexions of Ti_3Al are observed up to ~1170 °C. At higher temperatures (α Ti) is stable instead.....	69
Figure 32 BSE image of alloy TAN12 (Ti-39.8Al-19.9Nb) heat treated at a) 1100 °C showing a three-phase microstructure composed of (β Ti,Nb) _o (grey), TiAl (dark), and Nb_2Al (bright) and b) 1200 °C showing the same three-phase microstructure but with the (β Ti,Nb) phase being disordered now according to the DTA results.	70
Figure 33 BSE image of a) alloy TAN13 (Ti-43.4Al-4.9Nb) heat treated at 1100 °C showing a two-phase microstructure consisting of Ti_3Al (bright) and TiAl (dark); b) alloy TAN13 heat treated at 1200 °C showing a two-phase microstructure consisting of (α Ti) (bright) and TiAl (dark); c) alloy TAN14 (Ti-45.8Al-5.9Nb) heat treated at 1300 °C showing a two-phase microstructure consisting of (α Ti) (bright) and TiAl (dark); d) alloy TAN15 (Ti-44.7Al-12.3Nb) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing the three-phase equilibrium between (α Ti) (grey), (β Ti,Nb) (bright), and TiAl (dark).	71
Figure 34 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 1000 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 11 (symbols same as in Figure 17, unfilled stars: as-cast and nominal alloy composition).....	72
Figure 35 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 1100 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 12 (symbols as in Figure 17).....	73
Figure 36 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 1200 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 13 (symbols as in Figure 17).....	73

Figure 37 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 1300 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 14 (symbols as in Figure 17).....	74
Figure 38 DTA heat flow measurement of alloy TAN12 (Ti-39.8Al-19.9Nb) showing no peak between 1000 and 1100 C, which indicates that no invariant reaction takes place in this temperature interval. At higher temperatures, the disordering of (βTi,Nb) _o at 1199 °C and the dissolution of Nb ₂ Al at 1224 °C and TiAl at 1253 °C are will visible.....	77
Figure 39 BSE image of alloy TAN16 (Ti-35.0Al-5.0Nb) heat-treated at 1100 °C showing a two-phase microstructure between (βTi,Nb) _o (bright) and Ti ₃ Al (dark).....	79
Figure 40 Possible Ti ₃ Al island at 1200 °C (black dashed lines) superimposed on the isothermal section presented in Figure 36.....	80
Figure 41 a) Order/disorder temperatures for the (βTi,Nb) _o to (βTi,Nb) transition in selected alloys measured with heating rates of 1, 2, 5, and 10 °C/min; b) comparison of a heating and respective cooling heat flow curve of TAN8 (Ti-32.8Al-16.8Nb) the same transition temperature during heating and cooling.	84
Figure 42 Disorder temperatures and phase compositions of (βTi,Nb) plotted in a partial Gibbs-triangle with tentative areas of disordering temperatures above 1240 °C (dark-colored area) and 1200 °C (light-colored area). Included are also the A2/B2-disordering lines from the isothermal sections from 900 (Figure 19, green), 1000 (Figure 34, blue), and 1100 °C (Figure 35, brown).....	87
Figure 43 DTA heat flow curves (heating rate: 10 °C/min) of alloy TAN13 (Ti-44.3Al-4.9Nb) showing the transformation Ti ₃ Al to (αTi) for three differently heat-treated samples (preceding heat treatment at 700, 800, or 900 °C).....	91
Figure 44 a) DTA heating curves of alloy Ti-39.8Al-9.4Nb (TAN11) obtained with different heating rates; b) non-linear heating rate dependence of the transformation temperatures.	93
Figure 45 Plot of the experimentally determined transformation temperatures for the transformation ω _o to (βTi,Nb) _o as a function of (heating rate) ^{1/3} (approach of Zhu et al. [131, 132]). From the linear extrapolations to 0 °C/min heating rate, the equilibrium transformation temperatures for alloys TAN7, TAN8, TAN9, TAN11, TAN12, and TAN15 were determined.	93
Figure 46 Transformation temperature and composition of ω _o (stars) and O phase (circles) plotted in a partial Gibbs-triangle with homogeneity range of ω _o (orange colored area) and O phase (grey colored area) at 900 °C.	95
Figure 47 Comparison of the heating rate dependence of the transformations Ti ₃ Al to (αTi), O to (βTi,Nb) _o , and ω _o to (βTi,Nb) _o (for each type of transformation one specific example was chosen, the presented data belong to alloys TA1 (squares), and TAN6 (triangles), and TAN9 (circles), respectively).....	97
Figure 48 Partial isothermal section of Ti–Al–Nb at 1300 °C showing the shift of the position of the tie-triangle (αTi) + (βTi,Nb) + as obtained by Xu et al. [100], Nakamura et al. [112], Kainuma et al. [106], and the present investigations. The oxygen contents of the respective alloys is also given (as-cast condition).	100
Figure 49 Reaction schematic of the Ti–Al–Nb system from Liquid phase down to 600 °C. The reactions involving the liquid phase are based on the modelling work from Witusiewicz et al. [84], the reactions in the binary are taken from the respective literature [28, 29, 32], and all other reactions are based on the above discussed results.	107

Figure 50 As-cast alloy composition (Table 2) of the ternary bulk alloys (TAM1-TAM12, black stars) plotted in the ternary composition triangle.....	111
Figure 51 BSE image of alloy TAM1 (Ti-15Al-2.5Mo) heat-treated at a) 900 °C showing a two-phase microstructure composed of (α Ti) (dark) and (β Ti,Mo) (bright) and b) 1000 °C showing α'' martensite that formed from (β Ti,Mo) during quenching; c) DTA heat flow curve of alloy TAM1 heat-treated at 1000°C showing that dissolution of (α Ti) is complete at 999 ± 1 °C.	118
Figure 52 BSE image of a) alloy TAM2 (Ti-18.8Al-2.0Mo) quenched from 1000 °C showing a three-phase microstructure (α Ti) (grey) + (β Ti,Mo) _o (bright) + Ti ₃ Al (dark) and b) alloy TAM3 (Ti-30.0Al-5.0Mo) quenched from 900 °C showing big (β Ti,Mo) _o (bright) grains with fine Ti ₃ Al (dark) precipitates and Ti ₃ Al at the grain boundaries.	119
Figure 53 BSE image of alloy TAM4 (Ti-39.6Al-2.0Mo) a) heat-treated at 1000 °C showing a three-phase microstructure consisting of (β Ti,Mo) _o (bright), Ti ₃ Al (grey), and TiAl (dark) and b) heat-treated at 1200 °C showing a two-phase microstructure composed of (α Ti) (grey) and (β Ti,Mo) _o (bright) (despite various different contrasts only two different compositions were measured by EPMA).	120
Figure 54 BSE image of alloy TAM5 (Ti-44.9Al-1.2Mo) a) heat-treated at 1200 °C showing a three-phase microstructure consisting of (α Ti) (grey), (β Ti,Mo) _o (bright), and TiAl (dark) and b) heat-treated at 1200 °C showing a two-phase microstructure between (α Ti) (bright) and TiAl (dark).	120
Figure 55 BSE image of a) alloy TAM6 (Ti-45.0Al-2.5Mo) heat-treated at 1200 °C showing a two-phase microstructure composed of (β Ti,Mo) _o (bright) and TiAl (dark) and b) alloy TAM7 (Ti-44.6Al-3.7Mo) showing a three-phase microstructure consisting of (α Ti) (grey), (β Ti,Mo) (bright), and TiAl (dark) after quenching from 1300 °C.	121
Figure 56 BSE image of a) alloy TAM8 (Ti-45.0Al-5.0Mo) heat-treated at 1000 °C, b),c) alloy TAM9 (Ti-45.0Al-7.5Mo) heat-treated at 900 and 1300 °C, respectively; d) alloy TAM (Ti-45.0Al-10.0Mo) heat-treated at 1200 °C all showing a two-phase microstructure consisting of (β Ti,Mo)/(β Ti,Mo) _o (bright) and TiAl (dark).	122
Figure 57 BSE images of alloy TAM11 (Ti-56.1Al-10.9Mo) a) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing a two-phase microstructure composed of (β Ti,Mo) _o (bright) and TiAl (dark); b) heat-treated at 1000 °C; c) homogenized at 1300 °C for 48 h and subsequently heat-treated at 1000; and d) homogenized at 1300 °C for 48 h and subsequently heat-treated at 900 °C showing (β Ti,Mo) _o (grey), TiAl (dark), TiAl ₃ (light grey), and σ (bright) in their respective microstructures.	123
Figure 58 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Mo system at 800 °C based on the experimental results listed in Table 23. The measured overall compositions of the samples are indicated by black stars (unfilled stars: as-cast or nominal alloy composition, see Table 2), the yellow lines show the three-phase equilibria, and blue symbols and lines mark the results from bulk alloys and the resulting phase boundaries.	124
Figure 59 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Mo system at 900 °C based on the experimental results listed in Table 24 (symbols as in Figure 58).....	125
Figure 60 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Mo system at 1000 °C based on the experimental results listed in Table 25 (symbols as in Figure 58).....	125
Figure 61 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Mo system at 1100 °C based on the experimental results listed in Table 26 (symbols as in Figure 58).....	126

Figure 62 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Mo system at 1200 °C based on the experimental results listed in Table 27 (symbols as in Figure 58).....	126
Figure 63 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Mo system at 1300 °C based on the experimental results listed in Table 28 (symbols as in Figure 58).....	127
Figure 64: BSE image of alloy TAM11 (Ti-56.1Al-10.9Mo) a) in the as-cast condition showing solidification of primary (β Ti,Mo) completely surrounded by a grey contrast and a dark contrast filling the left over space; b) the heat-treated sample quenched from 800 °C showing first indications of formation of σ (bright).....	128
Figure 65 Reaction schematic of the Ti–Al–Mo system from Liquid phase down to room temperature (RT). The reaction scheme is based on Ref. [153] and the above presented results.	135
Figure 66 As-cast alloy compositions (Table 2) of the ternary bulk alloys (TAW1-TAW10) plotted in the composition triangle.	138
Figure 67 BSE image of a) alloy TAW1 (Ti-28.3Al-6.1W) heat-treated at 1200 °C showing a single-phase (β Ti,W) microstructure; b) alloy TAW2 (Ti-32.3Al-8.6W) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing a two-phase microstructure between (β Ti,W) and (W).	143
Figure 68 BSE image of a) alloy TAW3 (Ti-40.0Al-1.5W) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing a two-phase microstructure (α Ti) (dark) + (β Ti,W) (bright); b) alloy TAW4 (Ti-40.6Al-1.8W), heat-treated at 1100 °C showing a three-phase microstructure composed of (β Ti,W) (bright), Ti ₃ Al (grey), and TiAl (dark).	144
Figure 69 BSE image of a) alloy TAW6 (Ti-45.5Al-0.9W) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing a two-phase microstructure consisting of (α Ti) (bright) and (TiAl) (dark); b) alloy TAW5 (Ti-45.0Al-1.1W) heat-treated at 1000 °C composed of the three phases (β Ti,W) (bright), Ti ₃ Al (grey), and TiAl (dark).	145
Figure 70 BSE image of a) alloy TAW7 (Ti-47.1Al-4.1W) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing a two-phase microstructure (β Ti,W) (bright) + TiAl (dark); b) alloy TAW9 (Ti-50.8Al-6.6W) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing a TiAl matrix with bright (W) precipitates; a,d) alloy TAW8 (Ti-50.2Al-3.0W) heat treated at 1100 °C for 400 and 800 h, respectively, showing the same microstructure constituents as in b).....	146
Figure 71 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–W system at 800 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 31. The measured overall compositions of the samples are indicated by black stars (grey stars for as-cast compositions), the yellow lines mark the three-phase equilibria, and blue symbols and lines mark the results from bulk alloys and the resulting phase boundaries.	147
Figure 72 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–W system at 900 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 31 (symbols as in Figure 71).	148
Figure 73 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–W system at 1000 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 32 (symbols as in Figure 71).	148
Figure 74 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–W system at 1100 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Tabel 32 (symbols as in Figure 71).	149
Figure 75 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–W system at 1200 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 33 (symbols as in Figure 71).	149

Figure 76 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–W system at 1300 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 34 (symbols as in Figure 71)..... 150

Figure 77 BSE image of alloy TAW8 (Ti-50.2Al-3.0W) heat-treated at a) 1000 °C and b) 1200 °C showing a TiAl matrix with bright (W) precipitates. 151

Figure 78 a) BSE image of alloy TAW10 (Ti-54.9Al-3.3W) heat-treated at 1200 °C showing a TiAl matrix with bright (W) precipitates; b) Bright-field image of TEM sample; c) HAADF image and d) TEM-EDS map with the $W_{M\alpha}$ line showing that the bright precipitates are W rich. 152

Figure 79 a) TEM-EDS measurements of alloys TAW8 and TAW10 (dark arrows) superimposed on the isothermal section of Ti–Al–W at 1000 °C; BSE image of alloy TAW10 b) in the as-cast state showing TiAl and a primarily solidified phase with (~4 at.% W) and b) the sample quenched from 900 C with a TiAl matrix and first indications of (W) formation. 153

Figure 80 Increase of the solubility of W in TiAl as a function of temperature for the alloys TAW4, TAW8 and TAW10 in the temperature range of 1000 to 1300 °C..... 155

List of Abbreviations

ACARE	A dvisory C ouncil for A viation R esearch and I nnovation in E urope
APB	A nti- P hase B oundary
APT	A tom P robe T omography
bcc	B ody C entered C ubic
BF	B right- F ield
BSE	B ack S cattered E lectrons
CALPHAD	C ALculation of P Hase D iagram
CVM	C luster V ariation M ethod
DTA	D ifferential T hermal A nalysis
DESY	D eutsches E lektronen S ynchrotron
DFT	D ensity F unctional T heory
EDS	E nergy D ispersive X - R ay S pectroscopy
EPMA	E lectron P robe M icro A nalysis
GEFTA	G ERman S ociety F or T hermal A nalysis
HAADF	H igh A ngle A nnular D ark F ield
HEMS	H igh- E nergy M aterials S cience
HEXRD	H igh- E nergy X - R ay D iffraction
ICP-AES	I nductively C oupled P lasma A tomic E mission S pectroscopy
PETRA III	P ositronen- E lektronen- T andem- R ing- A nlage III
SAED	S electd A rea E lectron D iffraction
SEM	S canning E lectron M icroscopy
TEM	T ransmission E lectron M icroscopy
XRD	X - R ay D iffraction

1 Introduction and Motivation

Mankind has always dreamed of flying, what started with Icarus and Daedalus, who wanted to imitate birds continued with successful glider flights of Otto Lilienthal. The invention of piston engines led to the invention of the first engine-powered aircraft by the Wright Brothers. Two terrible and horrific World Wars in the first half of the 20th century accelerated and revolutionized aircraft technology dramatically, leading to the turbine jet engines used in modern aircraft [1]. At the beginning of the 21st century, huge and heavy aircraft such as the Airbus A380 and the Boeing 787 “Dreamliner” were built, capable of carrying more than 300 people. However, in view of the growing awareness of climate change and the resulting need to reduce the emission of so-called greenhouse gases such as CO₂, this concept has been put to the test. Lighter, smaller, and more efficient aircraft and propulsion systems are key to meeting future sustainable air transport requirements with minimal negative environmental impact. Therefore, the Advisory Council for Aviation Research and Innovation in Europe (ACARE) has set the following goal for future aviation-related research: A 75 and 90% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions of CO₂ and NO_x per passenger kilometre, and a 65% reduction in perceived noise. These values relate to the typical emission values of an aircraft in the year 2000 [2].

A lighter turbine and a more efficient combustion process (less fuel consumption for the same thrust) would contribute significantly to achieving the set goals [3]. Therefore new, lightweight, high-temperature structural materials for turbine blades are crucial to reduce the weight of future turbine jet engines and increase their efficiency. Due to their lower density (3.9 - 4.2 g/cm³ depending on composition), titanium aluminide-based materials are a promising alternative to the currently used Ni-based alloys (7.7 - 9.0 g/cm³ depending on composition) in specific parts of the turbine [4-6]. Early research focussed mainly on two classes of single-phase alloys based on the Al-rich binary intermetallic compounds TiAl (tetragonal, *tP4*, *P4/mmm* [7]) and TiAl₃ (tetragonal, *tI8*, *I4/mmm* [8]). Alloys based on TiAl₃ were finally dropped, because it was not possible to reduce the brittleness of these alloys by adding alloying elements [9, 10] and the focus shifted towards Ti₃Al (hexagonal, *hP8*, *P6₃/mmc* [11]) + TiAl two-phase alloys, where the addition of elements such as Nb and Mo has proven to be more successful (more details in Section 2.2). The two TiAl-based alloys currently in use, 4822 (Ti-48Al-2Nb-2Cr; alloy compositions are always given in at.% throughout the text) [12] and TNM

(Ti-43.5Al-4Nb-1Mo-0.1B) [13], rely on the addition of at least one of these elements to be manufactured and to achieve the mechanical properties required for the application. During manufacturing, the phase equilibria above 1000 °C play an important role, while the phase equilibria below 900 °C influence the mechanical properties of the alloy at application temperature [4, 12-15]. Therefore, knowledge of phase equilibria in TiAl-based alloy system is crucial for improving current and developing new generations of alloys. These new alloy generations are designed for application temperatures between 800 and 900 °C [14, 16]. By increasing the application temperature of TiAl alloys, the number of Ni-based blades can be further reduced, resulting in a reduction in the overall weight of the turbine engine. This once again underlines the importance of knowing phase equilibria in TiAl-based alloy systems.

As pointed out, alloy development relies on experimental results. Even computational approaches such as the CALPHAD (CALculation of PHase Diagram) method [17], which has proven its potential in other material systems [18], rely on experimentally determined data on phase equilibria and thermodynamic variables as the bases for its calculations. This method is able to calculate phase equilibria for a large number of different compositions, and can significantly increase the development speed of new alloy generations. However, the accuracy of these calculations depends on the accuracy of the data used, further emphasising the importance of precise knowledge of phase equilibria for alloy development.

Besides the already mentioned elements Nb and Mo, W is another alloying element that was already used in early TiAl-based alloys [19] and is still discussed as an alloying element for the next generation of alloys [4]. Surprisingly, the available data about phase equilibria in the ternary systems Ti–Al–X (X = Nb, Mo, W) is often incomplete or contradictory. Each of these systems is different and has unique characteristics. Two ternary intermetallic phases ω_0 (“Ti₄NbAl₃” hexagonal, *hP6*, *P6₃/mmc*) [20] and O (“Ti₂AlNb” orthorhombic, *oC16*, *Cmcm*) [21] are stable in the Ti–Al–Nb system below 1000 °C. These phases form during cooling and have an extended homogeneity range in the application temperature range, which is why they must be considered in the alloy development process. Due to the complex and sluggish formation of these phases, there is not much information available about the phase equilibria of these phases below 900 °C. In the Ti–Al–Mo system, the ternary σ phase (tetragonal, *tP30*, *P4₂/mnm*) [22] is stable up to above 1100 °C. However, the formation of this phase is very sluggish due to its high Mo content of about 30 at.%, which leads to contradictory phase equilibria reported in the literature. In the Ti–Al–W system, most results are limited to the phase equilibria in tungsten-poor alloys near the binary Ti–Al system. There are no reports of a ternary

intermetallic phase and little is known about phase equilibria with possible tungsten-rich phases.

In order to better predict and understand the interactions of Nb, Mo, and W in new TiAl-based alloys a precise knowledge of the phase equilibria, especially in the application temperature range, is required. To address this, series of alloys were synthesised in each of these three systems. Heat treatments were carried out in 100 °C steps from 700 to 1300 °C for Ti–Al–Nb and between 800 and 1300 °C for the Ti–Al–Mo and Ti–Al–W system. Additional diffusion couple experiments were performed between 700 and 900 °C in the Ti–Al–Nb system. Particular attention was paid to minimizing the uptake of impurities during alloy synthesis and heat treatment, as impurities such as O, N, and C are known to significantly shift phase boundaries in TiAl-based systems [23-27]. Therefore, selected as-cast and heat-treated alloys were checked with inert gas fusion to ensure that the impurity levels are low. The overall compositions were determined either by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES) or electron probe microanalysis (EPMA). The heat-treated alloys were thoroughly characterized by various complementary methods such as EPMA, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), *in situ* and *ex situ* high energy X-ray diffraction (HEXRD), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The aim of these experimental investigations, in conjunction with available literature data, is to clarify inconsistencies in the individual systems, as well as to close existing gaps in the investigated systems regarding the phase equilibrium data. This resulted in a series of partial isothermal sections for each of the three investigated systems. In addition, some investigations on the influence of oxygen on phase equilibria at high temperatures in the Ti–Al–Nb system were performed. The occurrence of two ternary intermetallic phases in the Ti–Al–Nb system is another important issue. These phases form on cooling (and decompose on heating) in the application temperature range as result of solid-state reactions leading to complex phase relations below 1000 °C. The kinetics of these phase transformations were investigated in a systematic DTA study. The results will help to improve an existing CALPHAD database for TiAl-based alloys.

2 Fundamentals of TiAl-based alloys for high-temperature structural applications

Many aspects need to be considered when developing alloys for high-temperature structural applications, starting with basic considerations such as suitable and available materials as well as the suitable manufacturing processes. Size and geometry of the component, as well as the machinability of the material, play an important role in these considerations. It is therefore important that the material properties can be adjusted for room and application temperature to meet the desired requirements. A prerequisite for these considerations is the precise knowledge of the base material. Further, the influence of alloying elements and composition on the phase equilibria is essential. This knowledge enables manipulation of the microstructure through thermal or thermomechanical treatments to achieve the desired mechanical properties. However, this is a rather complex undertaking, as there are always some drawbacks in addition to the obvious effect of an alloying element.

The addition of Nb to binary TiAl-alloys, for example, significantly improves hot formability, but also promotes the retention and formation of undesirable phases in the microstructure at lower temperatures. To counteract this, other elements are added, which in turn can themselves have an undesirable effect. Therefore, the desired increase in application temperature while at the same time maintaining at least the same level of mechanical properties can only be achieved by a balanced ratio between the alloying elements. Due to the large number of possible alloying elements, there is a wide range of possible combinations. Knowledge of phase equilibria is a powerful tool to reduce the number of these combinations, because certain groups of elements show the same effects on the phase equilibria and thus on the material properties, the number of element combinations is reduced to a manageable level. This has made it possible to solve the “alloy development puzzle”, as evidenced by new generations of alloys developed [4, 5, 12].

The information obtained on phase equilibria can be graphically illustrated in the phase diagram. The phase diagram shows the phase relations under equilibrium conditions as a function of, for example, temperature. In the case of two- or multicomponent systems, this includes, among other things, homogeneity ranges of single and multi-phase fields, transformation type and temperature, melting temperature, and phase fractions at a certain composition. All of these are important variables for alloy development and once again underline the importance of accurate knowledge of phase equilibria as they contribute

significantly to the solving and avoiding of problems during the alloy development process. Therefore, the binary Ti–Al system as the basis of titanium aluminide alloys will be presented first, followed by an explanation of the ideas and challenges behind the current alloy concept.

2.1 The Ti–Al phase diagram

The binary Ti–Al phase diagram in Figure 1 shows the (α Ti), (β Ti), and (Al) solid-solutions and the four intermetallic phases Ti_3Al , TiAl , TiAl_2 , and TiAl_3 , some of which have extended homogeneity ranges. The crystallographic information of these phases is summarized in Table 1.

Figure 1 Binary Ti–Al phase diagram assessed by Schuster and Palm [28] modified with the information summarized by Palm [29].

In the binary Ti–Al phase diagram, two separated phase fields of (α Ti) are observed showing a considerable solubility for Al (Figure 1). Between these two (α Ti) phase fields, the homogeneity range of the hexagonal, $D0_{19}$ -ordered Ti_3Al phase field is located. This phase can be regarded as an ordered version of the hexagonal (α Ti) phase and is therefore often designated as α_2 in the literature. Ti_3Al does not form from the liquid phase, but for Al contents between 28 and 35 at.% by a peritectoid solid state reaction at 1200 °C from (α Ti) and (β Ti) [28, 29]. There is an ongoing discussion whether (β Ti) also exists as $B2$ -ordered variant (cubic, $cP2$,

Pm-3m; designated as “(βTi)_o”) in the binary system at higher temperatures. So far, there is no clear experimental evidence for *B2*-ordering of (βTi) in the binary Ti–Al system, but CALPHAD calculations suggest that (βTi)_o is stable when vacancies are included in the calculations [30]. This uncertainty is indicated by the broken phase boundary (βTi)/(αTi) + (βTi) between 1200 and 1250 °C (Figure 1). Ordering of (βTi)_o is observed in several ternary and multicomponent systems [31] and will be discussed later (Sections 4.3.1.1 and 5.3.2). Because the (βTi) solid solution shows a complete miscibility with the body centred cubic metals X = Nb, Mo, and W [32-34], which is not the case for Al, it is denoted ($\beta\text{Ti,X}$) in the respective Sections 4-6. The next phase in terms of Al content is TiAl which has a wide homogeneity range especially at high temperatures and is often referred to as γ in the literature. On the Al-rich side of the system, the two intermetallic phases TiAl₂ and TiAl₃ are observed. For the latter, a *D0*₂₃ low-temperature and a *D0*₂₂ high-temperature polymorph were observed experimentally [8], which has been confirmed by several density functional theory (DFT) calculations [35-38]. However, the reported values for the transition temperatures between these two polymorphs show a large scatter [28]. This is related to the existence of highly stable *D0*₂₂ stacking configurations in the *D0*₂₃ structure, which have been found both experimentally [39] and by calculation [35] to be stable even after long heat treatment times. Therefore, it is difficult to determine a transformation temperature between these polymorphs [28] and only the high-temperature *D0*₂₂ polymorph is listed in Table 1 and there is no transition temperature shown in Figure 1. With the lowest density of the intermetallic phases in the Ti–Al system, TiAl₃ has been of interest in the past for application as a high-temperature structural material, as mentioned earlier. However, due to its tetragonal crystal lattice, this phase is brittle. The idea was to substitute Al or Ti by other elements, which would lead to a cubic *L1*₂ superstructure [9, 10] that could reduce brittleness and improve deformability due to more available slip systems. These attempts were not successful. Therefore, a different approach was chosen for alloys consisting mainly of the also tetragonal TiAl and hexagonal Ti₃Al. By adding a third element, the phase itself was not to be changed, but the phase equilibria were to be altered so that a certain microstructure could be achieved. The idea behind this concept is explained in the next section.

Table 1 Crystallographic information for all phases of the binary Ti–Al system (Figure 1) with their crystal system, Pearson symbol, space group, and Strukturbericht designation.

Phase designation	Crystal system	Pearson symbol	Space group	Strukturbericht designation	Reference
(α Ti)	hexagonal	<i>hP2</i>	<i>P6₃/mmc</i>	A3	[40]
(β Ti)	cubic	<i>cI2</i>	<i>Im-3m</i>	A2	[40]
(β Ti) ₀		<i>cP2</i>	<i>Pm-3m</i>	B2	
Ti ₃ Al, α_2	hexagonal	<i>hP8</i>	<i>P6₃/mmc</i>	D0 ₁₉	[11]
TiAl, γ	tetragonal	<i>tP4</i>	<i>P4/mmm</i>	L1 ₀	[7]
TiAl ₂	tetragonal	<i>tI24</i>	<i>I4₁/amd</i>		[41]
TiAl ₃	tetragonal	<i>tI8</i>	<i>I4/mmm</i>	D0 ₂₂	[8]
(Al)	cubic	<i>cF4</i>	<i>Fm-3m</i>	A1	[40]

2.2 Manufacturing and alloying concept

The main challenge in the manufacturing of TiAl-based components is the low ductility at room temperature [12], which leads to difficulties in the production of TiAl-based components and requires complex processing routes. To ensure economic and sustainable production, established manufacturing processes such as near-net-shape casting and/or forging with subsequent heat treatment and machining are a prerequisite for the use of such components [4, 5, 14]. This imposes further constraints on alloy development, as the alloy must additionally be castable and readily deformable at high temperatures while maintaining its mechanical properties at application temperature. In the case of turbine blades forged from cast blanks, the alloy must meet the following requirements to have homogeneous and isotropic mechanical properties: i) no significant texture and minimal amount of peritectically solidified (α Ti) after casting of the forging blank; ii) good deformability during thermomechanical treatment; iii) thermomechanical treatment not performed in single-phase field; iv) well-balanced ratio of phase fractions of the intermetallic phases Ti₃Al and TiAl; v) thermally stable microstructure [12, 42].

The technically relevant alloys currently used have an Al content between 42–48 at.% [4]. Figure 1 shows that alloys in this composition range consist mainly of Ti₃Al and TiAl and their phase fraction can be adjusted by the Al content in the alloy. During casting, however, primarily solidified (α Ti) forms as a result of the peritectic reaction $L + (\beta\text{Ti}) \rightarrow (\alpha\text{Ti})$ at

1491 °C [28, 29]. Furthermore, these alloy compositions are mostly located in the single-phase (α Ti) or two-phase (α Ti) + TiAl phase field at temperatures where thermomechanical treatments (e.g. forging, rolling) are usually carried out. This can lead to abnormal grain growth [4] and the hexagonal crystal lattice cannot be deformed as easily as the cubic (β Ti) phase, for example. Therefore, so called (β Ti)-stabilizing elements are added. These elements increase the Al solubility in (β Ti) compared to the binary Ti–Al phase diagram. As can be seen in Figure 2, the addition of 8 at.% Nb extends the homogeneity range of (β Ti). Depending on the added element, this effect is differently pronounced [15]. A positive effect of the increased Al solubility is the change of the solidification sequence from $L \rightarrow L + (\beta\text{Ti}) \rightarrow (\alpha\text{Ti}) \rightarrow \dots$ to $L \rightarrow L + (\beta\text{Ti}) \rightarrow (\beta\text{Ti}) \rightarrow \dots$, which significantly reduces the amount of peritectically solidified (α Ti) and leads to an equiaxed, lamellar microstructure free of casting-texture at room temperature [43-47]. Furthermore, a higher phase fraction of (β Ti) is present at high temperature, which is advantageous for hot-workability [46, 48].

Figure 2 Binary Ti–Al phase diagram (dashed grey lines) from 30-60 at.% Al overlaid with quasibinary section from Chen et al. [49] at 8 at.% Nb (dark lines). The blue dashed lines indicate the Al content range (42-48 at.%) of the currently used TiAl-based alloys.

The addition of (β Ti)-stabilizing elements, however, does not only have advantages. At low temperatures, the brittle, $B2$ -ordered (β Ti)_o is retained in the microstructure and therefore its phase fraction must be as low as possible, as opposed to high temperatures. Furthermore, in the case of Nb, a ternary intermetallic phase forms from (β Ti) at lower temperatures (Sections 4.1 and 4.3), and has to be accounted for since it can lead to embrittlement [5]. Therefore, a set of different alloying elements is used, as described above, to prevent the formation of undesirable phases and to achieve the desired mechanical properties [4, 5, 50]. This is reflected in the formula describing the composition of 3rd generation TiAl-based alloys: Ti-(42-48)Al-(0-10)X-(0-3)Y-(0-1)Z-(0-0.5RE) with X = Cr, Mn, Nb, Ta; Y = Mo, W, Hf, Zr; Z = C, B, Si. RE denotes rare earth elements (Yttrium is used in most studies). Each of these elements has its specific purpose in the alloy. Elements in the groups X and Y are (β Ti)-stabilizing elements improving hot-workability, and are beneficial for properties such as oxidation and creep resistance, at the same time contributing to achieve the desired microstructure. The addition of the elements C, B, and Si leads to considerable strengthening of the material due to dispersion hardening. Rare earth elements, such as Y, result in better room temperature mechanical properties as a result of grain refinement [4, 5, 15]. As mentioned above, in order to understand and predict the interaction between the different elements, it is important to know the phase equilibria in the temperature range between 700 and 1300 °C. This once more emphasises the need for precise knowledge of phase equilibria. The results of the present investigations on the phase equilibria in the three ternary Ti–Al–X systems with X = Nb, Mo, and W are presented and evaluated in the context of existing literature in Sections 4-6. First, however, alloy synthesis, heat treatment and alloy characterisation will be presented in the next chapter.

3 Materials and experimental methods

3.1 Materials preparation

3.1.1 Alloy synthesis

Three different synthesis methods were used for alloy production: i) crucible-free levitation melting; ii) arc melting with a non-consumable tungsten electrode and tiltable crucible; iii) induction melting. Originally, it was intended to synthesize all alloys with the crucible-free levitation melting method, to avoid potential contamination from crucible materials. However, not all alloys could be produced with this method, as it was not possible to sufficiently superheat the melt once Ti and Al were molten, resulting in unmolten Nb and W remaining in the alloy. This phenomenon was not observed in the alloys produced with the arc melting method and the impurity levels were comparably low. For W-containing alloys, an induction melting process was additionally tested, as the nominal W contents were not achieved (Table 2). The syntheses were performed in Ar atmosphere using high purity elements Ti (99.995 wt.%), Al (99.999 wt.%), Nb (99.9 wt.%), Mo (99.95 wt.%), and W (99.95 wt.%) (HMW Hauner GmbH & Co. KG). In case of arc and levitation melting, the melts were cast into rod-shaped copper moulds (\varnothing 15 mm) resulting in samples with a length of approximately 160 mm and a weight of 200 - 300 g depending on the alloy composition. The alloys synthesized by induction melting had a size of approximately (\varnothing 3 x 30 mm³). To ensure chemical homogeneity, the alloys were turned over and remolten several times in the arc and induction melting furnace or levitated for a few minutes in the levitation melting device. To minimize the uptake of impurities, the Ar gas was additionally dried (ZPure M™ 3800cc, Chromatography research supplies) to remove remaining moisture and oxygen. Furthermore, the electric arc was ignited on a piece of pure Ti to getter the remaining oxygen before melting the pure elements in the arc melting furnace. All synthesized alloys are summarized in Table 2, indicating the synthesis method used. Besides the ternary alloys, binary Ti–Al and Ti–Nb alloys were synthesized for diffusion couple experiments in the Ti–Al–Nb system. The overall composition of selected as-cast alloys were measured with ICP-AES. In cases where no measured as-cast composition is given in Table 2 the composition of the alloy was determined in several heat-treated alloys by EPMA measurements (Section 3.1.2.1). For subsequent analysis and heat treatments, the alloys were cut into pieces using a disc cutter.

Table 2 Synthesized ternary Ti–Al–Nb (TAN1 to TAN17), Ti–Al–Mo (TAM1 to TAM13), Ti–Al–W (TAW1 to TAW10), and binary Ti–Al (TA1 and TA2) and Ti–Nb (TN2 to TN4) alloys with their nominal and measured compositions (ICP-AES) as well as their contents of impurity elements (O and C). The N contents were also analysed, the values were all below the detection limit of 50 wt. ppm and are therefore not listed here.

Alloy No.	Synthesis method	Nominal composition (at.%)			Measured as-cast composition (ICP-AES) (at.%)			Impurity contents (wt. ppm)	
		Ti	Al	X	Ti	Al	X	O	C
Ti–Al–Nb									
TAN1	Arc	77.5	17.5	5	77.8	17.4	4.8	290	130
TAN2	Arc	72.5	17.5	10	b			-	-
TAN3	Arc	62.5	20	17.5	b			220	-
TAN4	Arc	60	25	15	60.5	24.6	14.9	130	110
TAN5	Arc	50	25	25	b			-	-
TAN6	Arc	45	30	25	b			-	-
TAN7	Arc	54.5	33	12.5	55	32.8	12.2	180	85
TAN8	Arc	49	33	17.5	50.3	32.4	17.3	290	120
TAN9	Arc	53	37	10	52.8	37.2	10.0	160	86
TAN10	Arc	49.5	37	13.5	b			-	-
TAN11	Arc	50	40	10	50.4	39.6	10.0	290	160
TAN12	Arc	40	40	20	40.3	39.8	19.9	130	110
TAN13	Arc	50	45	5	50.7	43.4	4.9	150	108
TAN14	Levitation	47.5	45	7.5	48.3	45.8	5.9	140	89
TAN15	Arc	42.5	45	12.5	43.0	44.7	12.3	200	102
TAN16	Arc	60	35	5	b			-	-
TAN17	Arc	56	37	7	b			-	-
Ti–Al–Mo									
TAM1	Levitation	82.5	15	2.5	b			-	-
TAM2	Levitation	79	19	2	79.2	18.8	2.0	230	93
TAM3	Levitation	65	30	5	b			-	-
TAM4	Levitation	58	40	2	58.4	39.6	2.0	200	94
TAM5	Levitation	53.75	45	1.25	53.9	44.9	1.2	210	94
TAM6	Levitation	52.5	45	2.5	b			-	-

Alloy No.	Synthesis method	Nominal composition (at.%)			Measured as-cast composition (ICP-AES) (at.%)			Impurity contents (wt. ppm)	
		Ti	Al	X	Ti	Al	X	O	C
TAM7	Arc	51.75	45	3.75	51.7	44.6	3.7	250	92
TAM8	Levitation	50	45	5	^b			-	-
TAM9	Levitation	47.5	45	7.5	^b			-	-
TAM10	Arc	45	45	10	^b			-	-
TAM11	Arc	32	55	13	33.0	56.1	10.9	150	78
TAM12	Levitation	35	62	3	^b			-	-
TAM13	Arc	50	25	25	-	-	-	-	-
Ti–Al–W									
TAW1 ^a	Induction	63.75	25	11.25	65.6	28.3	6.1	-	-
TAW2 ^a	Induction	48	25	27	59.1	32.3	8.6	-	-
TAW3	Arc	57.5	40	2.5	58.5	40.0	1.5	125	82
TAW4	Arc	55	40	5	57.6	40.6	1.8	215	90
TAW5	Arc	53.75	45	1.25	53.9	45.0	1.1	250	101
TAW6	Arc	52.5	45	2.5	53.6	45.5	0.9	385	120
TAW7 ^a	Induction	49.0	42.5	8.5	48.8	47.1	4.1	-	-
TAW8	Arc	45	50	5	46.8	50.2	3.0	190	80
TAW9 ^a	Induction	37.5	42.5	20	42.6	50.8	6.6	-	-
TAW10	Arc	40	55	5	41.8	54.9	3.3	155	64
Ti–Al									
TA1 ^a	Levitation	57	43	0	57.1	42.9	0	110	-
TA2 ^a	Arc	50	50	0	50.5	49.5	0	160	-
Ti–Nb									
TN1 ^a	Arc	80	0	20	80.5	0	19.5	-	-
TN2 ^a	Arc	70	0	30	69.2	0	30.8	-	-
TN3 ^a	Arc	50	0	50	51.3	0	48.7	-	-

^a The as-cast composition was determined by EPMA, as described in Section 3.1.2.1, instead of ICP-AES.

^b Overall composition of several heat-treated alloys were checked by EPMA instead of the as-cast composition.

3.1.2 Heat treatments

3.1.2.1 Bulk alloys

In order to minimize impurity uptake during the heat treatments, two different setups were used depending on the heat treatment temperature: i) encapsulation in fused silica ampules up to 1100 °C, and ii) a so-called “double crucible technique” at higher temperatures [51] (Figure 3). Cylindrical samples 10 mm long were cut from the rods and encapsulated in fused silica ampules backfilled with Ti-gettered Ar gas for heat treatments between 700 and 1100 °C. At temperatures above 1100 °C, the fused silica is no longer sufficiently gas-tight for oxygen and nitrogen [52] and devitrification starts. Therefore, the double crucible technique [51] is used for heat treatments at 1200 and 1300 °C. The sample is wrapped with Ta foil and placed in an alumina crucible, which in turn is placed upside down in a larger crucible. The leftover space is filled with Ti filings which act as getter material. The Ta foil prevents contact between filings and the sample. Additionally, the reaction between Ta and the sample is very sluggish, so Ta was not found in any of the samples. In both cases the samples were quenched in brine by breaking the ampules/crucibles. The described schematic setup of the heat treatment methods is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Schematic setup of the sample encapsulation (on the left) for heat treatments at 700 to 1100 °C and the double crucible technique (on the right) for heat treatments above 1100 °C.

Using these two methods, the ternary alloys were heat treated between 700 and 1300 °C, as summarized in Table 3, indicating the heat treatment temperature and duration for each alloy and system.

Table 3 Overview of the heat-treated ternary alloys showing heat treatment temperature and time.

Alloy No.	Heat treatment time (h)						
	Encapsulation					Double crucible technique	
	700 °C	800 °C	900 °C	1000 °C	1100 °C	1200 °C	1300 °C
Ti–Al–Nb							
TAN1	1500	1000	650	400	200		
TAN2	1500	1000	650	400	200		
TAN3	1500	1000	650	400	200		
TAN4	1500	1000	650	400	200		
TAN5			1000	650	400	30	20
TAN6			1000	650	400	30	20
TAN7	1500	1000	650	400	200		
TAN8	1500	1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAN9	1500	1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAN10			1000	400	200	30	
TAN11	1500	1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAN12	1500	1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAN13	1500	1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAN14	1500	1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAN15	1500	1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAN16					400	30	
TAN17						30	
Ti–Al–Mo							
TAM1		1000	650	400			
TAM2		1000	650	400			
TAM3		1000	650	400	400		
TAM4		1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAM5		1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAM6		1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAM7		1000	650	400	200	30	20

Alloy No.	Heat treatment time (h)						
	Encapsulation					Double crucible technique	
	700 °C	800 °C	900 °C	1000 °C	1100 °C	1200 °C	1300 °C
TAM8		1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAM9		1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAM10		1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAM11 ^a		1000	650	400	200	30	20
TAM12					400	30	20
Ti–Al–W							
TAW1 ^b						30	
TAW2 ^b						30	20
TAW3		2000	2000	650	400	30	20
TAW4		2000	2000	650	400	30	20
TAW5				650	400	30	20
TAW6				650	400	30	20
TAW7						30	20
TAW8 ^b		2000	2000	650	400	30	20
TAW9						30	20
TAW10 ^b		2000	2000	650	400	30	20

^a This alloy was additional heat treatment at 900, 1000, 1100 °C for 1000, 650, 400 h respectively after homogenizing the sample at 1300 °C for 48 h, see Section 5.2

^b Parts of the heat-treated alloys were again heat treated at 1000, 1100, 1200, and 1300 °C for the same time, see Section 6.2

3.1.2.2 Diffusion couples

Two different types of diffusion couples were used to study the Ti–Al–Nb system: i) solid-solid diffusion couple at 900 °C; ii) liquid-solid diffusion couples at 700 and 800 °C (Figure 4). For the solid-solid diffusion couple, blocks (approx. 4 x 4 x 6 mm³) were cut from different binary alloys, their surfaces were ground with SiC paper and cleaned with ethanol. The pieces were then placed on top of each other and fixed with a Mo-clamp to ensure that they remain in contact during the subsequent heat treatment (Figure 4). Prior to heat treatment, the solid-solid diffusion couple was encapsulated as described for the bulk alloys and then air-cooled before breaking the fused silica ampules.

Figure 4 Schematic setup for solid-solid (top) and liquid-solid (bottom) diffusion couples. On the top right side, the solid-solid diffusion couple is shown before encapsulation (piece 1 is TN1 (Ti-20Nb), piece 2 is TA2 (Ti-50Al), and piece 3 is TN2 (Ti-30Nb)). A solidified liquid-solid diffusion couple after heat treatment is displayed on the bottom right side. Figure from Ref. [53].

In case of the liquid-solid diffusion couples, cylinders ($\text{Ø } 15 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$) of the three binary Ti–Nb alloys were placed on top of solid Al pieces in an alumina crucible. At the heat treatment temperatures of 700 and 800 °C, the Al is liquid and completely surrounds the binary Ti–Nb alloy forming the diffusion couple. A piece of Ta-foil was placed 10 mm above this setup to prevent direct contact between the liquid-solid diffusion couple and the added Ti filings during heat treatment. This setup was heat-treated in a vacuum furnace at 700 or 800 °C for 100 h followed by furnace cooling. The diffusion couple was then encapsulated for further heat

treatment until the desired heat treatment time was reached. This was possible because the total amount of liquid Al had reacted with the Ti–Nb after this time and no liquid phase was left. The different diffusion couple experiments are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4 Overview of investigated diffusion couples specifying the combination, type, temperature, and time.

Combination	Type	Temperature (°C)	Time (h)
TN1-Al	Liquid-solid	700	1150
TN2-Al	Liquid-solid	700	1150
TN2-Al	Liquid-solid	800	750
TN2-Al	Liquid-solid	800	750
TN3-Al	Liquid-solid	800	750
TN1-TA2-TN2	Solid-solid	900	400

3.2 Materials characterization

3.2.1 Chemical analysis

Inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES, Optima 8300, Perkin Elmer) was used to measure the overall composition of selected as-cast alloys by determining the contents of the pure elements (Ti, Al, Nb/Mo/W). This verified that the intended compositions were achieved and no evaporation of Al occurred. Additionally, the C content in the alloys were determined with the same method in some alloys. The O and N contents were determined by inert gas fusion (Fusionmaster ONH, NCS Germany) in selected as-cast as well as heat-treated alloys. For the analyses, 1-2 mm thick slices from the top and/or bottom of the alloy rods were used to check if the alloy is homogeneous. If the impurity content in the as-cast alloys was above 400 wt. ppm O and larger than 50 wt. ppm N, the alloy synthesis was repeated.

3.2.2 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Selected as-cast and heat-treated alloys were cut and metallographically prepared for characterisation using SEM. The samples were hot embedded (PolyFast, Struers) and ground with abrasive SiC paper from 220 to 2500 grit. They were then polished with polishing cloth

and 3/1 μm diamond suspension before final polishing with oxide polishing suspension (OPS). A Zeiss Leo 1550 VP, operated at 15 kV with a working distance of 6 mm, was used to image selected alloys with low- and high-magnification in back-scattered electron (BSE) contrast.

3.2.3 Electron probe micro analysis (EPMA)

Electron probe micro analysis was performed to determine the overall and phase compositions using a JEOL JXA-8100 micro analyser operated with an acceleration voltage of 15 kV, a probe current of 20 nA, and pure elements as standards ($K\alpha_1$ line of Ti and Al; $L\alpha_1$ line of Nb, Mo, and W). The samples were prepared using the same routine as described in Section 3.2.2.

3.2.3.1 Bulk alloys

At least three representative areas of the microstructure were scanned with grids (usual step size 20 μm), each consisting of at least 196 point measurements, to determine the overall composition of selected heat-treated samples by averaging all measurements. The phase compositions were determined by averaging at least 12 point measurements (probing volume $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}^3$) taken in different areas of the sample cross section. In a few cases where the phases were too small for direct point analyses (diameters $\leq 1 \mu\text{m}$), the phase compositions were estimated by an extrapolation based on a plot of the grid measurements made to determine the overall composition (Figure 5). In fine lamellar areas, a widened beam was used to determine the average composition of this area. The data of the overall and phase compositions were also used to determine the phase fractions by applying the lever rule for two- and three-phase alloys.

Figure 5 EPMA grid measurement data of a three-phase sample plotted in a composition triangle to determine the equilibrium phase compositions (red dots).

3.2.3.2 Diffusion couples

Line scans with a step size of 1 μm were measured by EPMA to determine the concentration profiles (Figure 6a) along the diffusion direction. The equilibrium phase compositions were determined by taking advantage of the fact that a local equilibrium exists at the interface of the different diffusion layers [54, 55]. Taking this into account, the composition of the respective phases can be determined by extrapolating the concentration to the phase boundaries (Figure 6b). The chemical composition of the intermetallic phases was determined by averaging the values of at least five line scans.

Figure 6 a) Typical concentration profile of a $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})/\text{TiAl}$ diffusion couple; b) magnified view of the concentration profile, with extrapolated equilibrium phase compositions marked, showing a composition jump corresponding to the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})/\text{Ti}_3\text{Al}$ interface in the diffusion couple.

3.2.4 Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA)

Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA) was used to investigate transition temperatures and kinetics of phase transformations with a Netzsch DSC 404C Pegasus thermal analyser (Selb, Germany). The device was calibrated with certified Al, Au, and Ni standards. Heating rates of 0.8, 1, 2, 5, and 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ were used for the measurements. The accuracy of the temperature measurements was regularly checked by melting Al (660 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and Au (1064 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). The deviations were ≤ 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in all cases, which is why an accuracy of ± 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ is assumed for all reported temperature values. Square-shaped samples with approximate dimensions of $3 \times 3 \times 2$ mm^3 were cut from as-cast and heat-treated alloys and cleaned with ethanol before the DTA experiments. The samples were placed into alumina crucibles and the measurements were performed in Ar atmosphere. The standard DTA experiment consisted of two heating and cooling cycles of heat-treated samples between room-temperature (RT) and 1300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. For low heating rates, the samples were first heated with 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to a temperature about 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ below the expected reaction and only the temperature range including the transformation was measured with the low rate. For each heating rate a new sample was used. The measurements were evaluated based on the recommendations given by the German society for thermal analysis GEFTA [56-58].

3.2.5 X-ray diffraction

3.2.5.1 Conventional X-ray diffraction (XRD)

To identify the phases present in the quenched samples, parts of the alloys were crushed to powder with a grain size $< 90 \mu\text{m}$. The powder was fixed to a glass plate with hairspray (does not cause additional reflection peaks) and then measured with a Bruker D8 Advanced A25-X1-1 diffractometer using $\text{CoK}\alpha_1$ ($\lambda = 1.78897 \text{ \AA}$) radiation in Bragg-Brentano geometry. The intensity of the diffracted beam was measured with a Lynxeye 1D detector after passing a Soller collimator with an acceptance angle of 0.3° . To improve the grain statistics, the sample was rotated during the measurement and data were recorded in the diffraction angle range $2\theta = 20^\circ$ to 130° with a step size of 0.01° . The data were then analysed using the TOPAS software package [59].

3.2.5.2 *In situ* and *ex situ* high-energy X-ray diffraction (HEXRD)

The *in situ* and *ex situ* high-energy X-ray diffraction (HEXRD) measurements were performed and evaluated by Dr. Katja Hauschildt from Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon. The measurements were performed at the High-Energy Materials Science (HEMS) beamline [60] operated by Hereon at the synchrotron storage ring PETRA III, DESY, Hamburg, Germany. For the *in situ* HEXRD measurements, cuboidal samples ($4 \times 4 \times 10 \text{ mm}^3$) were cut from the heat-treated alloys. The samples were set up in a modified quenching and deformation dilatometer DIL805A/D from TA Instruments. The measurements were performed under Ar atmosphere. The temperature was controlled with S- and B-type thermocouples spot welded to the specimen. For the room temperature measurements (*ex situ*), cylindrical samples with a diameter of 15 mm and varying thickness were used. During the exposure time of 100 s for one diffraction pattern, the samples were slowly rotated up to 180° to obtain a better grain statistic. The samples were measured in transmission with a photon energy of 100 keV ($\lambda = 0.124 \text{ \AA}$) and a beam size of 1 mm^2 . The diffraction patterns were recorded with a 2D PerkinElmer flat panel detector XRD 1621. The data were integrated over 360° azimuthal angle using the program Fit2d [61]. The data were analysed using the MAUD software package [62].

3.2.6 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

The transmission electron microscopy (TEM) investigations were performed and analysed by Dr. Boryana Rashkova at Montanuniversität Leoben. All specimens for TEM investigations were cut, ground, polished and subsequently electrolytically thinned to electron transparency using an electrolyte (A3) from Struers. Conventional TEM was carried out using a Philips CM12 instrument, operated at 120 kV, and a FEI Technai F20 field emission high resolution TEM, operated at 200 kV. The chemical composition of the phases was measured by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) using an EDAX (Mahwah, NJ, USA) detector system without additional standardization.

4 Phase equilibria, microstructure, phase stability and phase transformation kinetics in Ti–Al–Nb alloys

Since Nb is used as (β Ti)-stabilizing element in both commercial used TiAl-alloys (4822 and TNM), a precise knowledge of the phase equilibria in Ti–Al–Nb is of vital importance for urgently needed improvements of these alloys. The addition of Nb leads to the occurrence of intermetallic phases from the binary Nb–Al system [63] showing a high solubility of Ti. Furthermore, two ternary intermetallic compounds ω_0 (Ti_4NbAl_3 , hexagonal, $hP6$, $P6_3/mmc$ [20]) and O (Ti_2NbAl , orthorhombic, $oC16$, $Cmcm$ [21]) exist below 1000 °C. The crystallographic information of these phases, which occur in addition to those of the binary Ti–Al system (listed in Table 1), is summarised in Table 5. The (β Ti) phase is now denoted as (β Ti,Nb) to indicate the complete miscibility of Nb in (β Ti). In the ternary system, this phase also occurs in a $B2$ -ordered variant marked as (β Ti,Nb)_o. Especially the two ternary intermetallic compounds result in complex phase equilibria below 1000 °C. These phases form/decompose on cooling/heating by solid-solid transformations taking place at about 900 °C, which coincides with the upper limit of the envisaged application temperature for newly developed TiAl-based alloys. Since these transformations are sluggish, a precise knowledge of the transformation kinetics and equilibrium transformation temperatures is necessary to determine the complex phase equilibria below 1000 °C.

Table 5 Crystallographic information (crystal system, Pearson symbol, space group, and Strukturbericht designation) of the additional phases present in the Ti–Al–Nb system. These phases are observed in the microstructure, the isothermal sections, and reaction scheme as a result of the addition of Nb.

Phase designation	Crystal system	Pearson symbol	Space group	Strukturbericht designation	Reference
(β Ti,Nb)	cubic	$cI2$	$Im-3m$	$A2$	[40]
(β Ti,Nb) _o		$cP2$	$Pm-3m$	$B2$	
Nb_2Al	tetragonal	$tP30$	$P4_2/mnm$	$D8_b$	[64]
Nb_3Al	cubic	$cP8$	$Pm-3n$	$A15$	[65]
NbAl_3	tetragonal	$tI4$	$I4/mmm$	$D0_{22}$	[8]
Ti_4NbAl_3 , ω_0	hexagonal	$hP6$	$P6_3/mmc$	$B8_2$	[20]
Ti_2NbAl , O	orthorhombic	$oC16$	$Cmcm$		[21]

In the following, the phase equilibria between 700 and 900 °C are described first (Section 4.1), followed by those in the temperature range between 1000 and 1300 °C (Section 4.2). This covers the entire temperature range relevant for alloy development. The results of a systematic DTA study on the solid-solid phase transformations in the Ti–Al–Nb system are presented in Section 4.3. Finally, the influence of oxygen on the phase equilibria at high temperatures was investigated by comparison of own experimental results and results available in literature (Section 4.4). Based on the presented results a reaction scheme for the Ti–Al–Nb system is presented in Section 4.5.

4.1 Low-temperature phase equilibria between 700 and 900 °C¹

4.1.1 Literature review

Experimental work on (in most cases partial) isothermal sections in the temperature range between 700 and 900 °C was reported by several authors [66-71]. Pavlov et al. [66] studied phase equilibria in a series of Nb-rich alloys heat-treated at 900 °C. Their results are limited exclusively to the Nb-corner of the system (< 40 at.% Ti). Rowe et al. [67] were interested in the solubility of Al in the (β Ti,Nb) solid solution and its phase relations to the ternary O phase at 900 °C. They established a partial isothermal section in the range of about 5-25 at.% Al and 10-40 at.% Nb showing the equilibria between (β Ti,Nb), Ti₃Al, and the O phase including the three-phase equilibrium. Miracle et al. [68] studied some alloys in the same composition range (fixed Al content of 22 at.% Al), but their data did not allow to determine the (β Ti,Nb) + Ti₃Al + O triangle. In his doctoral thesis, Sadi [69] performed experimental investigations on phase equilibria in the temperature range 700-900 °C using seven Ti–Al–Nb alloys in the composition range of the O and ω_o phase. Even though he determined various tie-triangles and tie-lines, his data are partially inconsistent, probably because he obtained the phase compositions by different techniques such as energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy in a scanning electron microscope (SEM-EDS), EPMA, and TEM-EDS. This might also explain, why the isothermal sections which he presented in his thesis and in later publications [70, 72] relied on calculations based on the thermodynamic database of Servant and Ansara [73] and not on his own experimental data. The only complete isothermal

¹ This chapter is based on the following publication: [53] B. Distl, K. Hauschildt, B. Rashkova, F. Pyczak, and F. Stein, Phase equilibria in the Ti-rich part of the Ti–Al–Nb system Part I. Low-temperature phase equilibria between 700 and 900 °C *Journal of Phase Equilibria and Diffusion* 2022, doi: 10.1007/s11669-022-00963-8

section in the 700-900 °C temperature range based on experimental work was presented recently by Xu et al. [71]. They derived local phase equilibria from extrapolations to phase interfaces obtained in a diffusion multiple consisting of Ti, Nb, Ti-73Al, Ti-40Nb, and Ti-60Nb annealed at 900 °C for 6000 h. No experimental sections for 700 and 800 °C were reported in the literature.

Some information on equilibria at these temperatures is available from vertical sections reported in the literature, but almost all of them are limited to the range of the O phase along constant Al contents of 22 at.% [68, 74-76], 25 at.% [77-79], and 27.5 at.% [80]. Only exceptions are a vertical section along 50 at.% Ti from Bendersky et al. [81] and a section along 8 at.% Nb presented by Xu et al. [82]. However, in case of the 50 at.% Ti section, this is only an estimated schematic based on two alloys [81], and in case of the 8 at.% Nb section, the authors mention that “because of the actual preparation process, the experimental isopleth showed metastable phase behaviour” [82].

Based on the experimental data available at the time, isothermal sections were also obtained using thermodynamic modelling. In 1992, Kattner and Boettinger [83] presented a rough isothermal section at 700 °C. Their thermodynamic description was slightly updated some years later by Servant and Ansara [73] and finally another updated description was reported in 2009 by Witusiewicz et al. [84]. However, the calculated sections at 700 to 900 °C still cannot describe the experimental data very well, as was also recently noted by Xu et al. [71]. A major reason for this may be, on the one hand, the partial inconsistency of the available experimental data and, on the other hand, the lack of such data in certain compositional ranges.

In the following sections, the results of the present investigations are shown. The resulting partial isothermal sections are then compared and discussed with the above mentioned results from literature.

4.1.2 Results

The phase and alloy compositions obtained by the EPMA measurements on the ternary bulk alloys (Table 2 Ti–Al–Nb part) and diffusion couples (Table 4) heat-treated between 700 and 900 °C, are summarized in Tables 6-9 along with the phase fractions and measured lattice parameters of all phases. The compositions given in the following text together with the alloy designations are always those measured in the as-cast condition (Table 2 Ti–Al–Nb part). The

actual overall compositions of the heat-treated samples are given in the respective Tables 6-8 and may slightly differ from the as-cast values. Figure 7 shows the overall composition of the bulk alloys as well as the composition of the binary starting materials for the diffusion couple studies listed in Table 2 plotted in the ternary composition triangle.

Figure 7 As-cast alloy composition (Table 2) of the ternary bulk alloys (TAN1-TAN15, black stars) and the compositions of the binary single-phase alloys (TA2 and TN1-TN3; grey circles), for diffusion-couple investigations, plotted in the ternary composition triangle.

Table 6 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 700 °C for 1500 h (accuracy of the lattice parameters is $\pm 0.001 \text{ \AA}$, n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)	Pearson symbol	Lattice parameters (\AA)		
			Al	Nb			a	b	c
TAN1	Ti-17.6Al-4.8Nb	(α Ti)	17.0 ± 1.0^c	4.3 ± 1.0^c	34	<i>hP2</i>	n.d.		n.d.
		(β Ti,Nb)	12.5 ± 1.0^c	11.0 ± 1.0^c	6	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.		
		Ti ₃ Al	18.4 ± 1.0^c	4.5 ± 1.0^c	61	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.		n.d.
TAN2	Ti-18.2Al-9.9Nb	(β Ti,Nb)	10.0 ± 1.0^d	18.0 ± 1.0^d	30	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.		
		Ti ₃ Al	21.3 ± 0.4	6.5 ± 0.3	70	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.		n.d.
TAN3	Ti-19.4Al-17.4Nb	(β Ti,Nb)	8.1 ± 0.6	35.4 ± 0.7	29	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.		
		Ti ₃ Al	23.5 ± 0.3	10.4 ± 0.6	71	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.		n.d.
TAN4	Ti-24.7Al-14.6Nb	Ti ₃ Al	25.2 ± 1.0^d	12.4 ± 1.0^d	41	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.		n.d.
		O	24.0 ± 1.0^d	16.2 ± 1.0^d	59	<i>oC16</i>	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
TAN7	Ti-32.7Al-11.6Nb	Ti ₃ Al	29.0 ± 1.0^d	11.0 ± 1.0^d	4 ^f	<i>hP8</i>	5.798		4.666
		ω_o	32.9 ± 1.0^d	11.6 ± 1.0^d	96 ^f	<i>hP6</i>	4.581		5.533
TAN8	Ti-32.8Al-16.8Nb	O	28.0 ± 1.0^d	20.0 ± 1.0^d	2 ^f	<i>oC16</i>	6.055	9.614	4.647
		ω_o	32.9 ± 0.4	16.7 ± 1.0	98 ^f	<i>hP6</i>	4.587		5.519
TAN9	Ti-36.4Al-9.7Nb	Ti ₃ Al	35.0 ± 1.0^d	9.5 ± 1.0^d	1 ^f	<i>hP8</i>	5.773		4.676
		TiAl	45.0 ± 1.0^d	8.0 ± 1.0^d	21 ^f	<i>tP4</i>	4.010		4.075
		ω_o	34.1 ± 0.6	10.5 ± 0.4	78 ^f	<i>hP6</i>	4.578		5.536
TAN11	Ti-39.8Al-9.4Nb	Ti ₃ Al	35.0 ± 1.0^d	9.5 ± 1.0^d	5 ^f	<i>hP8</i>	-		-
		TiAl	44.7 ± 0.5	8.0 ± 0.6	44 ^f	<i>tP4</i>	4.017		4.077
		ω_o	35.4 ± 0.7	10.3 ± 0.7	51 ^f	<i>hP6</i>	4.581		5.530
TAN12 ^a	Ti-39.6Al-20.0Nb	TiAl	43.7 ± 0.8	17.2 ± 1.0	48	<i>tP4</i>	4.021		4.080
		ω_o	36.0 ± 0.7	20.6 ± 1.1	42	<i>hP6</i>	4.595		5.498
		Nb ₂ Al	33.0 ± 1.0^e	37.0 ± 2^e	10	<i>tP30</i>	-		-
TAN13 ^b	Ti-44.3Al-4.9Nb	Ti ₃ Al	35.7 ± 0.8	6.8 ± 0.6	17	<i>hP8</i>	5.735		4.660
		TiAl	46.1 ± 0.7	4.4 ± 0.4	83	<i>tP4</i>	4.022		4.066

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)	Pearson symbol	Lattice parameters (Å)		
			Al	Nb			a	b	c
TAN14 ^b	Ti-45.8Al-5.2Nb	Ti ₃ Al	35.6 ± 0.6	8.4 ± 0.3	12	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.		n.d.
		TiAl	46.9 ± 0.6	5.3 ± 0.2	88	<i>tP4</i>	n.d.		n.d.
TAN15 ^a	Ti-44.5Al-11.7Nb	TiAl	46.0 ± 1.1	11.3 ± 1.4	86	<i>tP4</i>	4.028		4.069
		ω _o	35.0 ± 0.7	15.2 ± 0.6	14	<i>hP6</i>	4.587		5.516

^a Sample contains a small amount (≤ 2 vol.%) of Ti₃Al which is not an equilibrium phase, see Section 4.1.2

^b Sample contains a small amount (≤ 1 vol.%) of ω_o which is not an equilibrium phase, see Section 4.1.2

^c Microstructure too fine (particles < 1 μm) to determine phase composition by single spot EPMA measurements; phase composition approximated with the help of grid measurements

^d Phase compositions approximated taking into account tie-line data from nearby alloys and diffusion couples and/or phase fractions from HEXRD measurements, see Section 4.1.2

^e Phase composition is estimated, see Section 4.1.2

^f Phase fractions determined with HEXRD

Table 7 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 800 °C for 1000 h (accuracy of the lattice parameters is ± 0.001 Å, n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)	Pearson symbol	Lattice parameters (Å)		
			Al	Nb			a	b	c
TAN1	Ti-17.5Al-4.7Nb	(αTi)	17.0 ± 1.0 ^c	4.3 ± 1.0 ^c	35	<i>hP2</i>	2.929		4.678
		(βTi,Nb)	11.6 ± 1.0 ^c	10.8 ± 1.0 ^c	4	<i>cI2</i>	- ^f		
		Ti ₃ Al	18.1 ± 1.0 ^c	4.6 ± 1.0 ^c	60	<i>hP8</i>	5.808		4.667
TAN2	Ti-18.1Al-9.5Nb	(βTi,Nb)	10.6 ± 0.7	15.6 ± 0.7	36	<i>cI2</i>	- ^f		
		Ti ₃ Al	22.3 ± 0.3	6.1 ± 0.2	64	<i>hP8</i>	5.801		4.667
TAN3	Ti-20.2Al-16.3Nb	(βTi,Nb)	11.8 ± 0.5	28.1 ± 0.8	33	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.		
		Ti ₃ Al	24.1 ± 0.1	10.9 ± 0.4	67	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.		n.d.
TAN4	Ti-24.9Al-14.1Nb	Ti ₃ Al	25.5 ± 1.0 ^c	12.3 ± 1.0 ^c	44	<i>hP8</i>	5.804		4.657
		O	24.5 ± 0.3	15.5 ± 0.9	56	<i>oC16</i>	5.946	9.779	4.669
TAN7	Ti-32.3Al-11.8Nb	Ti ₃ Al	29.0 ± 1.0 ^c	11.0 ± 1.0 ^c	5 ^e	<i>hP8</i>	5.785		4.669
		ω _o	32.5 ± 1.0 ^c	11.8 ± 1.0 ^c	95 ^e	<i>hP6</i>	4.579		5.527

		Ti ₃ Al	27.0 ± 1.0 ^d	12.0 ± 1.0 ^d	1 ^e	<i>hP8</i>	-	-	
TAN8	Ti-32.7Al-17.0Nb	O	28.0 ± 1.0 ^d	20.0 ± 1.0 ^d	5 ^e	<i>oC16</i>	6.065	9.621	4.662
		ω _o	32.9 ± 1.0 ^d	17.0 ± 1.0 ^d	94 ^e	<i>hP6</i>	4.587		5.510
		Ti ₃ Al	34.5 ± 1.0 ^d	9.5 ± 1.0 ^d	1	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.		n.d.
TAN9	Ti-36.1Al-9.7Nb	TiAl	45.0 ± 1.0 ^d	7.7 ± 1.0 ^d	13	<i>tP4</i>	n.d.		n.d.
		ω _o	34.8 ± 0.8	10.0 ± 0.6	86	<i>hP6</i>	n.d.		n.d.
		Ti ₃ Al	34.5 ± 1.0 ^d	9.5 ± 1.0 ^d	3 ^e	<i>hP8</i>	5.757		4.676
TAN11	Ti-39.5Al-9.5Nb	TiAl	44.9 ± 1.1	7.4 ± 0.4	50 ^e	<i>tP4</i>	4.017		4.071
		ω _o	34.6 ± 0.8	11.1 ± 0.5	47 ^e	<i>hP6</i>	4.579		5.528
		TiAl	45.3 ± 0.1	16.6 ± 0.4	46	<i>tP4</i>	4.076		4.080
TAN12 ^a	Ti-39.9Al-19.3Nb	ω _o	35.0 ± 0.9	20.6 ± 0.6	46	<i>hP6</i>	4.595		5.497
		Nb ₂ Al	37.0 ± 0.5	27.7 ± 0.4	8	<i>tP30</i>	9.927		5.131
		Ti ₃ Al	33.2 ± 0.6	8.2 ± 0.3	18	<i>hP8</i>	5.752		4.652
TAN13 ^b	Ti-43.5Al-5.1Nb	TiAl	45.6 ± 0.2	4.8 ± 0.1	82	<i>tP4</i>	4.020		4.064
		Ti ₃ Al	34.1 ± 0.9	9.2 ± 0.4	11	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.		n.d.
TAN14	Ti-44.4Al-6.0Nb	TiAl	45.6 ± 0.4	5.7 ± 0.2	89	<i>tP4</i>	n.d.		n.d.
		TiAl	45.9 ± 0.4	10.6 ± 0.5	79	<i>tP4</i>	4.023		4.068
TAN15 ^a	Ti-43.3Al-12.2Nb	ω _o	33.5 ± 0.6	16.9 ± 0.6	21	<i>hP6</i>	4.584		5.511

^a Sample contains a small amount (≤ 2 vol.%) of Ti₃Al which is not an equilibrium phase, see Section 4.1.2

^b Sample contains a small amount (≤ 1 vol.%) of ω_o which is not an equilibrium phase., see Section 4.1.2

^c Microstructure too fine (particles < 1μm) to determine phase composition by single spot EPMA measurements; phase composition approximated with the help of grid measurements

^d Phase compositions approximated taking into account tie-line data from nearby alloys and diffusion couples and/or phase fractions from HEXRD measurements, see Section 4.1.2

^e Phase fractions determined with HEXRD

^f (βTi,Nb) transformed to α' martensite during quenching. Therefore, no lattice parameters could be determined for (βTi,Nb)

Table 8 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 900 °C for 650 h (1000 h in case of TAN5, TAN6, and TAN10) (accuracy of the lattice parameters is $\pm 0.001 \text{ \AA}$, n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)	Pearson symbol	Lattice parameters (\AA)		
			Al	Nb			a	b	c
TAN1	Ti-17.7Al-4.7Nb	(α Ti)	17.6 ± 0.5	3.7 ± 0.1	49	<i>hP2</i>	2.917		4.675
		(β Ti,Nb)	13.3 ± 0.2	8.1 ± 0.2	22	<i>cI2</i>	- ^f		
		Ti ₃ Al	21.1 ± 0.5	3.9 ± 0.2	29	<i>hP8</i>	5.805		4.667
TAN2	Ti-17.5Al-10Nb ^d	(β Ti,Nb)	12.8 ± 0.2	13.2 ± 0.2	53	<i>cI2</i>	- ^f		
		Ti ₃ Al	22.2 ± 0.4	6.2 ± 0.4	47	<i>hP8</i>	5.798		4.666
TAN3	Ti-20Al-17.5Nb ^d	(β Ti,Nb)	15.3 ± 0.5	22.1 ± 0.4	56	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.		
		Ti ₃ Al	23.7 ± 0.5	11.1 ± 0.2	44	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.		n.d.
TAN4	Ti-24.8Al-14.5Nb	(β Ti,Nb) _o	16.9 ± 0.1	23.6 ± 0.2	3	<i>cP2</i>	3.261		
		Ti ₃ Al	25.0 ± 0.2	12.7 ± 0.6	17	<i>hP8</i>	5.796		4.664
		O	25.0 ± 0.1	14.6 ± 0.5	80	<i>oC16</i>	5.945	9.780	4.668
TAN5	Ti-23.5Al-26.7Nb	(β Ti,Nb)	16.8 ± 0.7	33.5 ± 0.7	18	<i>cI2</i>	3.261		
		O	25.3 ± 0.1	24.3 ± 0.5	82	<i>oC16</i>	6.065	9.600	4.670
TAN6 ^a	Ti-28.9Al-25.3Nb	O	28.8 ± 0.6	24.9 ± 1.3	96	<i>oC16</i>	6.11 ^g	9.53 ^g	4.65 ^g
		Nb ₂ Al	32.6 ± 0.3	31.7 ± 0.7	4	<i>tP30</i>	9.94 ^g		5.14 ^g
	Ti ₃ Al	29.2 ± 0.6	12.5 ± 0.9	20	<i>hP8</i>	5.78 ^g		4.67 ^g	
	Ti-30.3Al-22.5Nb	O	28.2 ± 0.8	20.2 ± 0.9	40	<i>oC16</i>	6.11 ^g	9.53 ^g	4.65 ^g
		Nb ₂ Al	33.0 ± 0.4	30.0 ± 0.8	40	<i>tP30</i>	9.94 ^g		5.14 ^g
TAN7	Ti-33.2Al-11.7Nb	Ti ₃ Al	32.8 ± 0.7	9.0 ± 0.4	42	<i>hP8</i>	5.779		4.651
		ω_o	33.5 ± 0.2	12.4 ± 0.5	58	<i>hP6</i>	4.579		5.527
TAN8 ^b	Ti-32.6Al-16.9Nb	Ti ₃ Al	30.7 ± 0.2	12.8 ± 0.3	8	<i>hP8</i>	5.785		4.664
		O	30.5 ± 0.2	17.9 ± 0.4	20	<i>oC16</i>	6.065	9.600	4.662
		ω_o	33.4 ± 0.4	17.1 ± 0.4	72	<i>hP6</i>	4.580		5.534
TAN9	Ti-36.6Al-9Nb	Ti ₃ Al	34.6 ± 0.8	8.3 ± 0.2	57	<i>hP8</i>	5.775		4.643
		TiAl	45.1 ± 0.3	7.8 ± 0.1	19	<i>tP4</i>	4.026		4.061
		ω_o	34.3 ± 0.8	11.7 ± 0.3	24	<i>hP6</i>	4.576		5.538

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)	Pearson symbol	Lattice parameters (Å)		
			Al	Nb			a	b	c
TAN10 ^c	Ti-37Al-13.5Nb ^d	(βTi,Nb) _o	35.0 ± 0.2 ^e	13.9 ± 0.2 ^e	80	<i>cP2</i>	3.222		
		TiAl	45.2 ± 0.5	9.6 ± 0.2	15	<i>tP4</i>	4.010		4.054
		ω _o	35.0 ± 0.2 ^e	13.9 ± 0.2 ^e	5	<i>hP6</i>	n.d.		n.d.
TAN11	Ti-39.5Al-9.3Nb	Ti ₃ Al	35.9 ± 0.5	8.4 ± 0.2	1	<i>hP8</i>	5.775		4.643
		TiAl	45.3 ± 0.3	8.0 ± 0.2	47	<i>tP4</i>	4.027		4.063
		ω _o	34.1 ± 0.6	10.5 ± 0.4	52	<i>hP6</i>	4.576		5.533
TAN12 ^c	Ti-40.0Al-20.3Nb	TiAl	45.4 ± 0.6	11.4 ± 0.8	47	<i>tP4</i>	4.025		4.067
		Nb ₂ Al	35.6 ± 0.6	28.5 ± 0.8	53	<i>tP30</i>	9.921		5.133
TAN13	Ti-43.4Al-4.9Nb	Ti ₃ Al	35.4 ± 0.4	5.3 ± 0.3	25	<i>hP8</i>	5.769		4.649
		TiAl	45.8 ± 0.6	5.1 ± 0.3	75	<i>tP4</i>	4.027		4.066
TAN14	Ti-45.8Al-5.9Nb	Ti ₃ Al	36.5 ± 0.5	6.1 ± 0.2	6	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.		n.d.
		TiAl	46.4 ± 0.2	5.8 ± 0.3	94	<i>tP4</i>	n.d.		n.d.
TAN15 ^c	Ti-44.7Al-12.3Nb	TiAl	45.3 ± 0.5	11.8 ± 0.5	94	<i>tP4</i>	4.030		4.067
		ω _o	34.5 ± 0.3	17.6 ± 0.3	6	<i>hP6</i>	4.589		5.516

^a Sample consists of two parts with different composition, see Section 4.1.2

^b Furnace temperature must have been slightly below 900 °C; observed phases belong to the equilibrium state below 897 °C, at which temperature the transition reaction (βTi,Nb)_o + Ti₃Al ⇌ O + ω_o takes place, see Sections 4.1.2 and 4.1.3.2.5

^c Sample contains a small amount of Ti₃Al, which is not an equilibrium phase, see Section 4.1.2

^d Alloy composition after heat treatment not determined; therefore, the nominal composition of the alloy is given, which is also used to determine the phase fractions

^e (βTi,Nb)_o and ω_o compositions cannot be distinguished

^f (βTi,Nb) transformed to α' martensite during quenching. Therefore, no lattice parameters could be determined for (βTi,Nb)

^g HEXRD averages the slightly different lattice parameters of the two regions, which is why the accuracy here is one order of magnitude lower

Table 9 Extrapolated equilibrium compositions as obtained from the diffusion couples 700 °C/1150 h, 800 °C/750 h, and 900 °C/400 h.

Temperature (°C)	Diffusion couple	Phases	Phase compositions determined from line scans (at.%)			
			Phase 1		Phase 2	
			Al	Nb	Al	Nb
700	TN1-Al	(β Ti,Nb) + Ti ₃ Al	10.0 ± 1.0	19.0 ± 1.0	20.6 ± 0.5	8.4 ± 0.5
		Ti ₃ Al + TiAl	34.4 ± 0.3	6.8 ± 0.6	46.7 ± 1.1	3.2 ± 1.1
700	TN2-Al (path 1) ^a	(β Ti,Nb) + O	7.5 ± 2.0	39.5 ± 2.0	25.0 ± 2.0	21.0 ± 2.0
		O + ω_0	28.0 ± 2.0	17.0 ± 2.0	b	b
		ω_0 + TiAl	b	b	44.0 ± 2.0	9.0 ± 2.0
700	TN2-Al (path 2) ^a	(β Ti,Nb) + Ti ₃ Al	6.5 ± 0.7	35.5 ± 1.7	24.0 ± 0.5	10.8 ± 0.5
		Ti ₃ Al + ω_0	26.2 ± 1.0	10.8 ± 1.9	33.0 ± 2.0	11.8 ± 2.0
		ω_0 + TiAl	35.0 ± 2.0	13.0 ± 2.0	48.0 ± 2.0	9.5 ± 2.0
800	TN1-Al	(β Ti,Nb) + Ti ₃ Al	9.9 ± 0.1	17.0 ± 0.3	22.3 ± 1.0	6.4 ± 0.2
		Ti ₃ Al + TiAl	35.8 ± 0.3	6.2 ± 0.2	46.2 ± 0.4	4.2 ± 0.3
800	TN2-Al	(β Ti,Nb) + Ti ₃ Al	11.4 ± 0.1	29.9 ± 0.8	24.8 ± 0.6	11.3 ± 0.6
		Ti ₃ Al + ω_0	27.7 ± 0.3	11.4 ± 0.1	33.6 ± 0.2	13.9 ± 0.6
		ω_0 + TiAl	35.4 ± 0.5	13.1 ± 0.4	45.5 ± 0.1	7.7 ± 0.4
800	TN3-Al	(β Ti,Nb) + O	11.5 ± 0.4	48.5 ± 0.6	25.5 ± 0.4	28.0 ± 0.7
		O + Nb ₂ Al	27.0 ± 0.6	25.8 ± 0.6	30.3 ± 0.3	39.2 ± 0.8
		Nb ₂ Al + TiAl	37.2 ± 1.0	31.1 ± 0.1	49.0 ± 0.4	18.9 ± 0.6
900	TN1-TA2	(β Ti,Nb) + Ti ₃ Al	14.2 ± 0.6	11.2 ± 0.3	21.5 ± 0.6	4.4 ± 0.5
		Ti ₃ Al + TiAl	36.0 ± 0.4	0.0 ± 0.5	47.2 ± 1.0	0.0 ± 0.2
900	TN2-TA2	(β Ti,Nb) + Ti ₃ Al	14.7 ± 0.1	18.1 ± 0.6	23.7 ± 0.6	8.4 ± 0.8
		Ti ₃ Al + TiAl	36.3 ± 0.3	0.0 ± 0.5	46.7 ± 0.5	0.0 ± 0.2

^a Two different diffusion paths are observed in this diffusion couple. Because of the sometimes very thin diffusion zones, the accuracy of the extrapolated compositions is reduced to ± 2.0 at.% in some cases.

^b Diffusion layer too thin to perform a reliable extrapolation to the interfaces with the O phase and TiAl

Alloy TAN1 (Ti-17.4Al-4.8Nb) exhibits a three-phase microstructure at all three temperatures investigated, as can be seen in Figure 8a-c. The phases present were identified to be (α Ti), (β Ti,Nb), and Ti₃Al by HEXRD measurements of quenched samples.

In alloys TAN2 (Ti-17.5Al-10Nb) and TAN3 (Ti-20Al-17.5Nb), a two-phase microstructure ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) + Ti_3Al is observed after heat treatments at 700 to 900 °C. This was also confirmed both by *in situ* HEXRD (for alloy TAN2) and room-temperature HEXRD on the quenched samples. The microstructures of the heat-treated alloys TAN2 and TAN3 show large ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) grains with Ti_3Al at the grain boundaries and small Ti_3Al precipitates inside the grains (Figure 9a,b), which have the same composition. The extension and position of the ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) + Ti_3Al two-phase field are confirmed by the diffusion couple experiments in the entire temperature range (Table 9).

Figure 8 Back-scattered electron (BSE) images of alloy TAN1 (Ti-17.4Al-4.8Nb) heat-treated at a) 700 °C/1500 h, b) 800 °C/1000 h, c) 900 °C/650 h showing a three-phase microstructure of (αTi) (grey), ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) (bright), and Ti_3Al (dark).

Figure 9 BSE images of the microstructure of alloy TAN2 (Ti-17.5Al-10Nb) heat-treated at a) 700 °C for 1500 h and b) 900 °C for 650 h with (βTi,Nb) (bright) and Ti₃Al (dark).

In alloys TAN4 to TAN6, the ternary O phase occurs as equilibrium phase. After heat treatment at 900 °C, alloy TAN4 (Ti-24.6Al-14.9Nb) exhibits a three-phase microstructure consisting of the bright (βTi,Nb)_o phase (whose *B2*-ordering was confirmed by *in situ* HEXRD) and large O phase grains (grey) with fine, mostly plate-like Ti₃Al precipitates (black) inside (Figure 10a). On a TEM bright-field image (Figure 10b) of a respective grain, the plate-like morphology of the Ti₃Al precipitates is well visible, also indicating the existence of an orientation relationship between the two phases, which is not determined in this work. The compositional differences were confirmed by TEM-EDS and in some parts of the microstructure the phases were big enough to be measured by EPMA. Furthermore, the *in situ* HEXRD measurements show that the (βTi,Nb)_o phase appears at about 880 °C during heating. These results confirm the observations made in the microstructure of alloy TAN4, where (βTi,Nb)_o is only present at 900 °C, while at 700 and 800 °C the alloy is two-phase Ti₃Al + O.

Alloy TAN5 (Ti-25Al-25Nb) was heat-treated at 900 °C for 1000 h revealing a two-phase equilibrium between (βTi,Nb) and the O phase. No heat treatments were performed with this alloy at lower temperatures, but the diffusion couple experiments of TN2-Al confirm the existence of a (βTi,Nb) + O two-phase field at 700 and 800 °C (Table 9).

Figure 10 a) BSE image of alloy TAN4 (Ti-24.6Al-14.9Nb) heat-treated at 900 °C/650 h with $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ (bright), Ti_3Al (dark), and O phase (grey) and; b) Bright field TEM image of the matrix of alloy TAN4 showing plate-like Ti_3Al in an O phase matrix.

Alloy TAN6 (Ti-30Al-25Nb) with a 5 at.% higher Al content than TAN5 was also heat-treated at 900 °C for 1000 h. Its composition lies on the Al-rich side of the O phase field. In the metallographic cross section of this sample, some macroscopic inhomogeneity was observed as indicated by the occurrence of two different kinds of microstructure, which are labelled “TAN6a” and “TAN6b” (Figure 11). Respective EPMA grid measurements confirmed slightly different overall compositions in the two regions. While the Al-lean region consists of a two-phase microstructure of O phase and Nb_2Al , the Al-rich region additionally contains significant amounts of Ti_3Al (see Table 8). The existence of these phases is confirmed by HEXRD measurements.

Figure 11 BSE images of alloy TAN6 (Ti-30Al-25Nb) heat-treated at 900 °C/1000 h. The sample consists of two parts representing (a) the two-phase field O + Nb_2Al and b) the three-phase field Ti_3Al + O + Nb_2Al .

The microstructure of alloy TAN8 (Ti-32.4Al-17.3Nb) appears to be three-phase after the heat treatment at 900 °C, and HEXRD of the quenched sample identifies the phases Ti_3Al , O, and ω_o . Although these are the expected equilibrium phases up to slightly lower temperatures (more precisely: up to 897 °C, see Section 4.1.3.2.5, Table 19, and Figure 46), this does not correspond to the true equilibrium at 900 °C, which instead should be $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o + Ti_3Al + \omega_o$. As is discussed in detail in Section 4.1.3.2.5, some reactions occur just below 900 °C, and most likely the true heat treatment temperature for this sample was slightly below 900 °C (e.g., 896 °C would be already sufficient), which could explain the observed microstructure. At 700 and 800 °C, the microstructure is almost single-phase ω_o . HEXRD measurements reveal that an additional 5 vol.% O phase and 1 vol.% Ti_3Al are present at 800 °C and 2 vol.% O phase at 700 °C. Due to the low phase fractions and the smallness of the particles, the composition of these phases cannot be measured directly by EPMA, and grid measurements also do not provide reliable values for the phase compositions. However, using the tie-line data from the diffusion couple experiments (TN2-Al) and the phase fractions determined by HEXRD, the position of the tie-triangle $Ti_3Al + O + \omega_o$ at 800 °C and the tie-line $O + \omega_o$ at 700 °C can be approximated. This is possible under the assumption that tie-lines located close to tie-triangles are parallel and of similar length to the respective side of this tie-triangle. Using this approximation, it is possible to roughly estimate the phase compositions (Tables 6-7). By applying the lever rule, the obtained compositions can then be checked for agreement with the phase fractions determined by HEXRD.

The same method was used to determine the phase compositions in alloy TAN7 (Ti-32.8Al-12.2Nb) at 700 and 800 °C, where the microstructure again almost exclusively consists of the ω_o phase with 4-5 vol.% of Ti_3Al . At 900 °C, the two microstructure constituents are large enough to be measured with EPMA. Figure 12a shows the microstructure at 900 °C with Ti_3Al both as grain boundary phase and as precipitates within large ω_o grains.

Figure 12 a) BSE image of alloy TAN7 (Ti-32.8Al-12.2Nb) heat-treated at 900 °C with large ω_0 grains (bright) as matrix phase and Ti_3Al (dark) as grain boundary phase and inside the grains as precipitates (the contrast differences appearing in the ω_0 matrix are not due to chemical differences, which was verified by EPMA spot analyses at different positions resulting in identical compositions); b) BSE images of alloy TAN9 (Ti-37.2Al-10.0Nb) and c) alloy TAN11 (Ti-39.6Al-10.0Nb) heat-treated at 900 °C for 650 h lying in the same three-phase field composed of Ti_3Al (grey), $TiAl$ (dark), and ω_0 (bright), d) respective HEXRD pattern of B11 (with logarithmic intensity scale) confirming the microstructural results.

Figure 13 BSE images of alloy TAN9 (Ti-37.2Al-10.0Nb) at a) 700 °C heat-treated for 1500 h and b) 800 °C heat-treated for 1000 h; both showing a three-phase microstructure between ω_0 (grey) as matrix phase with fine TiAl precipitates and Ti_3Al at the grain boundaries; c) bright field TEM image of the ω_0 matrix with twinned TiAl precipitates identified by SAED.

Both alloys TAN9 (Ti-37.2Al-10.0Nb) and TAN11 (Ti-39.6Al-10.0Nb) show the three-phase equilibrium $Ti_3Al + TiAl + \omega_0$ in the entire studied temperature range from 700 to 900 °C. The respective three-phase microstructures of the two alloys at 900 °C are shown in Figure 12b,c. Since the Al content of the two alloys is different, the phase fractions change significantly, which is also visible in the microstructure. The phases were identified by room temperature HEXRD measurements (Figure 12d). Additionally, *in situ* HEXRD measurements of alloy TAN11 prove that ω_0 is present in the entire temperature range from 700 to 900 °C before it transforms to $(\beta Ti,Nb)_0$ at a temperature above 900 °C. This was confirmed by DTA investigations, which give equilibrium transformation onset temperatures of 908 and 906 °C for alloys TAN9 and TAN11 (Table 19). At 700 and 800 °C, the microstructure of both alloys is very fine-scaled (Figure 13a,b). HEXRD measurements confirm the three phases Ti_3Al , TiAl, and ω_0 . Large ω_0 grains make up the largest part of the microstructure. Small amounts of Ti_3Al

have precipitated along the grain boundaries, while the very fine, plate-like precipitates in the grains are TiAl (as was confirmed by TEM selected area diffraction) with a lot of twins visible in the TEM bright field image Figure 13c. Because of the small phase fraction and size of Ti₃Al, it was not possible to measure its composition by EPMA. Therefore, the composition of Ti₃Al at 700 and 800 °C was tentatively estimated using Ti₃Al phase boundary data from the nearby alloys TAN7, TAN13 and TAN14.

Alloy TAN10 (Ti-37Al-13.5Nb) was heat-treated at 900 °C only. It has a similar Al content as the three-phase alloys TAN9 and TAN11 but an about 4 at.% higher Nb content. XRD shows that this alloy contains large amounts of (βTi,Nb)_o and TiAl as well as some ω_o phase, see Figure 14a. The microstructure of the quenched sample shows large grains of (βTi,Nb)_o/ω_o (which cannot be distinguished because of their almost identical composition) and TiAl precipitates both inside the grains and on the grain boundaries. In addition, there is a small amount of another phase with lower Nb content, which most likely is some untransformed Ti₃Al. The presence of metastable phases in the quenched sample is confirmed by DTA measurements, which reveal strong exothermic effects upon heating. The DTA curve shown in Figure 14b shows at least two clearly visible exothermic effects that could be related to the transformation of the quenched-in (βTi,Nb)_o phase and the dissolution of the metastable Ti₃Al.

Figure 14 a) X-ray diffractogram of alloy TAN10 (Ti-37Al-13.5Nb) after heat-treatment at 900 °C and quenching showing the presence of (βTi,Nb)_o, TiAl as well as some ω_o phase; b) DTA heating curves of the same sample. The upper curve shows the heat flow signal during first heating (up to 1350 °C) of the quenched sample, and the lower curve is the result of a second heating of the same sample after cooling from 1350 °C. The exothermic effects during first heating reveal the metastability of the sample quenched from 900 °C (the dashed gray line is to indicate the course of the hypothetical baseline).

Alloy TAN15 (Ti-44.7Al-12.3Nb) contains a similar amount of Nb and about 8 at.% more Al than alloy TAN10. Its composition lies within the two-phase field $\text{TiAl} + \omega_0$ in the entire temperature range from 700 to 900 °C. Alloy TAN12 (Ti-39.8Al-19.9Nb) with an even higher Nb content additionally contains the phase Nb_2Al . At 900 °C, the microstructure is clearly two-phase (Figure 15a). HEXRD proves these phases to be TiAl and Nb_2Al , and the phase compositions can be well determined by EPMA. At 800 °C, alloy TAN12 is three-phase $\text{TiAl} + \omega_0 + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$ (Figure 15b). The HEXRD measurements of the quenched sample show the presence of a small amount of Nb_2Al (< 10 vol.%) together with the major phases TiAl and ω_0 having almost equal phase fractions. From the 800 °C diffusion couple TN3-Al, a tie-line between TiAl and Nb_2Al can be determined (Table 9), which is oriented parallel to the $\text{TiAl} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$ boundary of the TAN12 three-phase triangle. In addition, the orientation of the tie-line from alloy TAN15 is parallel to the $\text{TiAl} + \omega_0$ boundary of alloy TAN12. This is another confirmation of the existence of a three-phase equilibrium $\text{TiAl} + \omega_0 + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$ at 800 °C. The same three-phase equilibrium $\text{TiAl} + \omega_0 + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$ exists at 700 °C in alloy TAN12. However, the Nb_2Al phase is too small to be measured with EPMA and its phase fraction was found to be too low to be observed by the HEXRD measurements. The presence of Nb_2Al is nevertheless evident from the EPMA results, as the measured overall composition of alloy TAN12 at 700 °C lies above the tie-line between the measured compositions of TiAl and ω_0 . Due to the lower phase fraction of Nb_2Al compared to the 800 and 900 °C samples, its Nb content must be higher than at the higher temperatures, and, as is discussed in Section 4.1.3.4, with some additional information from the literature it is possible to give at least an approximate composition.

Figure 15 BSE image of alloy TAN12 (Ti-39.8Al-19.9Nb) a) heat-treated at 900 °C for 650 h showing a two-phase microstructure consisting of TiAl (dark) and Nb_2Al (bright), and b) heat-treated at 800 °C for 1000 h revealing the three-phase equilibrium $\text{TiAl} + \omega_0 + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$.

It should be mentioned that in the two Nb-rich samples (alloys TAN12 and TAN15), small amounts of Ti_3Al were found in addition to the equilibrium phases, similar as in case of alloy TAN10. Most likely Ti_3Al has formed during alloy synthesis. At high temperatures (just below the solidus temperature), these alloys are single-phase ($\beta Ti,Nb$). In a detailed study of the precipitation behaviour of such alloys during annealing at 800 °C, Yang et al. [85] showed that in an initial step, metastable Ti_3Al precipitates from the ($\beta Ti,Nb$) phase instead of the equilibrium phases $TiAl$ and ω_o . This metastable Ti_3Al decomposes only slowly during further annealing. It is therefore reasonable to assume that the annealing times used in the present experiments were not sufficient to completely transform the metastable Ti_3Al phase in these alloys.

A two-phase equilibrium between $TiAl$ and Ti_3Al is observed in alloys TAN13 (Ti-43.4Al-4.9Nb) and TAN14 (Ti-45.8Al-5.9Nb) from 700 to 900 °C. As the BSE images of alloy TAN13 in Figure 16 show, parts of the samples consist of a fine lamellar microstructure, while in other areas a coarser two-phase microstructure with bright Ti_3Al in a dark $TiAl$ matrix is observed (phases were identified with XRD measurements). In the latter areas, the phase compositions can be determined by single spot measurements. The overall composition of the fine lamellar regions is measured with a widened beam. It is found to lie close to the overall composition of the sample and exactly on the tie-line resulting from the single spot measurements confirming that the fine lamellar microstructure is also a $Ti_3Al + TiAl$ two-phase mixture. This is the case for both alloys TAN13 and TAN14 from 700 up to 900 °C. Another observation worth mentioning is that at 700 and 800 °C, the Nb content in Ti_3Al is significantly higher than in $TiAl$ (Tables 6 and 7), which is not the case at 900 °C (Table 8). Therefore, the tie-lines at 700 and 800 °C are inclined compared to the almost horizontal tie-line (parallel to the binary Ti–Al system) at 900 °C. This observation is consistent with the results obtained from the diffusion couples, where a similar behaviour of the tie-lines is observed.

It should also be mentioned that HEXRD measurements of alloys TAN13 at 700 and 800 °C and TAN14 at 700 °C show the presence of small fractions (<1.5 vol.%) of ω_o phase in the samples, which are not detectable in the microstructures or in standard XRD. However, it can be excluded that ω_o is an equilibrium phase in these alloys. If ω_o were an equilibrium phase, the composition of both alloys would lie within the tie-triangle $Ti_3Al + TiAl + \omega_o$, which means that the compositions of Ti_3Al and $TiAl$ in both alloys would have to be identical. This is clearly not the case. Moreover, the true three-phase equilibrium $Ti_3Al + TiAl + \omega_o$ has already been observed in the Nb-richer alloys TAN9 and TAN11 (see above and Figure 12).

Figure 16 BSE images of alloy TAN13 (Ti-43.5Al-4.9Nb) showing coarse- and fine-lamellar Ti₃Al (bright) + TiAl (dark) two-phase microstructures after heat treatment at a) 700 °C, b) 800 °C, and c) 900 °C.

4.1.3 Isothermal sections, phase fields, solubility and phase formation between 700 and 900 °C

Based on the experimental results presented above (Tables 6-9) and some information from the literature discussed below, partial isothermal sections at 700, 800, and 900 °C were established (Figures 17-19). For the binary boundary systems Ti–Al and Ti–Nb, the assessed phase diagrams reported in [28, 29] and [32], respectively, were used. In the following, these isothermal sections are discussed in detail with special emphasis on the equilibria and homogeneity ranges of the ω_0 and O phase.

Figure 17 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 700 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Tables 6 and 9. The measured overall compositions of the samples are indicated by black stars, the yellow lines mark the three-phase equilibria, grey symbols and lines indicate the data from the diffusion couples, and blue symbols and lines mark the results from bulk alloys and the resulting phase boundaries.

Figure 18 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 800 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Tables 7 and 9 (symbols as in Figure 17).

Figure 19 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 900 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Tables 8 and 9 (symbols as in Figure 17, unfilled stars: nominal alloy composition).

4.1.3.1 The two-phase field $Ti_3Al + TiAl$

In the investigated temperature range between 700 and 900 °C, the two-phase field $Ti_3Al + TiAl$ extends into the ternary system up to about 8-9 at.% Nb, as can be concluded from the results for the diffusion couples and alloys TAN9, TAN11, TAN13, and TAN14 (Figures 17-19). Although no tie-line data were reported in the literature for this temperature range, there are some studies on the solidification and phase transformation of alloys with compositions similar to TAN13 and TAN14 that confirm the existence of the two-phase region. For example, Chladil et al. [86] investigated four alloys with a constant Al content of 45 at.% Al and Nb contents between 0 and 10 at.%. With the help of DTA and *in situ* HEXRD measurements, they showed that Ti_3Al and $TiAl$ are present in alloys with up to 7.5 at.% Nb for temperatures up to above 900 °C. A similar observation was made by Rackel et al. [87], who found Ti_3Al and $TiAl$ (and a small amount of 0.3 vol.% ω_0 similar as in the present experiments in alloys TAN13 and TAN14) in a sample with 45 at.% Al and 7.5 at.% Nb after homogenization at 1100 °C and heat treatment at 700 °C for 5 h with consecutive air cooling.

At 900 °C, the $Ti_3Al + TiAl$ tie-lines of the diffusion couple TN1-TA2-TN2 are very close to the binary Ti–Al boundary (<0.5 at.% Nb). The measured Al contents of about 36 at.%

in Ti_3Al and 47 at.% in TiAl (Table 9) agree very well with the phase boundaries of the $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{TiAl}$ two-phase field in the assessed Ti–Al binary phase diagram [28, 29]. When Nb is added, the Al content in both phases remains almost constant. This results in phase boundaries almost parallel to the Ti–Nb binary system, suggesting that Nb preferentially replaces Ti in both crystal lattices. This behaviour was also experimentally observed by Konitzer et al. [88] and is predicted by density functional theory (DFT) calculations of Holec et al. [89] for both Ti_3Al and TiAl . Furthermore, these results show that Nb partitions equally between Ti_3Al and TiAl , which is also reported in literature [90].

4.1.3.2 Phase equilibria and homogeneity range of the ω_o phase

4.1.3.2.1 The Nb-poor limit ($\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{TiAl} + \omega_o$)

The ternary intermetallic phase ω_o is observed as equilibrium phase in the alloys with overall Al contents from 32 to 45 at.% and Nb contents above 9 at.% (alloys TAN7-11 and TAN15). The three-phase equilibrium $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{TiAl} + \omega_o$ was found in the alloys TAN9 (Ti-37.2Al-10.0Nb) and TAN11 (Ti-39.6Al-10.0Nb) between 700 and 900 °C. The chemical composition of the ω_o phase in these alloys determines the lower limit of the homogeneity range of ω_o with regard to Nb and Al content. Within the experimental accuracy, both the Nb and Al content remain almost constant with increasing temperature and have averaged values of 10.7 at.% Nb and 34.6 at.% Al. The presence of ω_o up to 900 °C in these two alloys agrees with the determined ω_o -to- $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ transition onset temperatures of 908 and 906 °C, respectively (Table 19). The existence of ω_o in equilibrium with Ti_3Al and TiAl at 900°C agrees with results reported by Xu et al. [71], who studied a diffusion multiple annealed at 900 °C, and Rackel et al. [91], who performed *in situ* HEXRD measurements of an alloy with composition Ti-42Al-8.5Nb. This composition lies inside the $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{TiAl} + \omega_o$ tie-triangle shown in Figure 19. Yu et al. [92] also observed the formation of ω_o besides Ti_3Al and TiAl in an alloy of composition Ti-40Al-10Nb (similar to TAN11) after hot rolling (1150 °C) and subsequent heat treatments at 700, 800, and 900 °C. The tie-triangle $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{TiAl} + \omega_o$ is also reported in the modelling work of Witusiewicz et al. [84] for temperatures of 700 and 800 °C, while it is missing in their 900 °C isothermal section. They assume that the ω_o phase exists only up to a maximum temperature of 811 °C, whereas its stability at 900 °C has been demonstrated in the present investigations and was also shown in the above mentioned literature [71, 91-93].

4.1.3.2.2 The Nb-rich limit (TiAl + ω_0 + Nb₂Al)

The upper limit of the ω_0 homogeneity range is determined by the tie-triangle TiAl + ω_0 + Nb₂Al, which is determined from alloy TAN12 at 700 and 800 °C. The composition of ω_0 is located at about 35.5 at.% Al and 20 at.% Nb. At 900 °C, alloy TAN12 is two-phase TiAl + Nb₂Al. For this temperature, the tie-triangle can be estimated from the position of the tie-lines of the two alloys TAN15 (TiAl + ω_0) and TAN12 (TiAl + Nb₂Al) (Figure 19). Since their compositions for TiAl are close to each other, the TiAl corner of the tie-triangle must be very near to this point. And since, for thermodynamic reasons, tie-lines which are very near to the sides of a tie-triangle can be expected to be (almost) parallel to the tie-triangle, the compositions of Nb₂Al and ω_0 are supposed to lie close to the corresponding compositions in alloy TAN12 and TAN15 (Figure 19). This results in a decrease of about 2 at.% for the maximum Nb content of ω_0 between 800 °C (20.6 at.% Nb) and 900 °C (~ 18.0 at.%), while the Al content remains almost constant being ~34.5 at.% at 900 °C. No information is available from the literature about this tie-triangle at 700 and 800 °C. For 900 °C, the diffusion multiple experiment of Xu et al. [71] confirms the existence of the TiAl + ω_0 + Nb₂Al three-phase field. Since they assumed an only small, nearly circular ω_0 phase field (for a discussion of this aspect, see also Section 4.1.3.2.6), they give a much lower value for the Nb content (15 at.%), while the Al content (34.5 at.%) is identical to the value estimated here.

4.1.3.2.3 Equilibria on the Al-rich side – Formation of the (β Ti,Nb)₀ phase from ω_0

The two-phase equilibrium TiAl + ω_0 is observed in alloy TAN15 at 700 to 900 °C and is also found in the diffusion couples heat-treated at 700 and 800 °C. It is worth to mention that the Al contents here on the Al-rich side of the ω_0 phase field are in the range 33.5-35.4 at.% (and do not include the stoichiometric value of 37.5 at.% corresponding to the commonly used formula “Ti₄NbAl₃”; see Section 4.1.3.2.6 for a discussion of this aspect). Bendersky et al. [20] investigated an alloy of composition Ti-37.5Al-12.5Nb lying in this two-phase field. After homogenization for 4 h at 1400 °C in the (β Ti,Nb)₀ single-phase state, their sample was annealed at 700 °C for 624 h. In agreement with the present findings, they observed an equilibrium between the ω_0 phase and TiAl. Their measured phase compositions (Ti-34.5Al-13Nb for ω_0 and Ti-50Al-9Nb for TiAl) are very similar to those determined in the 700 °C diffusion couple (Ti-35Al-13Nb for ω_0 and Ti-48Al-9.5Nb for TiAl).

Interestingly, in addition to the two equilibrium phases ω_o and TiAl, Bendersky et al. [20] found a trace amount of Ti_3Al , similar to the experimental results for alloys TAN12 and TAN15. As already mentioned in Section 4.1.2 and described in detail in Ref. [85] for a Ti-40Al-8Nb alloy, this could result from the easy formation of metastable Ti_3Al and its slow transformation to the ω_o equilibrium phase. The slow formation process of the ω_o phase from Ti_3Al was also described by Song et al. [94], who performed TEM studies of the structural relation between Ti_3Al and ω_o in a Ti-45Al-9Nb alloy annealed at 850 °C. Another possible explanation for the presence of non-equilibrium Ti_3Al phase is the effect of interstitial impurity elements. High amounts of such interstitial elements tend to shift phase compositions of phase equilibria with hexagonal phases, such as Ti_3Al , to higher Nb contents (further information see Section 4.4) [25].

As for the formation/dissolution temperature of the $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$ phase in the ternary system, the only information available from literature comes from *in situ* neutron diffraction experiments on a Ti-36.5Al-12.9Nb alloy in the temperature range between 700 and 960 °C [70]. In this work, the transformation from ω_o to $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$ was found to start at about 800 °C. The composition of alloy TAN10 (Ti-37.0Al-13.5Nb) is very similar to the one studied by neutron diffraction. In DTA measurements of this alloy, the onset of a reaction is visible at about 790 °C (Figure 20). Therefore, from the observations of Sadi et al. [70] together with the presence of the thermal effect in the DTA measurement of alloy TAN10, it is concluded that at ~790 °C the $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$ phase forms in the two-phase field TiAl + ω_o in a eutectoid reaction $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o \rightleftharpoons TiAl + \omega_o$. The composition of the $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$ phase at 800 °C in the alloy used for the neutron diffraction experiments was reported to be Ti-34.5Al-15.1Nb [69], and this value was used in the isothermal section at 800 °C for drawing the $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$ phase field (Figure 18). From the DTA curve in Figure 20, it can be seen that the transformation of ω_o to $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$ in alloy TAN10 is finished at ~905 °C, which corresponds to the peak temperature. XRD of this alloy after heat treatment at 900 °C confirms the coexistence of $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$, ω_o , and TiAl (Figure 14a). The composition of the $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$ phase measured in alloy TAN10 at 900 °C (Ti-35.0Al-13.9Nb) marks the Nb-poor end of the small phase field. The tie-triangle at this temperature is already very narrow (Figure 19) as the sample becomes two-phase $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$ + TiAl at ~905 °C (Figure 20).

Figure 20 DTA heat flow curve of alloy TAN10 (heat-treated at 1000 °C for 400 h, heating rate 5 °C/min) showing the ω_0 -to- $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ transformation.

4.1.3.2.4 Equilibria on the Ti-Nb-rich side

The Ti-rich phase boundary of the ω_0 phase field at low Nb contents is determined by the two-phase equilibria between Ti_3Al and ω_0 in alloy TAN7 (Ti-32.8Al-12.2Nb) between 700 and 900 °C. The same phase equilibrium with very similar microstructures was observed by Song et al. [95] in an alloy with nominal composition Ti-34Al-13Nb after annealing for 100 h at 700 and 900 °C (cf. Figure 12 in Section 4.1.2 and Fig. 3 in Ref. [95]). The compositions in Ref. [95] were measured by TEM-EDS and are slightly different from the present values. Regarding the accuracy of their composition values from TEM-EDS, Song et al. point out that “Although the EDS analysis on TEM cannot be as precise as that obtained on electron microprobe, it still reflects the composition redistribution between different phases.” [95]. Thus, the results can be taken as a confirmation of the here reported data regarding the existence and position of the $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \omega_0$ two-phase field.

At 700 and 800 °C, the ω_0 phase field is further defined by the adjacent tie-triangle $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{O} + \omega_0$, which is observed at 800 °C in alloy TAN8 (Ti-32.4Al-17.3Nb) both in the quenched microstructure as well as by *in situ* HEXRD measurements. At 700 °C, the same alloy is two-phase $\text{O} + \omega_0$, indicating that the position of the $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{O} + \omega_0$ tie-triangle (or at least the $\text{O} + \omega_0$ tie-line of the triangle) must have shifted to lower Nb contents. The existence of this three-phase equilibrium is confirmed by results of Sadi [69] in a Ti-29.5Al-14.2Nb alloy heat-treated

at 700 °C. As the exact phase compositions at 700 °C are not known, the position of the tie-triangle based on the measured nearby tie-lines is tentatively estimated (see Figure 17).

The existence of the two-phase equilibrium $O + \omega_o$, which was observed at 700 °C in alloy TAN8, was also confirmed by Bendersky et al. [96], who performed TEM studies on a Ti-30Al-20Nb alloy, but did not determine the phase compositions. On the Nb-rich side of this two-phase field, the tie-triangle $O + \omega_o + Nb_2Al$ is located. The existence of this three-phase equilibrium at 700 °C was confirmed by Sadi [69]. From the present investigations, no experimental data are available in this composition range at 700 and 800 °C.

At 900 °C, the phase equilibria in this composition range between the phases Ti_3Al , O , ω_o , and Nb_2Al differ significantly from the lower temperatures. This is a result of the appearance of the $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$ phase and the onset of decomposition of the ω_o phase, which leads to a splitting of the ω_o phase field as discussed in the next section.

4.1.3.2.5 Splitting of the ω_o phase field

As reported above in Sections 4.1.3.2.1 and 4.1.3.2.2 and visible in Figures 17-19, the ω_o phase at 700 and 800 °C exhibits an extended homogeneity range from about 10 to 20 at.% Nb. DTA investigations on a series of ternary alloys containing the ω_o phase have revealed that the onset temperature of the decomposition reaction depends in an unexpected way on the composition (Figure 46). The highest stability, i.e., the highest onset temperatures of the decomposition reaction were found for ω_o compositions at the Nb-poor and Nb-rich end ($T_{onset} \sim 920$ °C) of the homogeneity range, while at intermediate Nb contents there is a stability minimum ($T_{onset} < 900$ °C). In case of alloy TAN8, ω_o starts to transform to $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$ at 897 °C (Table 19), which means that above this temperature (i.e. specifically in the isothermal section at 900 °C), the $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$ phase must be present on the Al-poor side of the ω_o phase field, and the overall composition of alloy TAN8 must be located in a tie-triangle/two-phase field that includes $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$. One possible way to achieve this is that the $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o$ phase field formed at 790 °C on the Al-rich side of the ω_o phase field further constricts the ω_o phase field with increasing temperature and finally splits it into two separate phase fields (at an unknown temperature between 800 and 897 °C, therefore the temperature is estimated to be 850 ± 45 °C). This would lead to the formation of two new tie-triangles $(\beta Ti, Nb)_o + O + \omega_o$ (violet filled tie-triangles in Figure 21a) in the former $O + \omega_o$ two-phase field. The lower of these two tie-

triangles must take part in a transition-type reaction with the $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{O} + \omega_o$ three-phase equilibrium ($(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al} \rightleftharpoons \text{O} + \omega_o$). Similar reactions have to occur between the upper $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{O} + \omega_o$ and $\text{O} + \omega_o + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$ tie-triangles ($(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al} \rightleftharpoons \text{O} + \omega_o$). This leads to four new tie-triangles $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \omega_o + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al}/\text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$ and $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{O} + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al}/\text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$ as shown in Figure 21b (green-shaded tie-triangles). The two three-phase equilibria containing ω_o will take part in the dissolution of the remaining ω_o above 900 °C, and the tie-triangles containing the O phase must undergo another transition-type reaction ($\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al} \rightleftharpoons (\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{O}$) to result in the phase equilibria that are observed at 900 °C (Figure 19). The described transition-type reactions have to take place between 897 and 900 °C. Alloy TAN8 would be only involved in the transition reaction at 897 °C changing its three-phase equilibrium from $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{O} + \omega_o$ to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \omega_o$. Therefore, a slight temperature deviation of the heat treatment furnace by, e.g., 5 °C (i.e., 895 °C instead of the intended value of 900 °C) would be sufficient to explain the observed $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{O} + \omega_o$ equilibrium in alloy TAN8. On further heating of alloy TAN8, the transformation of the ω_o phase to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ continues until the sample enters the two-phase field $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al}$, which happens at approximately 910 °C (which is a rough estimation from an extrapolation of peak temperatures from DTA heating curves to heating rate 0 °C/min). At 1000 °C, the alloy is still in this two-phase field as was confirmed by the phase equilibria reported in Section 4.2 (Figure 34).

Figure 21 Schematic partial isothermal sections a) at 850 ± 45 °C just above the (unknown) temperature where the growing $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ phase has split the ω_o phase field into two parts resulting in the two new ternary triangles marked in violet, and b) at 898 °C after the transition-type reaction $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al} \rightleftharpoons \text{O} + \omega_o$ on the Nb-poor and $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al} \rightleftharpoons \text{O} + \omega_o$ on the Nb-rich side.

4.1.3.2.6 Stoichiometry of the ω_0 phase – revised formula

In the literature, the formula Ti_4NbAl_3 is commonly used for the ω_0 phase, which corresponds to a stoichiometric composition Ti-37.5Al-12.5Nb. The present investigations show that the homogeneity range of ω_0 between 700 and 900 °C extends parallel to the Ti-Nb axis along an almost constant Al content varying only slightly between 32.5 and 36 at.%. In agreement with that, Xu et al. [71] found equilibrium compositions of the ω_0 phase at 900 °C in the range 33.1 to 34.5 at.% Al. Obviously, the composition corresponding to the formula is outside of the homogeneity range of the ω_0 phase. The formula Ti_4NbAl_3 stems from the fundamental work of Bendersky et al. [20], who were the first to describe the transformation from the ordered $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ phase and the structure of the ω_0 phase in detail. Reading their original work [20], it becomes clear that there was a misunderstanding in the later literature that lead to the wrong phase designation. In their paper, Bendersky et al. never referred to the equilibrium ω_0 phase by this formula, but instead Ti_4NbAl_3 corresponds to the alloy composition they studied. This alloy was found to be single-phase $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ after annealing at 1400 °C, and after quenching to room temperature it transformed to a metastable single-phase ω'' structure with a trigonal unit cell and space group P-3m1. This displacive transformation from B2-ordered $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ to the metastable, trigonal ω'' structure occurs without any change in chemistry and the trigonal ω'' can be described by the formula Ti_4NbAl_3 (or $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al}_{2.25}\text{Nb}_{0.75}$ as used by Shoemaker et al. [97]). However, the final transformation to the equilibrium ω_0 phase, which was observed by Bendersky et al. to occur after prolonged annealing at 700 °C, is “strongly first order” [20] and does not only affect the crystal structure but also involves a change of chemical composition accompanied by the precipitation of a second phase, which is TiAl. With that the transformation sequence to reach the equilibrium state is $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0 \rightarrow \omega'' \rightarrow \text{TiAl} + \omega_0$. Since TiAl is richer in Al compared to the alloy composition (37.5Al), it is obvious that the equilibrium ω_0 phase must contain a lower amount of Al relative to the alloy composition. In case of their Ti-37.5Al-12.5Nb alloy, Bendersky et al. obtained a composition of Ti-34.5Al-13Nb for their ω_0 phase (Table 3 in Ref. [20]), which is in perfect agreement with the 700 °C isothermal section (Figure 17).

Interestingly, the crystal structure of the ω_0 phase is of the $B8_2$ type, prototype Ni_2In , and Pearson symbol $hP6$. Regarding this structure type and the observed homogeneity range of about 10 to 20 at.% Nb and 32.5 to 36 at.% Al, a formula of the type $(\text{Ti,Nb})_2\text{Al}$ would be an obvious choice for the ω_0 phase. With Al sitting on the In site and Ti and Nb sharing the Ni site of the prototype structure, this corresponds to a stoichiometric Al content of 33.3 at.%. The unit

cell of the $B8_2$ crystal structure contains three independent Wyckoff sites ($2a$), ($2c$), and ($2d$), where – in case of the prototype phase Ni_2In – the In atoms occupy the ($2c$) positions and Ni the two other sites. For a ternary phase such as the ω_o phase, the existence of the three Wyckoff sites offers the additional possibility of a non-statistical site occupation of Nb (respectively Ti) on the two sites ($2a$) and ($2d$). Structure refinements of single-crystal XRD data by Bendersky et al. indicate that the Nb atoms prefer the ($2a$) sites (i.e., Ti occupies all the ($2d$) sites and the remaining ($2a$) sites) [20].

Thus, it is obvious that the frequently cited formula Ti_4NbAl_3 is not suitable to describe the ω_o phase. Instead it is suggested to use the designation $(Ti,Nb)_2Al$. The range of Nb contents then can be described approximately by $(Ti_{1-x}Nb_x)_2Al$ with $0.15 < x < 0.3$.

4.1.3.3 Phase equilibria and homogeneity range of the O phase

The above described reaction sequence, which resulted from the splitting of the ω_o phase, also influences the Al-rich side of the homogeneity range of the neighbouring O phase, which is the second ternary intermetallic phase of the system and has a stoichiometric composition of Ti-25Al-25Nb. As mentioned above, the presence of the two tie-triangles $Ti_3Al + O + \omega_o$ and $O + \omega_o + Nb_2Al$ as well as the two-phase field $O + \omega_o$ are well documented at 700 and 800 °C. The same two tie-triangles were found by Xu et al. [71] in their diffusion multiple studies at 900 °C. However, the present investigations reveal that at 900 °C, the $O + \omega_o$ two-phase field no longer exists and instead the O phase is in a three-phase equilibrium with Ti_3Al and Nb_2Al . This three-phase equilibrium was observed in alloy TAN6b (corresponding to the three-phase region in alloy TAN6 with an overall composition Ti-30.3Al-22.5Nb) as described above (see also Figures 11b and 19). The same tie-triangle $Ti_3Al + O + Nb_2Al$ was also reported by Sadi [69] at 900 °C (and 800 °C).

Similar as in case of the ω_o phase, the homogeneity range of the O phase mainly extends parallel to the Ti-Nb axis. The maximum Nb content in the O phase is determined by its equilibria with Nb_3Al , which, however, did not occur in the alloys studied here. Xu et al. [71] report a maximum value of 26.7 at.% Nb for the O phase. However, the results of diffusion couple TN3-Al, which was heat-treated at 800 °C, indicate that the maximum Nb content in the O phase must be higher and is more in the range of 30 at.%. This is also consistent with results from Kestner-Weykamp et al. [77], who found that an alloy of composition Ti-25Al-30Nb was

single-phase O phase at 800 °C, and agrees with the work of Rowe et al. [67], who reported an upper limit of the O phase field of 30 at.% Nb.

The Nb-poor boundary of the O phase field is defined by the two-phase field between Ti_3Al and O. In alloy TAN4, minimum Nb contents of 16.2, 15.5, and 14.6 at.% are measured at 700, 800, and 900 °C, respectively. Xu et al. [71] again report a different value of 19.3 at.% Nb at 900 °C, while the here presented data are in good agreement with the work of Kestner-Weykamp et al. [77] and Rowe et al. [67] (who give a minimum value of 15 at.% Nb for 900 °C).

The tie-triangle $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o + Ti_3Al + O$ is observed in alloy TAN4 at 900 °C. In an alloy with similar composition (Ti-25.2Al-15.7Nb), Rowe et al. [67] also observed this three-phase equilibrium after heat treatment at 900 °C. However, they did not analyse the phase compositions. At 700 and 800 °C, none of the present alloys contained this three-phase equilibrium, but the position of its tie triangle could be estimated from the two-phase alloys TAN3 and TAN4 and the diffusion couples.

On the Al-poor side of the O phase, there is an extended two-phase field with the $(\beta Ti,Nb)$ solid solution. Alloys in this composition range have been studied by various authors as new structural materials with even better mechanical properties than the TiAl-based alloys, see, e.g., the review of Zhang et al. [98]. However, these studies focus on mechanical properties and microstructural aspects of such alloys and no data on equilibrium phase compositions were reported. At 900 °C, many of the alloys studied by Rowe et al. [67] lie in this phase field and they concluded that the Al-poor phase boundary of the O phase field is at a constant Al content of about 25 at.%. Xu et al. [71] report a similar value of 25.2 at.% Al. This value is in agreement with the results for alloys TAN4 and TAN5 at 900 °C (25.0 and 25.3 at.% Al, respectively). At 700 and 800 °C, the two-phase equilibrium $(\beta Ti,Nb) + O$ in the diffusion couples TN2-Al (700 °C) and TN3-Al (800 °C) giving Al contents for the O phase of 25.0 and 25.5 at.%, respectively (Table 9). As is visible from the isothermal sections, the minimum Al content most likely is reached at the lower, Nb-poor end of the phase field and is tentatively estimated as ~24 at.%. It should also be mentioned that the $(\beta Ti,Nb)$ phase at 700 and 800 °C is disordered for all compositions. At 900 °C, B2-ordering only occurs in a small composition range corresponding to the highest Al contents and is observed in alloy TAN4, while alloys TAN1-3 and TAN5 contain disordered $(\beta Ti,Nb)$ phase, see Figure 19.

The maximum Al contents found in the O phase are in the range 28-30 at.% Al. This is in agreement with the results of Xu et al. [71], who reported a maximum Al content of 28.2 at.% for this phase at 900 °C. Furthermore, Rowe et al. [67] also gave 28 at.% as the upper Al limit for the composition range of the O phase at 900 °C. There is no information from the literature about lower temperatures, but the present data indicate a slight decrease of the maximum Al content with decreasing temperature.

By taking all data into account, the homogeneity range of the O phase is well determined in the temperature range 700 to 900 °C. The Nb-rich end of its homogeneity range is located at about 30 at.% Nb for all temperatures and the Nb-poor limit lies at about 15 at.%. As for the Al contents, the maximum extension of the O phase field ranges from about 24 to 28 at.% Al.

Table 10 Lattice parameters (accuracy of the lattice parameters is ± 0.001 Å) of the O phase as function of the Nb content measured in quenched samples (Tables 6-8).

Nb content in the O phase (at.%)	Lattice parameters (Å)		
	a	b	c
12.3 ^a	5.804	10.053	4.657
12.7 ^a	5.796	10.039	4.664
14.6	5.945	9.780	4.668
15.5	5.946	9.779	4.669
17.9	6.065	9.600	4.662
20.0	6.065	9.621	4.662
20.0	6.055	9.614	4.647
24.3	6.065	9.600	4.670
24.9	6.11	9.53	4.65

^a lattice parameter of Ti₃Al converted to “pseudo”-orthorhombic unit cell

Another observation regarding the O phase is the systematic increase and decrease in lattice parameters *a* and *b*, respectively, while *c* stays nearly constant (Table 10). This behaviour agrees very well with the XRD measurements from Kestner-Weykamp et al. [77]. If the hexagonal Ti₃Al is converted to a “pseudo”-orthorhombic unit cell it is observed that the lattice parameters of this unit cell continuously change to the lattice parameters of the orthorhombic unit cell of the O phase as function of the Nb content (Figure 22).

Figure 22 Lattice parameters of a “pseudo”-orthorhombic Ti_3Al and the O phase plotted as function of Nb content superimposed with the results from Kestner-Weykamp [77] (unfilled triangles) showing the continuous change of the lattice parameters (a = blue dots; b = red dots; c = green dots) from the “pseudo”-orthorhombic to the orthorhombic unit cell with increasing Nb content.

4.1.3.4 Solubility of ternary elements in the boundary phases (αTi), ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$), Ti_3Al , and Nb_2Al

The solubility of Nb in the (αTi) solid solution slightly increases with the Al content and reaches its maximum value in the three-phase equilibrium with Ti_3Al and ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) (alloy TAN1). Within the accuracy of the experiments, this value is independent of temperature and amounts to an averaged value of (4.0 ± 0.5) at.% Nb. The associated Al contents also vary only slightly and are in the range 17.0-17.6 at.%. Xu et al. [71] extracted a similar low value of 3.3 at.% for the solubility of Nb (at an Al content of 15.6 at.%) from their diffusion couple experiments at 900 °C.

Ti_3Al has a significantly higher solubility for Nb. From the present data, a solubility of (12.5 ± 0.5) at.% Nb can be estimated for an Al content of (25.0 ± 0.5) at.%. Temperature again has only a very weak effect on the Nb solubility (increasing from about 12.4 at.% at 700 °C to 12.8 at.% at 900 °C). Xu et al. [71] found a higher value of 16 at.% Nb at 900 °C, whereas the here presented results are in good agreement with those of Sadi [69], who measured maximum Nb contents in Ti_3Al of 13.2, 11.8, and 12.8 at.% Nb at 700, 800, and 900 °C, respectively.

In the (β Ti,Nb) solid solution, considerable amounts of Al are soluble throughout the investigated Nb-Ti composition range. With increasing temperature, the (β Ti,Nb) phase field continuously grows into the ternary system reaching, e.g. along a constant Nb content of 25 at.%, approximate values of 8, 12, and 17 at.% Al at 700, 800, and 900 °C, respectively. Experimental data from literature are in the same range. Xu et al. [71] obtained a maximum Al content of 14.7 at.% in their experiments at 900 °C, Rowe et al. [67] estimated a solubility of 13-15 at.% Al, and in Sadi's work [69] values of 14.3, 14.6, and 16.0 at.% Al are reported for 700, 800, and 900 °C, respectively.

Nb₂Al is the binary phase with the highest ternary solubility in the Ti-Al-Nb system. The maximum Ti contents in the temperature range 700-900 °C exceed 30 at.%. The measured solubility of about 37.5 at.% at 900 °C is consistent with a value of 37.1 at.% reported by Xu et al. [71]. For 800 °C, these present experiments give a value of 36 at.% Ti, and for 700 °C, the present data indicate a further, possibly even stronger decrease in solubility. However, no value could be measured in the present experiments for this temperature. Even though the presence of Nb₂Al in alloy TAN12 is evident from EPMA grid measurements, the precipitates were too small to be measured. The non-visibility of Nb₂Al peaks in XRD of this sample reveals that the phase fraction is very low. This means the Nb₂Al corner of the respective tie-triangle must be far away from the overall composition, which is the case if the Ti content is further decreased. This is also in accordance with the calculated phase diagram of Witusiewicz et al. [84]. From their isothermal sections, approximate values for the Ti solubility of 37, 36, and 30 at.% can be read for 900, 800, and 700 °C, respectively. As the values for 900 and 800 °C agree very well with the above presented results, their value for 700 °C is adopted for a tentative drawing of the 700 °C isothermal section in this range.

The solubility trends observed in the temperature range 700 to 900 °C in the binary phases continue at higher temperatures. This will be shown in the next chapter dealing with the phase equilibria at 1000 to 1300 °C.

4.2 High-temperature phase equilibria between 1000 and 1300 °C²

At temperatures above 1000 °C, the phase equilibria between (α Ti), (β Ti,Nb), and Ti₃Al are of vital importance for alloy development, as previously mentioned. To give further insights into the homogeneity ranges of these phases, two more ternary alloys (TAN16 and TAN17) were produced (blue stars in Figure 23, see also Table 2). Heat treatments of alloys TAN1-17 were performed at 1000, 1100, 1200, and 1300 °C for the times listed in Table 3. From the equilibrium phase compositions established by EPMA, isothermal sections were established for these temperatures.

Figure 23 As-cast alloy composition (Table 2) of the ternary bulk alloys (TAN1-TAN15, black stars/TAN16 and TAN17, blue stars) plotted in the ternary composition triangle.

4.2.1 Literature review

In the temperature range studied here, several isothermal sections have been published, some of which cover the entire ternary Ti-Al-Nb system [100-108]. As exemplarily shown in Figure 24 these data are often contradicting. The isothermal section (grey lines) from Li et al.

² This chapter is based on the following publication: [99] B. Distl, K. Hauschildt, F. Pyczak, and F. Stein, Phase equilibria in the Ti-rich part of the Ti-Al-Nb system Part II. High-temperature phase equilibria between 1000 and 1300 °C submitted to *Journal of Phase Equilibria and Diffusion*, 2022.

[102] is based on 17 ternary alloys and shows two three-phase equilibria ((β Ti,Nb) + Ti_3Al + Nb_2Al and Ti_3Al + $TiAl$ + Nb_2Al) is superimposed with data from Eckert et al. [105] and data summarized by Kattner et al. [83] which show the presence of different three-phase equilibria ((β Ti,Nb)_o + $TiAl$ + Nb_2Al and Ti_3Al + $TiAl$ + Nb_2Al). Furthermore, the tie-lines reported for the two-phase field (β Ti,Nb) + Ti_3Al show completely different inclinations and intersect each other (Figure 24). This is also observed at other temperatures.

Figure 24 Isothermal section at 1100 °C from Li et al. [102] (black dots; grey and red lines) superimposed with experimental results from Eckert et al. [105] (orange diamonds and violet lines) and summarized results by Kattner et al. [83] (blue stars and green lines) showing several contradicting phase equilibria.

In another study, covering 1100 °C Chen et al. reports a ternary intermetallic compound, which was named γ_1 ($TiAl_3Nb$) because according to their experiments, as the Nb content increases, these atoms occupied specific sites in the crystal lattice leading to further ordering in $TiAl$. This compound showed an extended homogeneity range [101]. However, since other studies have not been able to reproduce these results when following the experimental procedures described, the existence of this phase is controversial and has been discussed at length [109-111]. It is not considered an equilibrium phase in this work.

In a recent study, which is based on 38 heat-treated alloys, from Xu et al. [100], a much higher Nb solubility in (α Ti) at 1300 °C was measured than before [106, 112]. Another difference in the reported phase equilibria is the stability of Ti_3Al at 1200 °C. Hellwig et al. [104] reported an isothermal section, based on diffusion couple experiments and bulk alloys, at 1200 °C showing a Ti_3Al phase field extending up to 10 at.% into the ternary composition

triangle. Furthermore, this phase field shows a solubility of 30-33 at.% Al in the binary Ti–Al system. Due to the decomposition of Ti_3Al into (αTi) and TiAl at 1200 °C [28, 29] the phase field should only be connected to the boundary system at one composition (~32 at.%). In contrast to this Takeyama et al. [113] suggested the existence of an isolated Ti_3Al phase field in the ternary composition triangle and Kainuma et al. [106] did not report Ti_3Al to be stable at 1200 °C. There is also not much information available on the stability range of ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)_o at temperatures above 1000 °C. This once again underlines the need for further investigations and critical evaluation of the reported phase equilibria in this temperature range.

Based on the experimental results available at the time a thermodynamic description of the Ti–Al–Nb system was published [73] alongside several isothermal sections at certain temperatures [73, 83, 114]. This description was later updated by Witusiewicz et al. [84] and Cupid et al. [115] since more data became available, especially in the composition range Ti-(40-50)Al-(2-10)Nb [106, 112, 116-118]. However, due to the above described inconsistencies in literature the agreement between modelling and experiment needs improvement (c.f. Fig. 16a in Ref. [84]).

4.2.2 Results

The phase and alloy compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters measured after the different heat treatments are summarized in Tables 11-14. In the following, some characteristic microstructures of the heat-treated alloys and the resulting phase equilibria are presented.

Table 11 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 1000 °C for 400 h (accuracy of the lattice parameters is ± 0.001 Å, n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase composition measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)	Pearson symbol	Lattice parameters (Å)	
			Al	Nb			a	c
TAN1	Ti-17.8Al-4.8Nb	(β Ti,Nb)	17.7 ± 0.2	4.7 ± 0.1	96	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.	
		Ti ₃ Al	23.0 ± 0.2	2.8 ± 0.1	4	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.	n.d.
TAN2 ^a	Ti-17.6Al-10.1Nb	(β Ti,Nb)	17.6 ± 0.1	10.1 ± 0.1	100	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.	
TAN3 ^a	Ti-19.7Al-17.7Nb	(β Ti,Nb)	19.7 ± 0.1	17.7 ± 0.3	100	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.	
TAN4	Ti-25.2Al-13.9Nb	(β Ti,Nb) _o	24.2 ± 0.1	16.3 ± 0.2	55	<i>cP2</i>	3.245	
		Ti ₃ Al	26.6 ± 0.2	11.0 ± 0.1	45	<i>hP8</i>	5.789	4.662
TAN5 ^a	Ti-25.0Al-24.9Nb	(β Ti,Nb) _o	25.0 ± 0.2	24.9 ± 0.3	100	<i>cP2</i>	n.d.	
TAN6	Ti-30.4Al-22.9Nb	(β Ti,Nb) _o	29.1 ± 0.2	20.1 ± 0.3	77 ^b	<i>cP2</i>	3.236	
		Ti ₃ Al	28.2 ± 0.2	14.2 ± 0.2	8 ^b	<i>hP8</i>	5.790	4.680
		Nb ₂ Al	32.5 ± 0.2	32.8 ± 0.6	15 ^b	<i>tP30</i>	9.943	5.137
TAN7	Ti-32.8Al-12.2Nb	(β Ti,Nb) _o	33.3 ± 0.2	12.4 ± 0.3	84	<i>cP2</i>	3.226	
		Ti ₃ Al	32.3 ± 0.2	9.1 ± 0.3	16	<i>hP8</i>	5.778	4.656
TAN8	Ti-32.4Al-17.3Nb	(β Ti,Nb) _o	32.4 ± 0.1	17.2 ± 0.2	98	<i>cP2</i>	3.229	
		Ti ₃ Al	30.9 ± 0.1	12.3 ± 0.2	2	<i>hP8</i>	5.777	4.681
TAN9	Ti-37.2Al-10.0Nb	(β Ti,Nb) _o	35.8 ± 0.1	10.7 ± 0.1	64	<i>cP2</i>	3.223	
		Ti ₃ Al	36.2 ± 0.2	8.0 ± 0.1	32	<i>hP8</i>	5.774	4.644
		TiAl	45.3 ± 0.3	7.7 ± 0.1	5	<i>tP4</i>	4.030	4.061
TAN10 ^c	Ti-36.7Al-12.9Nb	(β Ti,Nb) _o	34.9 ± 0.2	13.3 ± 0.1	81	<i>cP2</i>	3.223 ^d	
		TiAl	44.6 ± 0.2	10.0 ± 0.2	19	<i>tP4</i>	4.035 ^d	4.060

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase composition measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)	Pearson symbol	Lattice parameters (Å)	
			Al	Nb			a	c
TAN11	Ti-39.1Al-9.5Nb	(βTi,Nb) _o	35.5 ± 0.4	11.1 ± 0.2	46	<i>cP2</i>	n.d.	
		Ti ₃ Al	36.0 ± 0.3	8.3 ± 0.2	17	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.	n.d.
		TiAl	44.9 ± 0.3	8.1 ± 0.2	36	<i>tP4</i>	n.d.	n.d.
TAN12 ^c	Ti-40.2Al-19.1Nb	(βTi,Nb) _o ^e	35.5 ± 1.0	18.0 ± 1.0	22	<i>cP2</i>	3.228 ^d	
		TiAl	45.3 ± 0.4	13.6 ± 0.1	48	<i>tP4</i>	4.032 ^d	4.074
		Nb ₂ Al	35.2 ± 0.4	29.9 ± 0.4	29	<i>tP30</i>	9.929 ^d	5.134
TAN13 ^e	Ti-43.7Al-5.3Nb	Ti ₃ Al	36.9 ± 0.6	5.4 ± 0.2	26	<i>hP8</i>	5.777	4.634
		TiAl	46.1 ± 0.4	5.0 ± 0.5	74	<i>tP4</i>	4.014	4.062
TAN14	Ti-45.8Al-5.9Nb	Ti ₃ Al	37.1 ± 0.3	6.0 ± 0.2	7	<i>hP8</i>	5.770	4.637
		TiAl	46.5 ± 0.3	5.6 ± 0.2	93	<i>tP4</i>	4.017	4.063
TAN15 ^c	Ti-43.9Al-12.3	(βTi,Nb) _o	35.3 ± 0.2	16.2 ± 0.3	16	<i>cP2</i>	3.225	
		TiAl	45.5 ± 0.2	11.9 ± 0.3	84	<i>tP4</i>	4.032	4.064

^a DTA measurements (Figure 26) show that this alloy is single-phase (βTi,Nb) at 1000 °C despite small phase fractions of Ti₃Al observed in the microstructure

^b Phase fractions determined by HEXRD measurement

^c Alloy contains small amount of Ti₃Al which is not considered an equilibrium phase, see Section 4.1.2

^d Lattice parameters determined by XRD measurements

^e Phase composition determined based on tie-line data of alloy TAN15, see Section 4.2.3.1.1

Table 12 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 1100 °C for 200 h (accuracy of the lattice parameters is ± 0.001 Å, n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase composition measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)	Pearson symbol	Lattice parameters (Å)	
			Al	Nb			a	c
TAN1	Ti-17.4Al-4.8Nb	(βTi,Nb)	17.4 ± 0.1	4.8 ± 0.1	100	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.	
TAN2	Ti-18.4Al-9.6Nb	(βTi,Nb)	18.4 ± 0.1	9.6 ± 0.1	100	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.	
TAN3	Ti-20.2Al-17.2Nb	(βTi,Nb)	20.2 ± 0.1	17.2 ± 0.1	100	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.	
TAN4	Ti-24.1Al-14.5Nb	(βTi,Nb) _o	24.1 ± 0.1	14.5 ± 0.1	100	<i>cP2</i>	n.d.	
TAN5	Ti-25.8Al-23.8Nb	(βTi,Nb) _o	25.8 ± 0.2	23.8 ± 0.2	100	<i>cP2</i>	n.d.	

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase composition measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)	Pearson symbol	Lattice parameters (Å)	
			Al	Nb			a	c
			TAN6	Ti-30.9Al-24.8Nb			(β Ti,Nb) _o	30.1 ± 0.2
		Nb ₂ Al	33.6 ± 0.1	34.0 ± 0.5	26	<i>tP30</i>	n.d.	n.d.
TAN7	Ti-33.4Al-11.5Nb	(β Ti,Nb) _o	33.3 ± 0.2	11.7 ± 0.1	95	<i>cP2</i>	3.226	
		Ti ₃ Al	32.5 ± 0.2	8.8 ± 0.1	5	<i>hP8</i>	5.772	4.677
TAN8	Ti-32.3Al-16.6Nb	(β Ti,Nb) _o	32.3 ± 0.3	16.6 ± 0.3	100	<i>cP2</i>	3.227 ^d	
		(β Ti,Nb) _o	36.9 ± 0.2	10.0 ± 0.2	72	<i>cP2</i>	3.219	
TAN9	Ti-37.2Al-10.0Nb ^b	Ti ₃ Al	38.1 ± 0.2	8.0 ± 0.2	26	<i>hP8</i>	5.767	4.640
		TiAl	45.7 ± 0.1	7.6 ± 0.2	2	<i>tP4</i>	4.027	4.057
TAN10 ^c	Ti-37.0Al-13.5Nb ^a	(β Ti,Nb) _o	36.4 ± 1.0	13.1 ± 1.0	n.d.	<i>cP2</i>	n.d.	
		TiAl	45.0 ± 1.0	10.2 ± 1.0	n.d.	<i>tP4</i>	n.d.	n.d.
		(β Ti,Nb) _o	36.9 ± 0.2	10.5 ± 0.2	46	<i>cP2</i>	n.d.	
TAN11	Ti-40.3Al-9.3Nb	Ti ₃ Al	38.3 ± 0.2	8.4 ± 0.1	19	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.	n.d.
		TiAl	45.8 ± 0.4	8.2 ± 0.1	35	<i>tP4</i>	n.d.	n.d.
		(β Ti,Nb) _o	36.3 ± 0.2	17.0 ± 0.2	25	<i>cP2</i>	3.217 ^d	
TAN12	Ti-41.2Al-18.0Nb	TiAl	45.4 ± 0.3	13.6 ± 0.1	50	<i>tP4</i>	4.019 ^d	4.060 ^d
		Nb ₂ Al	35.9 ± 0.2	30.7 ± 0.3	21	<i>tP30</i>	9.899 ^d	5.119 ^d
		Ti ₃ Al	37.8 ± 0.4	5.0 ± 0.2	22	<i>hP8</i>	5.765 ^d	4.637 ^d
TAN13	Ti-43.6Al-5.1Nb	TiAl	45.3 ± 0.4	5.0 ± 0.2	78	<i>tP4</i>	4.014 ^d	4.060 ^d
		Ti ₃ Al	37.1 ± 0.3	5.8 ± 0.1	n.d. ^c	<i>hP8</i>	5.766	4.640
TAN14	Ti-45.8Al-5.9Nb	TiAl	45.0 ± 0.2	5.9 ± 0.1	n.d. ^c	<i>tP4</i>	4.014	4.060
		(β Ti,Nb) _o	36.1 ± 0.3	15.2 ± 0.2	8	<i>cP2</i>	3.224 ^d	
TAN15 ^c	Ti-44.4Al-11.9Nb	TiAl	45.0 ± 0.2	11.9 ± 0.3	92	<i>tP4</i>	4.022 ^d	4.067 ^d
		(β Ti,Nb) _o	35.1 ± 0.2	7.2 ± 0.3	66	<i>cP2</i>	n.d.	
TAN16	Ti-35.0Al-6.7Nb	Ti ₃ Al	35.3 ± 0.2	5.5 ± 1.0	34	<i>hP8</i>	n.d.	n.d.

^a Nominal composition.

^b As-cast composition. Phase fractions from HEXRD since the as-cast composition lies outside the tie-triangle.

^c Alloy contains small amount of Ti₃Al which is not considered an equilibrium phase, see Section 4.1.2

^d Lattice parameters determined by XRD measurements.

Table 13 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 1200 °C for 20 h (accuracy of the lattice parameters is $\pm 0.001 \text{ \AA}$, n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase composition measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)	Pearson Symbol	Lattice parameters (\AA)	
			Al	Nb			a	c
TAN5	Ti-24.1Al-25.2Nb	($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)	24.1 ± 0.1	25.2 ± 0.2	100	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.	
TAN6	Ti-30.6Al-24.7Nb	($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) _o	30.4 ± 0.2	24.5 ± 0.3	97	<i>cP2</i>	n.d.	
		Nb ₂ Al	33.4 ± 0.2	36.3 ± 0.5	3	<i>tP30</i>	n.d.	n.d.
TAN8	Ti-32.3Al-16.9Nb	($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) _o	32.3 ± 0.3	16.9 ± 0.3	100	<i>cP2</i>	n.d.	
TAN9	Ti-35.2Al-9.8Nb	($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) _o	35.2 ± 0.2	9.8 ± 0.2	100	<i>cP2</i>	3.219	
TAN10 ^b	Ti-36.5Al-12.8Nb	($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) _o	36.5 ± 0.2	12.8 ± 0.2	100	<i>cP2</i>	3.220 ^e	
TAN11	Ti-40.0Al-9.5Nb	(αTi)	40.0 ± 0.2	8.3 ± 0.2	16	<i>hP2</i>	d	
		($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) _o	37.4 ± 0.5	10.3 ± 0.1	58	<i>cP2</i>	3.218	
		TiAl	45.8 ± 0.2	8.4 ± 0.1	26	<i>tP4</i>	4.024	4.064
TAN12	Ti-39.6Al-19.5Nb	TiAl	45.4 ± 0.2	15.4 ± 0.2	23	<i>tP4</i>	n.d.	n.d.
		($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) _o	38.1 ± 0.5	19.0 ± 0.3	67	<i>cP2</i>	n.d.	
		Nb ₂ Al	36.5 ± 0.3	32.2 ± 0.3	10	<i>tP30</i>	n.d.	n.d.
TAN13	Ti-43.4Al-4.9Nb ^a	(αTi)	39.9 ± 0.3	5.0 ± 0.2	43	<i>hP2</i>	d	
		TiAl	45.7 ± 0.3	4.9 ± 0.1	57	<i>tP4</i>	n.d.	n.d.
TAN14	Ti-43.6Al-5.8Nb	(αTi)	39.7 ± 0.2	6.1 ± 0.2	36	<i>hP2</i>	d	
		TiAl	45.5 ± 0.4	5.9 ± 0.3	64	<i>tP4</i>	n.d.	n.d.
TAN15 ^b	Ti-41.9Al-12.4Nb	($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) _o	37.4 ± 0.3	14.1 ± 0.2	48	<i>cP2</i>	3.221	
		TiAl	45.8 ± 0.2	11.6 ± 0.2	52	<i>tP4</i>	4.026	4.066
TAN16	Ti-34.6Al-6.5Nb	($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) _o	34.6 ± 0.2	6.5 ± 0.1	100	<i>cP2</i>	n.d.	
TAN17	Ti-37.0Al-6.5Nb	($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) _o	37.0 ± 0.2	6.5 ± 0.1	100	<i>cP2</i>	n.d.	

^a As-cast composition.

^b Alloy contains small amount of Ti₃Al which is not considered an equilibrium phase, see Section 4.1.2

^c Lattice parameters determined by XRD measurements.

^d (αTi) undergoes phase transformation to Ti₃Al during quenching. Therefore, no lattice parameters could be determined.

Table 14 EPMA and HEXRD results on phase contents, alloy and phase compositions, phase fractions, and lattice parameters of alloys heat-treated at 1300 °C for 30 h (accuracy of the lattice parameters is ± 0.001 Å, n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase composition measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)	Pearson Symbol	Lattice parameters (Å)	
			Al	Nb			a	c
TAN5	Ti-25.4Al-23.6Nb	(β Ti,Nb)	25.4 ± 0.2	23.6 ± 0.3	100	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.	
TAN6	Ti-30.7Al-23.9Nb	(β Ti,Nb)	30.7 ± 0.2	23.9 ± 0.3	100	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.	
TAN8	Ti-32.8Al-16.8Nb	(β Ti,Nb)	32.8 ± 0.2	16.8 ± 0.2	100	<i>cI2</i>	3.228	
TAN9	Ti-37.5Al-9.5Nb	(β Ti,Nb)	37.5 ± 0.2	9.5 ± 0.1	100	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.	
TAN11	Ti-39.5Al-9.7Nb	(β Ti,Nb)	39.5 ± 0.2	9.7 ± 0.2	100	<i>cI2</i>	3.212	
TAN12	Ti-39.8Al-19.4Nb	(β Ti,Nb)	39.8 ± 0.3	19.4 ± 0.2	100	<i>cI2</i>	n.d.	
TAN13	Ti-44.4Al-4.8Nb	(α Ti)	44.1 ± 0.2	4.7 ± 0.1	93	<i>hP2</i>	b	
		TiAl	48.8 ± 0.9	4.7 ± 0.1	7	<i>tP4</i>	4.003^a	4.060^a
TAN14	Ti-45.5Al-5.7Nb	(α Ti) ^b	44.0 ± 0.2	5.5 ± 0.2	66	<i>hP2</i>	b	
		TiAl	48.6 ± 0.3	5.4 ± 0.2	34	<i>tP4</i>	4.004^a	4.069^a
TAN15	Ti-44.2Al-12.1Nb	(α Ti) ^b	43.2 ± 0.6	11.7 ± 0.2	6	<i>hP2</i>	b	
		(β Ti,Nb)	40.8 ± 0.8	13.1 ± 0.2	40	<i>cI2</i>	3.217	
		TiAl	46.8 ± 0.6	11.4 ± 0.2	54	<i>tP4</i>	4.013	4.074

^a Lattice parameter determined by XRD measurement

^b (α Ti) undergoes phase transformation to Ti₃Al during quenching. Therefore, no lattice parameters could be determined.

The microstructure of alloy TAN1 (Ti-17.4Al-4.8Nb) quenched from 1000 °C (Figure 25a) consists of a Ti₃Al (dark phase) and a (β Ti,Nb) matrix. In the BSE image, two different contrasts are observed in the matrix. No variations in composition could be measured by EPMA in the matrix. This can be explained by a martensitic transformation which takes place during quenching and has been observed by HEXRD measurements in alloy TAN1 heat-treated at 800 and 900 °C (Tables 7 and 8). Since this transformation does not change the composition, but only the appearance of the microstructure, two things are concluded: i) the measured composition is identical to the composition of (β Ti,Nb) at 1000 °C and ii) the martensitic transformation is responsible for the two observed contrasts in the matrix phase. At 1100 °C, (β Ti,Nb) is the only microstructure constituent, which is consistent with the DTA measurements showing that the continuous dissolution of Ti₃Al is finished at 1022 °C.

Figure 25 BSE image of a) alloy TAN1 (Ti-17.4Al-4.8Nb) quenched from 1000 °C showing a two-phase microstructure (martensitic decomposed (βTi,Nb) + Ti₃Al) and b) alloy TAN3 (Ti-20.0Al-17.5Nb) quenched from 1100 °C being single-phase (βTi,Nb).

Alloys TAN2 (Ti-17.5Al-10.0Nb) and TAN3 (Ti-20.0Al-17.5Nb) are single-phase (βTi,Nb) at 1000 and 1100 °C, which is confirmed by DTA measurements. In Figure 26, a continuous deviation from the base line (dashed line) is observed. This results from the continuous dissolution of Ti₃Al and ends at 995 (TAN2) and 985 °C (TAN3), whereupon the heat flow signal returns to the baseline.

Figure 26 DTA heat flow curve of alloys TAN2 and TAN3 showing the dissolution of Ti₃Al at 985 °C (TAN3) and 995 °C (TAN2). The grey dashed line indicates the baseline.

In alloy TAN4 (Ti-24.6Al-14.9Nb), a two-phase microstructure consisting of B2-ordered ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) and Ti_3Al is observed in the sample quenched from 1000 °C (Figure 27a). This is confirmed by HEXRD measurements of this sample (Figure 27b) as well as by *in situ* HEXRD measurements. Ti_3Al has formed predominantly at the grain boundaries of the ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)_o grains. At 1100 °C, this alloy is single-phase ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)_o.

Alloy TAN5 (Ti-25.0Al-25.0Nb) shows a single-phase microstructure over the complete temperature range. The ordered ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)_o phase is present up to 1169 °C, where disordering is completed (as obtained by DTA, see Table 17).

a)

b)

c)

d)

Figure 27 BSE image of alloy TAN4 (Ti-24.6Al-14.9Nb) heat treated at 1000 °C with a two-phase microstructure consisting of ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)_o (bright) and Ti_3Al (dark); b) respective HEXRD pattern (with logarithmic intensity scale) confirming the microstructural results; c) BSE image of alloy TAN6 (Ti-30.0Al-25.0Nb) heat treated at 1000 °C showing a three-phase microstructure consisting of Nb_2Al (bright), Ti_3Al (dark) and ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)_o (grey); d) respective HEXRD pattern (with logarithmic intensity scale) confirming the microstructural results.

The three phases $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$, Ti_3Al , and Nb_2Al are observed in the microstructure of alloy TAN6 (Ti-30.0Al-25.0Nb) quenched from 1000 °C (Figure 27c), which is confirmed by HEXRD measurements (Figure 27d). At 1100 and 1200 °C, the microstructure consists of Nb_2Al and a $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ matrix. At 1300 °C, the microstructure is single-phase and only the A2-disordered $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ phase is present, since disordering finished at 1243 °C (Table 17).

Alloy TAN7 (Ti-32.8Al-12.2Nb) shows a two-phase microstructure consisting of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ and Ti_3Al at 1000 (Figure 28a) and 1100 °C. The same two phases are observed in alloy TAN8 (Ti-32.4Al-17.3Nb) quenched from 1000 °C (Figure 28b). At higher temperature this alloy is single-phase $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ with B2-ordering present up to 1248 °C (Table 17).

Figure 28 BSE images of a) alloy TAN7 (Ti-32.8Al-12.2Nb) and b) alloy TAN8 (Ti-32.4Al-17.3Nb) heat treated at 1000 °C showing a two-phase microstructure between $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ (bright) and Ti_3Al (dark).

Both alloys TAN9 (Ti-37.2Al-10.0Nb) and TAN11 (Ti-39.6Al-10.0Nb) show a three-phase microstructure composed of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$, Ti_3Al , and TiAl at 1000 and 1100 °C (Figure 29a,b). For alloy B11, the *in situ* HEXRD measurements (Fig. 9) show that the transformation of Ti_3Al to (αTi) is finished at ~1170 °C. This is also confirmed by DTA measurements, which show that the transition takes place at 1171 °C. Therefore, at 1200 °C the equilibrium phases are (αTi) , $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$, and TiAl . With the dissolution of Ti_3Al and TiAl with increasing temperature, as well as the disordering of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$, which is observed with DTA and *in situ* HEXRD measurements, both alloys are single-phase $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ at 1300 °C (Figure 29c). Figure 30a shows the intensity of the (001) and (110) peaks of TiAl in alloy TAN9. A continuous decrease in intensity is observed up to about 1150 °C, which marks the dissolution temperature of TiAl . The intensity of the (100) superstructure reflection of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ shown in Figure 30b

vanishes at the disordering temperature of 1222 °C, which is the same value as obtained by DTA measurements (Table 17).

Figure 29 BSE images of a) alloy TAN9 (Ti-37.2Al-10.0Nb) and b) alloy TAN11 (Ti-39.6Al-10.0Nb) heat treated at 1100 °C showing a three-phase microstructure composed (βTi,Nb)₀ (matrix), Ti₃Al (grey), and TiAl (dark); c) alloy TAN11 heat-treated at 1300 °C with single-phase (βTi,Nb) microstructure.

Figure 30 Intensity over temperature plot of a) the (001) and (110) peak of TiAl, showing the dissolution of TiAl at about 1150 °C in alloy TAN9 (Ti-37.2Al-10.0Nb); b) the (001) superstructure reflection of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ showing the disordering of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ at 1222 °C (data obtained by *in situ* HEXRD measurements).

For alloy TAN11, the *in situ* HEXRD measurements (Figure 31) show that the transformation of Ti_3Al to (αTi) is finished at ~ 1170 °C, which is also observed with DTA measurements resulting in a transition temperature of 1171 °C (Table 18). Therefore, at 1200 °C the equilibrium phases are (αTi) , $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$, and TiAl. At 1300 °C, both TAN9 and TAN11 (Figure 29c) are single-phase $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$.

Figure 31 Plot of the *in situ* HEXRD measurement (heating rate 2 °C/min) of alloy TAN11 (Ti-39.6Al-10.0Nb) in the Temperature range between 1000 and 1200 °C showing the presence of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ + Ti_3Al + TiAl above 1000 °C. The (100) and (101) superstructure reflexions of Ti_3Al are observed up to ~ 1170 °C. At higher temperatures (αTi) is stable instead.

TiAl and $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ are present in the microstructure of alloy TAN10 (Ti-37.0Al-13.5Nb) at 1000 and 1100 °C. Since the *B2*-ordering of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ disappears above 1225 °C (Table 17), the single-phase microstructure observed at 1200 °C must belong to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$.

The three-phase equilibrium $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{TiAl} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$ is observed in alloy TAN12 (Ti-39.8Al-19.9Nb) at 1000 and 1100°C (Figure 32a). The disordering temperature of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ in this alloy lies at 1199 °C (Table 17), therefore the three-phases observed at 1200 °C are $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$, TiAl, and Nb_2Al (Figure 32b). The phase fraction of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o/(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ phase has increased at 1200 °C, and at 1300 °C the alloy is finally single-phase $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$.

Figure 32 BSE image of alloy TAN12 (Ti-39.8Al-19.9Nb) heat treated at a) 1100 °C showing a three-phase microstructure composed of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ (grey), TiAl (dark), and Nb_2Al (bright) and b) 1200 °C showing the same three-phase microstructure but with the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ phase being disordered now according to the DTA results.

A two-phase microstructure is observed in alloys TAN13 (Ti-43.4Al-4.9Nb) and TAN14 (Ti-45.8Al-5.9Nb) over the entire temperature range (Figure 33a-c). DTA measurements show, that the transformation from Ti_3Al to (αTi) takes place at 1143 and 1159 °C, respectively (Table 18). Therefore, the phases in equilibrium at and below 1100 °C are Ti_3Al and TiAl, while at 1200 °C the stable phases are (αTi) and TiAl. These phase equilibria have been confirmed by DTA, XRD and HEXRD measurements. From 1000 to 1200 °C, $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{TiAl}$ is observed in the quenched samples of alloy TAN15 (Ti-44.7Al-12.3Nb). At 1300 °C, the three-phase equilibrium consisting of (αTi) , $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$, and TiAl was observed (Figure 33d) and has been confirmed by HEXRD measurements.

Alloys TAN16 (Ti-35.0Al-5.0Nb) and TAN17 (Ti-37.0Al-7.0Nb) both show a single-phase $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ microstructure after quenching from 1200 °C. When quenched from 1100 °C

alloy TAN16 consists of Ti_3Al and $(\beta Ti, Nb)_\alpha$ as was determined by *in situ* HEXRD measurements.

Figure 33 BSE image of a) alloy TAN13 (Ti-43.4Al-4.9Nb) heat treated at 1100 °C showing a two-phase microstructure consisting of Ti_3Al (bright) and TiAl (dark); b) alloy TAN13 heat treated at 1200 °C showing a two-phase microstructure consisting of (αTi) (bright) and TiAl (dark); c) alloy TAN14 (Ti-45.8Al-5.9Nb) heat treated at 1300 °C showing a two-phase microstructure consisting of (αTi) (bright) and TiAl (dark); d) alloy TAN15 (Ti-44.7Al-12.3Nb) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing the three-phase equilibrium between (αTi) (grey), $(\beta Ti, Nb)$ (bright), and TiAl (dark).

4.2.3 Isothermal sections, phase fields, solubility and phase formation between 1000 and 1300 °C

As with the phase equilibria between 700 and 900 °C (see Section 4.1), partial isothermal sections of the Ti-rich corner from 1000 to 1300 °C (Figures 34-37) were constructed based on the analysis of the present experimental results (Tables 11-14) and some supplementary information from the literature. For the binary boundary systems Ti–Al and Ti–Nb, the assessed phase diagrams [28, 29, 32] already mentioned above in Section 4.1 were used.

The phase fields of (αTi) , $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$, and Ti_3Al and their temperature-dependent evolution are discussed in more detail below.

Figure 34 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 1000 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 11 (symbols same as in Figure 17, unfilled stars: as-cast and nominal alloy composition).

Figure 35 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 1100 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 12 (symbols as in Figure 17).

Figure 36 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 1200 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 13 (symbols as in Figure 17).

Figure 37 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Nb system at 1300 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 14 (symbols as in Figure 17).

4.2.3.1 Phase fields and solubility limits of (βTi,Nb)

4.2.3.1.1 Isolated (βTi,Nb)_o phase field

The isothermal sections at 1000 (Figure 34) and 1100 °C (Figure 35) show an isolated (βTi,Nb)_o island in the ternary composition space, that has formed at 790 °C (see Section 4.1.3.2.3). Such an isolated (βTi,Nb)_o phase field has been previously reported by Hellwig et al. [103, 104], Li et al. [102], and Eckert et al. [105] at 1000 °C.

The Nb-poor limit of this isolated (βTi,Nb)_o phase field is determined by the tie-triangle Ti₃Al + (βTi,Nb)_o + TiAl. The studies of Hellwig et al. [104] and Eckert et al. [105] report the same Al contents of around 36 at.% Al and 12 at.% Nb. The Nb content is about 1 at.% higher than the present values for alloys TAN9 and TAN11, which lies outside the measurement uncertainty, while the value for the Al content is in very good agreement with the present ones (35.8 and 35.5 at.%, respectively) (Table 11). The values of Li et al. [102] are shifted to slightly lower Al and higher Nb contents. It should be noted that Li et al. [102] mention that the weight sums of their EPMA measurements were ranging between 97 and 103 wt.%. This deviation is not within the error of the measurement (± 1 wt.% relative) [119] which indicates the measured

values are not precise. This can result from an incorrect or incomplete standardization or the presence of additional elements in the sample. Therefore, the phase compositions reported by Li et al. [102] should be taken with caution. The phase compositions measured by Eckert et al. [105] are shifted to slightly higher Al contents compared to the measurements presented here. This could be related to the measurement method used (SEM-EDS) which does not use pure elements as standard. Nevertheless, the presented results confirm the existence of the isolated $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ phase field.

The Nb-rich limit of this phase field is determined by the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{TiAl} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$ tie-triangle. For this value, a large scatter is observed in the reported data [102, 104, 105] at 1000 °C. The Nb content measured for $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ in alloy TAN12 is slightly lower than in alloy TAN15. This would lead to an intersection of the tie-triangle (TAN12) and tie-line (TAN15), which is thermodynamically forbidden. Therefore, the value for $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ in alloy TAN12 was estimated such that the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{TiAl}$ side of the tie-triangle is parallel to the tie-line obtained for alloy TAN15. This is indicated by the dashed lines in the isothermal section (Figure 34).

All authors report the same three tie-triangles ($(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{TiAl}$, $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$, and $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{TiAl} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$) at 1000 °C, which determine the homogeneity range of the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ island. The homogeneity range reported here ((32-35) at.% Al and (11-18 at.%) Nb) is similar to that reported by Hellwig et al. [103, 104], who used diffusion couples and heat-treated bulk alloys to determine the phase equilibria. In contrast, Li et al. [102] reported a slightly smaller homogeneity range.

These values together with the results from alloys TAN10 and TAN15 indicate that the Al-rich side of the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ phase field extends along a Al content of 35 at.% Al between 11 and 18 at.% Nb at 1000 °C. At 1100 °C, the maximum Al content increases slightly to 36 at.% with the minimum Nb content decreasing to 7.2 at.% as result of the determined phase compositions in alloy TAN16 (Table 12)

The Al-poor phase boundary is determined by the alloys TAN7 and TAN8 and the maximum Nb content at 1000 °C is to be about 18 at.% at 32 at.% Al. This composition shifts to lower Al and higher Nb contents at 1100 °C. This value is consistent with Hellwig et al. [104] who reported a Nb content of 17.4 at.% and 32.5 at.% Al in the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ phase of the tie-triangle $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$. Additionally, the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al}$ tie-line obtained for alloy TAN8 (Table 11) is located parallel and very close to the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al}$ side of the tie-triangle $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$ reported by Hellwig et al. [104]. Therefore, the position

of this tie-triangle is adopted in the present isothermal section at 1000 °C (Figure 34). The values reported by Li et al. [102] are again shifted, compared to the results from Hellwig et al. [104] and the here presented ones.

The experimental results of Bendersky et al. [20, 120] on two alloys (Ti-37.5Al-20Nb and Ti-37.5Al-12.5Nb) heat-treated at 1100 °C show the presence of two tie-triangles ($(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{TiAl}$ and $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o + \text{TiAl} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$). In combination with further results on the two-phase field $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb}) + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al}$ the calculations for Kattner et al. [83] showed that the isolated $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ phase field is still present at 1100 °C. The tie-lines measured for alloy TAN7 at 1000 and 1100 °C have a similar inclination (Figures 34 and 35). This suggests that the observed phase equilibria belong to the same phases and no significant change to the Nb contents is observed. This would be the case when the isolated $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ phase field and the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ solid solution merge to one phase field, as it is observed at 1200 °C (Figure 36). Therefore, it is concluded that the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ phase field is still present at 1100 °C and has not merged with the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ solid-solution. Also, Eckert et al. [105] came to the same conclusion based on their experimental results. In the study by Li et al. [102] the isolated $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ phase field is no longer present at 1100 °C. Instead, they report the tie-triangle $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{TiAl} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$ (in an alloy with the composition Ti-39.1Al-17.7Nb) alongside the tie-triangle $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb}) + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$ (already reported at 1000 °C). The tie-triangle $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{TiAl} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al}$ must have formed as a result of a ternary peritectoid reaction $(\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{TiAl} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al} \rightleftharpoons (\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o)$. The composition of alloy TAN12 is located within this tie-triangle. Therefore, a strong thermal effect should be observed in the DTA measurement as a result of this invariant reaction. As can be seen from Figure 38 this is not the case. From the presented results it is concluded that at 1100 °C $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ still exists as an isolated island.

Figure 38 DTA heat flow measurement of alloy TAN12 (Ti-39.8Al-19.9Nb) showing no peak between 1000 and 1100 °C, which indicates that no invariant reaction takes place in this temperature interval. At higher temperatures, the disordering of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ at 1199 °C and the dissolution of Nb_2Al at 1224 °C and TiAl at 1253 °C are visible.

4.2.3.1.2 $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ solid-solution

In addition to this $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ island, there exists a second $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ phase field in the partial isothermal sections at 1000 (Figure 34) and 1100 °C (Figure 35) present, which extends from the binary Ti–Nb system towards higher Al contents into the ternary composition space. The maximum Al solubility at 1000 and 1100 °C corresponds to the composition of the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ phase in the three-phase equilibrium with Ti_3Al and Nb_2Al (see Figures 34 and 35). At 1000 °C, alloy TAN6 lies in this tie-triangle and a solubility of 29.1 at.% Al is obtained for the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ phase (Table 11). This value increases only slightly at 1100 °C (Figure 35). The maximum values for the Al solubility reported in the literature vary between 20-30 at.% Al and Nb, but always refer to the composition of the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ phase in the tie-triangle $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al} + (\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ [102, 104]. The presence of this tie-triangle at 1000 °C further demonstrates that the O phase is not an equilibrium phase at 1000 °C, as reported by Kumar et al. [121]. This conclusion is based on the assumption that this three-phase equilibrium formed as a result of the ternary peritectoid dissolution ($\text{Nb}_2\text{Al} + (\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0 + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al} \rightleftharpoons \text{O}$) of the O phase.

At 1200 and 1300 °C (Figures 36 and 37), only one $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ phase field is observed, which is the consequence of the two tie-triangles $\text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{Nb}_2\text{Al} + (\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ above 1100 °C. The calculations from Witusiewicz et al. [84] predict an eutectoid reaction $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0 \rightleftharpoons \text{Nb}_2\text{Al} + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al}$ with a reaction temperature of 1073 °C. As shown above this temperature must lie

above 1100 °C. This reaction also leads to an increase of the maximum solubility of Al in (β Ti,Nb) up to 41 at.% Al at 1300 °C (Table 14 and Figure 37), which is in agreement with the values reported in the literature [100, 106, 112]. There is also a composition range determined by DTA measurements, where the *B2*-ordered (β Ti,Nb) phase is stable. This is indicated throughout the isothermal sections with a dotted line and will be discussed in more detail in Section 4.3.1.1.

4.2.3.2 The (α Ti) and Ti₃Al phase fields

4.2.3.2.1 The Ti₃Al phase field

At 1000 °C, Ti₃Al is stable in a composition range of Ti-(23-37)Al-(0-15)Nb with the maximum Nb content reached in the three-phase equilibrium with (β Ti,Nb)_o and Nb₂Al (Figure 34). This is in agreement with the results shown in [102, 104], where the same solubility value of 15 at.% Nb was reported. At 1100 °C, the maximum Nb content in Ti₃Al remains the same, but considered as a function of Al content, the Nb solubility shows a very particular behaviour. As is well visible in the isothermal section in Figure 35, there is a local solubility minimum of only 5.5 at.% Nb located at 35.0 at.% Al, which is related to the growing (β Ti,Nb)_o phase field. The respective two-phase equilibrium (β Ti,Nb)_o + Ti₃Al is observed in alloy TAN 16 (see Table 12 and Figure 39). To higher Al contents, the Nb solubility increases again to ~8 at.% (reached in the three-phase equilibrium (β Ti,Nb)_o + Ti₃Al + TiAl that occurs in alloys TAN9 and TAN11, Table 12 and Figure 29a,b). In the isothermal section at 1100 °C presented by Li et al. [102], the Ti₃Al phase field has a qualitatively very similar shape with a local minimum of the Nb content at intermediate Al contents. However, this minimum appears to be less pronounced than indicated in the present results, which is related to the absence of the isolated (β Ti,Nb)_o phase field in the isothermal section shown by Li et al. [102].

Figure 39 BSE image of alloy TAN16 (Ti-35.0Al-5.0Nb) heat-treated at 1100 °C showing a two-phase microstructure between (βTi,Nb)₀ (bright) and Ti₃Al (dark).

In the isothermal sections at 1200 and 1300 °C (Figures 36 and 37), Ti₃Al no longer occurs (with the exception of a single point at the Ti–Al binary boundary at 1200 °C as also reported by Kainuma et al. [106]). However, there are two other studies that propose a stable Ti₃Al phase field at 1200 °C extending into the ternary composition space [113, 122]. Based on the accepted dissolution of Ti₃Al at 1200 °C in the binary Ti–Al system [28, 29], this phase field must be connected to the binary system at a single point (composition of Ti₃Al in the binary). In order to study the possible existence of a Ti₃Al phase field in the ternary system at 1200 °C in more detail the two alloys TAN16 and TAN17 were synthesized. Both alloys were found to be single phase after quenching from 1200 °C (with compositions of Ti-34.6Al-6.5Nb and Ti-37.0Al-6.5Nb). However, this does not completely rule out the existence of a Ti₃Al phase field at 1200 °C, since it is still possible that this phase field is stable at Nb contents below 6 at.% and was therefore not found in the alloys studied. Unfortunately, there is no data available in literature that would give indications about the existence of Ti₃Al at 1200 °C at this low Nb levels. In Figure 40, the just described possibility of the existence of Ti₃Al at 1200 °C is superimposed on the isothermal section from Figure 36 with black dashed lines.

Figure 40 Possible Ti_3Al island at 1200 °C (black dashed lines) superimposed on the isothermal section presented in Figure 36.

4.2.3.2.2 The (αTi) solid solution

The binary Ti–Al system (Figure 1) shows that the (αTi) solid solution has two separated phase fields [28, 29], which is also the case in the ternary Ti–Al–Nb system. The Ti-rich (αTi) solid solution is stable up to 1170 °C and dissolves at this temperature in a peritectic reaction $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb}) + \text{Ti}_3\text{Al} \rightleftharpoons (\alpha\text{Ti})$ in the binary Ti–Al system [28, 29]. This means that the Nb solubility in (αTi) must decrease compared to the 4.0 at.% measured at 900 °C (see Section 4.1.3.1). However, there is no direct experimental evidence of the solubility limit at 1000 °C, but a solubility limit of 2 at.% Nb in (αTi) is estimated based in on the tie-line data of alloy TAN1 (Figure 34). At 1100 °C the solubility will further decrease and the tie-triangle is located close to the binary Ti–Al axis of the ternary composition triangle Figure 35.

The Al-rich (αTi) solid solution forms at 1120 °C in the binary Ti–Al system (see Figure 1) and is observed at 1200 °C in the ternary alloy TAN11, TAN13 and TAN14 (Figure 36). There are two possibilities for the formation of the (αTi) phase. Either it forms as a result of the $(\alpha\text{Ti}) \rightleftharpoons \text{Ti}_3\text{Al} + \text{TiAl}$ at 1120 °C in the binary Ti–Al system [28, 29], or an isolated (αTi) phase field forms in the ternary composition triangle, and connects to the binary Ti–Al boundary at

1120 °C. In both cases, the solubility of Nb in (α Ti) increases with increasing temperature. The experimentally determined transition temperatures for alloys TAN11, TAN13, and TAN14 (Table 18) show a systematic increase as function of the Nb content of the alloy, which is consistent with other experimental results from literature on alloys with different compositions [84, 86, 123-126]. Furthermore, *in situ* neutron diffraction experiments by Kononikhina et al. [127] on two alloys (Ti-42Al and Ti-42Al-2Nb) indicate that the transition from Ti_3Al to (α Ti) in the binary alloy occurs at a temperature just below the ternary one. All experimental observations strongly support the formation of (α Ti) at 1120 °C in the binary and a temperature dependent increase of the Nb solubility in (α Ti). Based on these experimental observations the formation of an isolated (α Ti) phase field above 1120 °C in the ternary composition space as predicted by Witusiewicz et al. [84] is unlikely. Since there is no clear experimental evidence and also no need for this isolated phase field for the construction of the reaction scheme (see Section 4.5), the second possibility for the formation of (α Ti) is excluded.

As a result of the eutectoid reaction (α Ti) \rightleftharpoons Ti_3Al + TiAl at 1120 °C, the tie-triangle (α Ti) + Ti_3Al + TiAl must be present at higher temperatures. At 1200 °C, the tie-triangle (α Ti) \rightleftharpoons (β Ti,Nb)_o + TiAl is observed instead (Figure 36). This tie-triangle is assumed to have formed as a result of the transition reaction (α Ti) + Ti_3Al \rightleftharpoons (β Ti,Nb)_o + TiAl of the just mentioned tie-triangle and the tie-triangle Ti_3Al + (β Ti,Nb)_o + TiAl found at 1100 °C in alloy TAN9 and TAN11 (Table 12). This reaction is estimated to take place at 1170 \pm 5 °C, corresponding to the transformation temperature determined by *in situ* HEXRD in alloy TAN11 (Figure 31). This type of reaction was proposed by Takeyama et al. [122] and, according to Shaaban et al. [128], occurs between 1140 and 1200 °C in the Ti–Al–V system. Since V is in the same group in the periodic table of elements as Nb, and the observed transition temperatures in both systems are similar, there is a chance that these two systems undergo the same transformations. As a result of the transition-type reaction, a second tie-triangle (α Ti) + Ti_3Al \rightleftharpoons (β Ti,Nb)_o must exist above the transformation temperature. This tie-triangle is not observed in the present experiments, since Ti_3Al is assumed to decompose at 1200 °C as explained above in Section 4.2.3.2.1.

The maximum solubility of Nb in (α Ti) is always determined by the composition of (α Ti) in the tie-triangle (α Ti) + Ti_3Al + TiAl. At 1300 °C 11.7 at.% Nb are measured in (α Ti) (Table 14). The values reported in literature differ between 11 and 15 at.% Nb while Al content always agrees (about 43 at.%) [100, 106, 112]. A possible explanation for the significant variations in Nb content reported in the literature is discussed in Section 4.4.

Besides the investigations on the phase equilibria presented above, the Ti–Al–Nb system is very well suited for studying the fundamental thermodynamics of various types of solid-solid phase transformations. Type and kinetics of these transformations play an important role in determining the correct phase equilibria, especially at lower temperatures, as is evident from the research presented in Section 4.1.3.2. The results of a systematic DTA investigation of the solid-state phase transformations in Ti–Al–Nb alloys are discussed in the following section.

4.3 Thermal analysis of solid-solid phase transformations³

The phase equilibrium investigations of Ti–Al–Nb alloys presented above show that there are different types of solid-solid transformations in this system. As the experiments discussed in this chapter will show, they behave very differently in terms of their kinetics. On the one hand, there are order/disorder transformations (*B2/A2* transition from ordered $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ to the disordered $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ phase), which proceed without any long-range diffusional processes and the transition temperature only changes as function of composition [129]. This can be seen by the changing homogeneity range of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ in the presented isothermal sections (Figures 19 and 34-37). On the other hand, more complex transformations requiring long-range diffusion to occur involving changes in composition, crystal lattice, and phase fractions [129]. Examples of this type of transformation in the Ti–Al–Nb systems are reactions involving Ti_3Al and the two ternary phases O and ω_o . Based on the diffusional character of the transformation, which was confirmed by *in situ* HEXRD measurements of Stark et al. [130] for the transformation from ω_o to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$, it can be assumed that a heating rate dependent transformation temperature is observed in the DTA measurements. The transformation temperatures of Ti_3Al to (αTi) , O to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$, and ω_o to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ all show a non-linear dependence on the heating rate. Therefore, a model developed by Zhu et al. [131, 132] specifically for sluggish solid phase transformations was used to determine the equilibrium transformation temperatures at a heating rate of $0^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. This model will be briefly explained in Section 4.3.2.

For the DTA experiments, samples pre-annealed at 700°C were used (except for alloys TAN5, TAN16, and TAN17 that were studied in the as-cast state, alloy TAN4 and TAN10,

³ This chapter is based on the following publication: [93] B. Distl, K. Hauschildt, F. Pyczak, and F. Stein, Solid-Solid Phase Transformations and Their Kinetics in Ti–Al–Nb Alloys, *Metals*, 2021, **11**(12), p 1991. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met11121991>

where the heat-treated state 1000 °C/400 h was used, and alloy TA1, where the as-cast alloy was held at 1000 °C for 60 h in the DTA) as described in the Section 3.2.4. In some cases, additional samples heat-treated at 800, 900, and/or 1000 °C were measured to check how and if the heat treatment condition affects the phase transformation temperature. The alloys investigated and the transformations that occurred are summarised in Table 15. First, the results of the DTA measurements for the different phase transformations are presented and then discussed in comparison with the available literature.

Table 15 Types of phase transformations that occur in the various alloys studied are marked with “x” (for simplicity, only the phases that transform into each other are mentioned, although other phases may be involved whose phase fraction and composition also change).

Alloy No.	Alloy composition (at.%)			Heating rate dependent			Heating rate independent
	Ti	Al	Nb	ω_o to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$	O to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$	Ti_3Al to (αTi)	$(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$
TA1	57.1	42.9	0			x	
TAN4	60.9	25.2	13.9		x		x
TAN5	50.7	24.1	25.2		x		x
TAN6	45.4	30.7	23.9		x		x
TAN7	55.6	32.7	11.6	x			x
TAN8	50.4	32.8	16.8	x	*		x
TAN9	53.9	36.4	9.7	x		*	x
TAN10	49.5	37.0	13.5	x			x
TAN11	50.8	39.8	9.4	x		x	x
TAN12	40.4	39.6	20.0	x			x
TAN13	50.8	44.3	4.9			x	
TAN14	49.0	45.8	5.2			x	
TAN15	43.8	44.5	11.7	x			x
TAN16	60.0	35.0	5.0				x
TAN17	56.0	37.0	7.0				x

* transformation temperatures could not be reliably measured by DTA because of a very small phase fraction of the transforming phase and/or proximity of the critical temperature to another reaction in the same alloy.

4.3.1 Heating rate independent transition ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)_o to ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)

Except for alloys TAN1, TAN13, and TAN14, all alloys listed in Table 15 contain the ordered ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)_o phase, which disorders at high temperatures. The measured transition temperatures of selected alloys are displayed in Figure 41a, which shows that the transition temperature is independent of the heating rate. Furthermore, the deviation from the average values determined for the order/disorder transition does not exceed 1 °C (exceptions are the 1 °C/min measurement of TAN8 (32.8Al-16.8Nb) and 5 °C/min measurement of TAN11 (Ti-39.8Al-9.4Nb) showing a still small deviation of 2 °C).

Figure 41 a) Order/disorder temperatures for the ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)_o to ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$) transition in selected alloys measured with heating rates of 1, 2, 5, and 10 °C/min; b) comparison of a heating and respective cooling heat flow curve of TAN8 (Ti-32.8Al-16.8Nb) the same transition temperature during heating and cooling.

As the results for alloys TAN9 and TAN15 listed in Table 16 show, different preceding heat treatments obviously have no effect on the measured order/disorder temperature of ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)_o. Moreover, comparisons were made of the reaction temperature on heating and cooling. As Figure 41b shows, the order/disorder temperature of alloy TAN8 on heating coincides with the onset temperature of ordering on cooling. The same is true for all other alloys showing the order/disorder transition. In addition, the slope change of the DTA heat flow curve before the transition is very shallow (Figure 41b). This means that there is no sudden onset of disorder. Instead, the ordered structure disorders continuously over a wide temperature range and the process is finished at the peak maximum of the heat flow curve during heating, which corresponds to the order/disorder transition temperature. Such a transition is a typical example for a second-order type transformation [129]. The same characteristics were observed in

literature for example by Das et al. [31], who investigated two ternary Ti-Al-Nb alloys using DTA as well as by Malinov et al. [133] in quaternary Ti-Al-Nb-Cr alloys. These observations can be explained by the fact that the $B2$ -ordered $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ and $A2$ -disordered $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ both have a cubic body-centered crystal lattice and the only difference is that in the case of the disordered $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$, the lattice sites are statistically occupied by the different types of atoms. In the low-temperature, ordered $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ state, the degree of ordering continuously decreases with increasing temperature due to thermally induced jumps of atoms to other crystal lattice sites resulting in a shallow slope change in the heat flow curve until there is no ordered $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ left at the transition temperature.

Table 16 Disorder temperature of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ as measured with constant heating rate of 10 °C/min for differently heat-treated samples of the alloys TAN9 (Ti-36.4Al-9.7Nb) and TAN15 (Ti-44.5Al-11.7Nb).

Heat treatment temperature (°C) and time (h)	Disordering temperature (°C)	
	TAN9 (Ti-36.4Al-9.7Nb)	TAN15 (Ti-44.5Al-11.7Nb)
700 / 1500	1222	1204
900 / 650	1223	1204
1000 / 400	1223	1204

The equilibrium disordering temperatures of all investigated alloys are summarized in Table 17. Since there is no change in disordering temperature with heating rate the measured disordering temperatures correspond to the equilibrium transformation temperature at 0 °C/min heating rate.

Table 17 Equilibrium disordering temperatures of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ for alloys TAN4-12 and TAN15-17 with the respective composition of the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ phase.

Alloy No.	Phase composition of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ (at.%)			Disordering temperature (°C)
	Ti	Al	Nb	
TAN4	60.9	25.2	13.9	1104 ± 1
TAN5	50.7	24.1	25.2	1169 ± 1
TAN6	45.4	30.7	23.9	1243 ± 1
TAN7	55.6	32.7	11.6	1237 ± 1
TAN8	50.4	32.8	16.8	1248 ± 1
TAN9	54.4	35.8	9.8	1222 ± 1

Alloy No.	Phase composition of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ (at.%)			Disordering temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
	Ti	Al	Nb	
TAN10	50.7	36.5	12.8	1225 ± 1
TAN11	52.3	37.4	10.4	1201 ± 1
TAN12	42.9	38.1	19.0	1199 ± 1
TAN15	49.8	35.0	15.2	1204 ± 1
TAN16	58.9	34.6	6.5	1214 ± 1
TAN17	56.5	37.0	6.5	1209 ± 1

4.3.1.1 Stability range of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$

As can be already seen from the isothermal sections presented in Section 4.1 and 4.2, there is a certain composition range where $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ is stable, which is indicated by the dotted lines. This line is the second-order $B2/A2$ transition line and is approximated based on the results measured here and the literature discussed below. A plot of the compositions of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ and the respective disordering temperatures determined from the alloys listed in Table 17 into a composition-triangle (Figure 42) indicates that there is a stability maximum of the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ phase in the range marked in the figure. The dark-colored area in Figure 42 shows a tentative region where the disordering temperature lies above 1240°C . The maximum is located within a composition range of 30–35 at.% Al, 15–25 at.% Nb, and 45–55 at.% Ti. This is different from other TiAl-based systems with (βTi) -stabilizing ternary elements such as the Ti–Al–Mo system. In this case, literature results from Böhm et al. [134], Hamajima et al. [135], and Das et al. [31] also indicate the existence of such a stability maximum, which however is suggested to lie at a stoichiometric composition Ti_2AlMo . Assuming an ideal Ti content of 50 at.% for the present case of the Ti–Al–Nb system, the composition range of the maximum stability temperature can be roughly described by the formula $\text{Ti}_2\text{Al}_{1+x}\text{Nb}_{1-x}$ ($0 < x \leq 0.4$). To investigate the site occupancy in the ordered $B2$ phase, Banerjee et al. [136] investigated an alloy with the composition Ti-25.6Al-10.1Nb. Their experimental findings together with the results from Leonard et al. [137], who found a strong site preference of Ti and Al atoms in a Ti-25Al-25Nb alloy, lead to the conclusion that in the ideally ordered case the atom types on the two independent lattice sites $1a$ and $1b$ of the $B2$ structure tend to be strictly separated with the Ti atoms occupying preferentially the $1a$ site and Al + Nb atoms sharing the $1b$ site. This is

supported by density functional theory (DFT) calculations of Holec et al. [89] for $(\beta\text{Ti})_0$ indicating that Nb prefers to substitute Al. Therefore, one might indeed expect the most stable composition on the section $\text{Ti}_2\text{Al}_{1+x}\text{Nb}_{1-x}$.

Figure 42 Disordering temperatures and phase compositions of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ plotted in a partial Gibbs-triangle with tentative areas of disordering temperatures above 1240 °C (dark-colored area) and 1200 °C (light-colored area). Included are also the A2/B2-disordering lines from the isothermal sections from 900 (Figure 19, green), 1000 (Figure 34, blue), and 1100 °C (Figure 35, brown).

The present experimental observations are also supported by Das et al. [31], who investigated two alloys (Ti-25Al-25Nb and Ti-33Al-17Nb) with DTA finding disordering temperatures of 1141 °C and ~1242 °C, respectively. The compositions of these alloys are close to alloys TAN5 (1169 °C) and TAN8 (1248 °C). The differences in disordering temperatures can be explained by the fact that Das et al. [31] only gave the intended composition of the alloys and did not measure the actual composition. From TEM investigations of alloys with nominal compositions of Ti-25Al-25Nb and Ti-12.5Al-37.5Nb, Bendersky et al. [81] concluded that the alloy with 25 at.% Nb has the stronger tendency to form B2-ordered $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$. This translates into a decrease of disordering temperature with increasing the Nb content above 25 at.% along the section TiAl-TiNb. The same trend is observed in *ab initio* total energy calculations of Asta et al. [138] using the cluster variation method (CVM). However, as they do their calculations for a purely bcc-based system neglecting the stability of the hexagonal (αTi) and Ti_3Al as well as the tetragonal TiAl phases, they obtain the highest order/disorder temperature for a hypothetical, binary bcc-TiAl. These trends are also present in the presented experimental

results. The A2/B2 transition line shifts to higher Al contents with increasing temperature (Figure 42) and consequently the order/disorder temperatures first increase with Nb content (1204 °C for alloy TAN15 with 12 at.% Nb, 1248 °C for alloy TAN8 with 17 at.% Nb) and then decrease again (1169 °C for alloy TAN5 with 25 at.% Nb).

For a constant Al content of 25 at.%, i.e., along a section starting from Ti_3Al in the direction of Nb_3Al , the experimentally observed disordering temperatures for alloys TAN4 (Ti-25.2Al-13.9Nb, 1104 °C) and TAN5 (Ti-24.1Al-25.2Nb, 1169 °C) show an increase of the stability of the ordered phase by replacing Ti by Nb (Figure 42). The same observations were made by Kestner-Weykamp et al. [77] in alloys with up to 30 at.% Nb. Additionally, Muraleedharan et al. [78] found a disordering temperature of 1130 °C for a nominal composition of Ti-24Al-15Nb which is in line with the presented experimental results. Moreover, Asta et al. [138] found the same trend indicating a maximum of the disordering temperature along this section at 25 at.% Nb in their calculations for a purely bcc-based system.

The highest transition temperature which was measured in the present investigation was for alloy TAN8 (Ti-32.8Al-16.8Nb, 1248 °C). Results of Suryanarayana et al. [139], who found B2-ordered ($\beta Ti,Nb$) at 1200 °C for two alloys with nearby composition (Ti-36Al-13Nb and Ti-33Al-17Nb), confirm a high disordering temperature in this composition range. From Figure 42 it is clear that the maximum disordering temperature should lie within the dark-colored composition area of 30–35 at.% Al, 15–25 at.% Nb, and 45–55 at.% Ti. This is also observed in the CALPHAD modelling of Cupid et al. [115] and Witusiewicz et al. [84], where calculations indicate that the ($\beta Ti,Nb$)_o phase is stable in the mentioned composition range even up to 1300 °C and 1400 °C, respectively. The extremely high maximum temperature obtained in the modelling work of Witusiewicz et al. [84] is based on some indirect observations from Bendersky et al. [20]. From the absence of anti-phase boundaries (APBs) in the ($\beta Ti,Nb$)_o phase of an alloy cooled from 1400 °C, they concluded that the sample must have been B2-ordered at 1400 °C (as rapid cooling from a disordered to an ordered state usually leads to formation of APBs) [20]. However, since cooling of the samples was performed in the furnace with an estimated cooling rate of 400 °C/min [20], there is the possibility that APBs indeed have formed but have been annealed out already during further cooling, i.e., it is well possible that ($\beta Ti,Nb$) was not ordered at 1400 °C. There is not any direct measurement of such high transition temperatures mentioned in the literature. The present results and all other experimental work reported in the literature, where the transition temperature was directly measured, clearly suggest that the maximum temperature is much lower and will be in the range of 1250 °C.

4.3.2 Heating rate dependent transformations

For transformations that show a nonlinear heating rate dependence, it is not trivial to determine the equilibrium transition temperatures at 0 °C/min heating rate. Therefore, a model for sluggish heating rate dependent phase transformations was developed by Zhu et al. [131, 132]. This model can be applied to determine equilibrium transformation temperatures from continuous heating or cooling DTA experiments for diffusion-controlled solid-solid transformations showing a non-linear heat rate dependence, which is the case here. Assuming that the formation of the new phase is initiated by heterogeneous nucleation at the grain boundaries, they derived a simplified expression for the incubation time of nucleation. For the non-isothermal situation of constant heating/cooling DTA experiments, the ‘concept of additivity’ described by Christian [140] is applied following a similar approach as is used for the calculation of continuous-cooling-transformation diagrams from time-temperature-transformation diagrams. The resulting integral can be solved by some approximations such as not too high heating/cooling rates (maximum in the range 10–20 °C/min) and not too high differences between equilibrium and measured transition temperatures. The final equation as derived by Zhu et al. [132] is of the form $T_m = T_{equ.} + cS^{1/3}$, where T_m is the measured transition temperature, $T_{equ.}$ is the equilibrium transition temperature, c is a temperature-independent constant, and S is the heating rate. Therefore, the equilibrium transition temperatures can be obtained by plotting the measured transition temperatures as a function of $S^{1/3}$ and extrapolating these values to a rate of 0 °C/min. This simple approach is used in the present study to determine the equilibrium transition temperatures for all heating rate dependent phase transitions, since they all show the same characteristics.

4.3.2.1 The Ti_3Al to (αTi) transformation

In Ti–Al alloys with 38.5–46.5 at.% Al, the transformation from Ti_3Al to (αTi) takes place by an invariant (eutectoid) reaction at 1120°C involving a change in composition, i.e., requiring long-range diffusional processes. This change is very small in the binary Ti–Al system (about 0.5 at.% Al [28, 29]) and both Ti_3Al and (αTi) possess a hexagonal crystal lattice. Therefore, even though some long-range diffusional processes are involved, this solid-solid transformation can be expected to proceed comparably easily and its onset temperature in heating experiments should only reveal a weak heating rate dependence as is confirmed here

for the binary alloy TA1 (Table 18). This decomposition reaction of Ti_3Al also occurs in the ternary system. Three of the present alloys, TAN9 (Ti-39.8Al-9.4Nb), TAN13 (Ti-44.3Al-4.9Nb), and TAN14 (Ti-45.8Al-5.2Nb) show the Ti_3Al to (αTi) transformation. From the DTA results in Table 18 it can be seen that indeed there seems to be a weak trend to increased transformation temperatures with higher heating rates in both the binary and ternary alloys. This dependence on the heating rate is nonlinear, as also is observed for the transition ω_o to ($\beta Ti, Nb$) $_o$ and O to ($\beta Ti, Nb$) $_o$ (see below in Section 4.3.2.2 and 4.3.2.3, respectively). Therefore, the equilibrium phase transition temperatures (last row of Table 18) were determined with the above described model of Zhu and Devletian.

Table 18 Transformation temperatures for the Ti_3Al to (αTi) transformation in different alloys as determined from DTA heating curves. The extrapolated equilibrium transformation temperatures (corresponding to 0 °C/min heating rate) are given in the last row.

Heating Rate (°C/min)	Ti_3Al to (αTi) transformation temperature (°C)			
	TA1 (Ti-42.9Al)	TAN9 (Ti-39.8Al-9.4Nb)	TAN13 (Ti-44.3Al-4.9Nb)	TAN14 (Ti-45.8Al-5.2Nb)
10	1140	1174	1147	1163
5	1139	1173	1148	1163
2	1139	1173	1145	1161
1	1138	1172	a	a
0	1137 ± 1	1171 ± 1	1143 ± 1	1159 ± 1

^a measured signal was too small to allow an exact determination of the value of the onset

Similar as in case of the order/disorder transition of ($\beta Ti, Nb$) $_o$, the effect of preceding heat treatments at different temperatures on the transition temperatures was tested. Again, the results show that the onset temperature of the Ti_3Al decomposition remains unaffected, see Figure 43.

Figure 43 DTA heat flow curves (heating rate: 10 °C/min) of alloy TAN13 (Ti-44.3Al-4.9Nb) showing the transformation Ti_3Al to (αTi) for three differently heat-treated samples (preceding heat treatment at 700, 800, or 900 °C).

4.3.2.2.1 Influence of Nb on the Ti_3Al to (αTi) transformation temperature

In the binary phase diagram assessed by Schuster et al. [28, 29], a value of 1120 ± 10 °C was chosen for the eutectoid reaction based on the DTA measurements of Jones et al. [141], who determined the transformation for three different binary Ti-Al alloys (Ti-40Al/Ti-42Al/Ti-45Al). However, the present results for alloy TA1 suggest a slightly higher transformation temperature of 1137°C. The reported literature values for the transformation temperature from Ti_3Al to (αTi) vary significantly. For an alloy Ti-45Al, Appel et al. [142] found a transformation temperature of ~1130 °C, whereas Chladil et al. [86] determined 1122 °C by DTA. Kononikhina et al. [127] determined with *in situ* neutron diffraction that the transformation from Ti_3Al to (αTi) is completed between 1150 and 1160 °C. Witusiewicz et al. [84] reported the transformation temperature to be 1108 °C in an alloy with 44 at.% Al. Recently, Xu et al. [82] measured the transformation temperature in Ti-42.5Al (onset: 1150 °C) and Ti-44Al (onset: 1146 °C) for a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The reason for the significant scattering of the reported values is not obvious. As found in the present investigations, the effect of the heating rate on the measured value is comparably weak (the difference between the value obtained with a heating rate of 10 °C/min and the equilibrium transformation temperature is only 3 °C for the binary alloy TA1 (Ti-42.9Al), see Table 18). It is reported in the literature that interstitial elements such as O and C can significantly affect the eutectoid transformation temperature of Ti_3Al to (αTi) [23, 123]. The O content of alloy TA1 is only 110 wt. ppm. Therefore, the transformation temperature value found here is considered to be representative.

A similar, weak heating rate dependence as for the binary alloy is also observed for the ternary alloys TAN11, TAN13, and TAN14 (Table 18), which experience the same first-order transformation (some typical DTA curves are shown in Figure 43) from the ordered Ti_3Al phase to disordered (αTi). Similar to the binary alloy, both ternary alloys TAN13 and TAN14 are two-phase $Ti_3Al + TiAl$ (Figure 33a,b) and transform to (αTi) + $TiAl$ (Figure 33c) on heating. The same transformation occurs in alloy TAN11, which in addition contains the ordered $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ phase (Figure 29b). As the heating rate dependence in all cases is weak and similar to that of the binary alloy, it can be assumed that the change in composition between the low-temperature Ti_3Al and high-temperature (αTi) phase again is small. This indeed is confirmed by EPMA analysis of the phase compositions showing a difference of the Al content of about 2 at.% between the Ti_3Al phase (measured at 1100 °C, Table 12) and (αTi) (measured at 1200 °C, Table 13) while the Nb content remains about constant.

From the transformation temperatures of the alloys listed in Table 18, it is also observed that the transformation temperature increases with increasing Nb content indicating that Nb additions stabilize Ti_3Al to higher temperatures. This observation is supported by results of Chladil et al. [86], who observed a similar increase in transformation temperature in alloys with 45 at.% Al and 5, 7.5, and 10 at.% Nb. The same trend is also observed when comparing experiments from different authors who investigated alloys with the same Al content but different amounts of Nb [84, 86, 118, 123-126]. All these observations classify this reaction as first-order type reaction.

4.3.2.2 The ω_o to $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ transformation

A significantly stronger heating rate dependence is observed for the transformation from ω_o to $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$. As an example, the transformation peak measured with different heating rates for alloy TAN 11 (Ti-39.8Al-9.4Nb) is presented in Figure 44a showing a continuous but non-linear increase of the onset temperature with increasing heating rate Figure 44b. The onset temperature marks the temperature at which $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ begins to form. At the peak maximum ω_o has completely transformed. The fact that an onset temperature can be determined and that the transformation is heating rate dependent classifies this reaction as first-order type. A possible explanation for the stronger heating rate dependence (compared to the Ti_3Al to (αTi) transformation) could be the fact that the crystal lattice needs to change from a hexagonal (ω_o

phase) to a cubic ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)_o structure (whereas both Ti_3Al and (αTi) possess a hexagonal lattice). Apart from the crystallographic rearrangements, a change in composition and phase fraction as described in Section 4.1.3.2.6 has to occur during the transformation. These two factors might be responsible for the increased heating rate dependence compared to the transformation Ti_3Al to (αTi).

Figure 44 a) DTA heating curves of alloy Ti-39.8Al-9.4Nb (TAN11) obtained with different heating rates; b) non-linear heating rate dependence of the transformation temperatures.

Figure 45 Plot of the experimentally determined transformation temperatures for the transformation ω_o to ($\beta\text{Ti,Nb}$)_o as a function of $(\text{heating rate})^{1/3}$ (approach of Zhu et al. [131, 132]). From the linear extrapolations to 0 °C/min heating rate, the equilibrium transformation temperatures for alloys TAN7, TAN8, TAN9, TAN11, TAN12, and TAN15 were determined.

Applying the above described model of Zhu et al. [131, 132] results in a plot as shown in Figure 45. The data for alloys TAN7 and TAN8 shows some scatter. This can be explained

by the complex phase equilibria around 900 °C as explained in Section 4.1.3.2 and illustrated in Figure 21b. Multiple reactions occur in quick succession and the peaks are overlapping resulting in some uncertainty on the determination of the onset point. Nevertheless, the data can now easily be fitted by a linear function which allows the equilibrium transition temperature to be determined by extrapolating to a heating rate of 0 °C/min. The same is true for all other alloys showing this transition. The resulting equilibrium transition temperatures are listed in Table 19.

Table 19 Equilibrium phase transformation temperatures for the phase transformation ω_o to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ determined by applying the approach of Zhu et al. [131, 132]

Alloy	Phase composition (at.%)			ω_o to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ (°C)
	Ti	Al	Nb	
TAN7	55.6	32.7	11.6	919 ± 2
TAN8	50.4	32.8	16.8	897 ± 3
TAN9	53.9	36.4	9.7	908 ± 1
TAN10	-	-	-	790 ± 5
TAN11	50.8	39.8	9.4	906 ± 1
TAN12	40.4	39.6	20.0	923 ± 1
TAN15	43.8	44.5	11.7	913 ± 1

Figure 46 shows the chemical compositions of the ω_o phases (measured with EPMA) together with the respective equilibrium transformation temperatures plotted into a partial Gibbs-triangle. The indicated phase fields of the ω_o phase is for a temperature of 900 °C (Figure 19) and serves as a guide for the eye. There are two groups of high transition temperatures observed at the Nb-rich and -poor end of the composition range. The temperatures in between are lower (TAN8 and TAN10). This results from the splitting of the ω_o phase field in a temperature range of 850 ± 45 °C (Figure 21a)

Figure 46 Transformation temperature and composition of ω_0 (stars) and O phase (circles) plotted in a partial Gibbs-triangle with homogeneity range of ω_0 (orange colored area) and O phase (grey colored area) at 900 °C.

4.3.2.3 The O phase to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ transformation

A clear dependence on the heating rate is also evident for the transformation of the O phase to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$, which was observed in three ternary alloys. The measured transformation temperatures for the alloys TAN4 (Ti-25.2Al-13.9Nb), TAN5 (Ti-24.1Al-25.2Nb), and TAN6 (Ti-30.7Al-23.9Nb) are listed in Table 12. Once more the equilibrium transformation temperatures were determined using the approach of Zhu et al. [131, 132], see last row in Table 20.

Similar as for the transformation ω_0 to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$, there is also a change of the crystal structure required for the transformation of the orthorhombic O phase to cubic $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$, which was theoretically described by Banerjee et al. [21]. As is the case for the transformation of the ω_0 phase, there is also a change in phase composition and phase fraction involved. As can be seen from Table 20, the difference in the measured transformation temperatures for heating rates of 10 °C/min and 1 °C/min is larger than 10 °C resulting in an equilibrium transformation temperature well below the measured values (last row of Table 20). Obviously, the transformation of the O phase has the strongest heating rate dependence of the three described

transformations (Figure 47). Alloys Ti-25.2Al-13.9Nb (TAN4) and Ti-24.1Al-25.2Nb (TAN5) transform in the same temperature range and it appears that the influence of the Nb content is not very strong. When the Al content is increased by 5 at.% keeping the Nb content similar to that of TAN11, the transformation temperature increases to 963 °C in alloy Ti-30.7Al-23.9Nb (TAN6) (see also Figure 46). This behaviour is surprising as one might have expected to find the highest stability of the O phase at the stoichiometric composition (Ti_2AlNb , i.e., Ti-25Al-25Nb). The here determined value of 963 °C must lie very close to the peritectoid dissolution temperature of the O phase, because at 1000 °C (Figure 34) the O phase is no longer observed as an equilibrium phase. In contrast to this expectation, alloy TAN5 with its O phase composition (Ti-25.3Al-24.3Nb) very near to this stoichiometric composition possesses the lowest of the measured transformation temperatures.

Table 20 Transformation temperatures for the O to $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ transformations in different alloys upon heating as determined by DTA. The extrapolated equilibrium transformation temperatures are given in the last row.

Heating rate (°C/min)	O to $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ transformation temperature (°C)		
	TAN4 (Ti-25.2Al-13.9Nb)	TAN5 (Ti-24.1Al-25.2Nb)	TAN6 (Ti-30.7Al-23.9Nb)
10	964	979	985
5	960	973	981
2	956	962 ^a	976
1	951	955 ^a	973
0	941 ± 1	935 ± 2	963 ± 1

^a increase in uncertainty to ± 2 °C due to difficulties in onset determination resulting from weak signal at low heating rates.

Figure 47 Comparison of the heating rate dependence of the transformations Ti_3Al to (αTi) , O to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$, and ω_0 to $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_0$ (for each type of transformation one specific example was chosen, the presented data belong to alloys TAl (squares), and TAN6 (triangles), and TAN9 (circles), respectively).

In Figure 47 characteristic examples for the three different heating rate dependent transformations are shown. As described above, the transformation from Ti_3Al to (αTi) only requires a slight compositional change and no rearrangement of the crystal structure. Therefore, this transformation can proceed relatively easy. As soon as the transformations become more complex involving changes of the crystal structure as well as significant changes of the phase fractions and phase compositions, it can be well understood that the heating rate dependence becomes stronger.

As the above described systematic DTA investigations of the phase transitions in the Ti–Al–Nb system have shown, heating rate and alloy composition play an important role with regard to the measured transformation temperature. Furthermore, it was mentioned above (Section 4.3.2.2.1) and in literature that elements such as O can significantly influence the transformation temperature in the binary Ti–Al system [23]. Therefore, the influence of oxygen on phase equilibria in ternary alloys was investigated and the results are presented in the next chapter.

4.4 Effect of oxygen on phase equilibria⁴

As mentioned in Section 4.2.3.2.2, there are several differing compositions reported for the three-phase equilibrium (α Ti) + (β Ti,Nb) + TiAl at 1300 °C [100, 106, 112]. A possible explanation for these differences could be different amounts of oxygen in the alloys. From the literature it is well known that the solubility of impurities in the hexagonal phases (α Ti) and Ti₃Al is very high compared to the tetragonal TiAl phase [143-145]. This solubility by far exceeds the impurity levels even for industrial alloys [42] and, therefore, no oxides, carbides or nitrides form in the bulk alloys. This means that a visual inspection of the microstructure gives no indication of the presence and amount of oxygen.

The effect of oxygen on the binary Ti–Al system is well known [23]. Similar observations are made in ternary TiAl-based systems where equilibrium phase compositions of three-phase equilibria involving the (α Ti) or Ti₃Al phase shift to higher amounts of the third element as a result of increased impurity (O, N, C) content in the alloy [24, 26, 27]. In the following, own experimental results for phase equilibria at 1300 °C are compared with available data from the literature. The reason for choosing this temperature is threefold: i) 1300 °C is the upper limit of heat treatment temperatures in the present study and, since oxygen uptake should increase with increasing temperature, the strongest effect on phase equilibria should be observed at this temperature; ii) According to existing literature and the here presented results, the phase relations at 1300 °C are simpler than at lower temperatures since all solid-state reactions are finished; iii) Finally, some literature about experimental work on phase equilibria at this temperature is available where information about impurity contents of the respective alloys is included [100, 106, 112]. After presenting the results and comparing them with literature, an attempt to explain the observed behaviour is discussed.

⁴ This chapter is based on the following publication: [25] B. Distl, G. Dehm, and F. Stein, Effect of Oxygen on High-temperature Phase Equilibria in Ternary Ti-Al-Nb Alloys, *Zeitschrift für anorganische und allgemeine Chemie*, 2020, **646**(14), p 1151-1156. <https://doi.org/10.1002/zaac.202000098>

4.4.1 Results and comparison of the Nb solubility in (α Ti) with the literature

Of the alloys heat-treated at 1300 °C (Table 14), a series of samples with compositions in the range of the (α Ti) phase was selected. Alloys TAN13 and TAN14 show a lamellar two-phase microstructure consisting of (α Ti) and TiAl (Figure 33c), alloy TAN15 contains the three phases (α Ti) + (β Ti,Nb) + TiAl (Figure 33d), and Alloys TAN8, TAN9 and TAN11 (Figure 29c) are single-phase (β Ti,Nb). The compositional data of the investigated alloys are listed in Table 14. The oxygen contents were analysed after alloy synthesis in the as-cast state and after the heat treatment at 1300 °C. As described in Section 3.1, special attention was paid in the present study to synthesize high-purity alloys with low impurity contents. As Table 21 shows, the oxygen contents were at a very low level (≤ 200 wt.ppm with one exception), and the increase in oxygen content during heat treatment was also kept very low. Therefore, the effect of oxygen on the phase equilibria is considered not to be strong for these alloys.

Table 21 Comparison of oxygen contents measured with inert gas fusion of alloys TAN8, 9, 11, and 13-15 in as-cast and heat-treated (1300 °C for 20 h) samples (n.d.: not determined).

Sample No.	Oxygen content (wt. ppm)	
	As-cast	Heat treated
TAN8	160	280
TAN9	190	n.d.
TAN11	290	300
TAN13	150	220
TAN14	140	150
TAN15	200	n.d.

The literature studies at 1300 °C [100, 106, 112], mainly focus on the three-phase equilibrium (α Ti) + (β Ti,Nb) + TiAl in alloys with an Al content of 40-50 at.%. The oxygen contents of the representative alloys used in the literature Kainuma et al. [106] ~240 wt. ppm O, Nakamura et al. [112] ~350 wt. ppm O, Xu et al. [100] ~400 wt. ppm O are higher than in the samples used in the present investigations. In Figure 48, the tie-triangle (α Ti) + (β Ti,Nb) + TiAl obtained by the different studies is plotted.

Figure 48 Partial isothermal section of Ti–Al–Nb at 1300 °C showing the shift of the position of the tie-triangle (α Ti) + (β Ti,Nb) + as obtained by Xu et al. [100], Nakamura et al. [112], Kainuma et al. [106], and the present investigations. The oxygen contents of the respective alloys is also given (as-cast condition).

As can be seen in Figure 48, the phase compositions vary significantly between the different studies. The samples from the literature studies were prepared in a similar way as described in Section 3.3.1, either by arc- or plasma-arc-melting. Due to the use of different raw materials, the oxygen content in the as-cast samples varies between ~200-400 wt. ppm. In addition, Xu et al. [100] homogenized their samples in fused silica ampules backfilled with Ti-gettered argon for 5 h at 1400°C followed by furnace cooling to 1300°C and holding there for 20-110 h. After heat treatment, they removed 1 mm from the sample surface to minimize the influence of the reaction layer between sample and fused silica formed during the heat treatment. However, fused silica is known to be no longer gas-tight at such temperatures and can start to soften and collapse already above 1100°C [52, 146]. Therefore, it is very doubtful how effective the removal of the surface layer is since the here presented investigations on cylindrical samples (\varnothing 15x10 mm³) reveal that alloys heat-treated at 1100°C for 200 h already contain significantly higher amounts of oxygen (~500 wt. ppm) than alloys after 400 h at 1000°C (~220 wt. ppm). The chemical analyses were carried out with parts taken from near the center of the cylindrical sample. This indicates that oxygen diffuses through the entire cross-section of the sample at these temperatures. Since the samples of Xu et al. [100] with dimensions of 8x8x9 mm³ are smaller in size and the heat treatment temperature is 1300 °C, it can be assumed that the oxygen content in the heat-treated sample is significantly higher as in the as-cast state.

To minimize the effects of impurity uptake, Kainuma et al. [106] wrapped their samples in Mo foil. Moreover, their heat treatment time of 24 h is short compared to the 110 h of Xu et al. [100]. In the study of Nakamura et al. [112], the heat treatment was performed for 48 h at 1300 °C with samples encapsulated in fused silica ampules. Unfortunately, none of the authors measured the impurity contents after heat treatment. Therefore, the oxygen content of the as-cast alloys is used here for comparison of the results. From the experimental results (Figure 48), it is evident that as-cast samples with low impurity contents (Kainuma et al. [106] and present work) result in phase compositions with the lowest Nb contents after heat treatment. The results from Nakamura et al. [112] and Xu et al. [100] are shifted to higher Nb contents. The increase of Nb solubility in the (α Ti)-phase with increasing oxygen content raises to some questions. Do phases of the displayed tie-triangle differ with respect to the effect of oxygen on Nb solubility? Is only the (α Ti)-phase affected by oxygen? How can the relation between oxygen content and Nb solubility be explained?

4.4.2 Discussion: Octahedral voids

From his atom probe tomography (APT) measurements, Menand et al. [144] concluded that oxygen in a TiAl + Ti₃Al two-phase microstructure almost exclusively occupies octahedral voids in Ti₃Al. In addition, these investigations show that oxygen solubility in TiAl varies slightly with Ti concentration but does not exceed ≈ 500 at. ppm [144], which is in agreement with the ternary Ti–Al–O phase diagram [145]. There are two types of unoccupied octahedral voids in the Ti₃Al structure: i) formed by 4 Ti atoms and 2 Al atoms (Ti₄Al₂); ii) formed by 6 Ti atoms (Ti₆). Neutron diffraction measurements from Jones et al. [147] indicate that oxygen atoms in Ti₃Al only occupy Ti₆ octahedral voids, what was also indicated by APT-measurements of Menand et al. [144]. Since this kind of octahedral void does not exist in TiAl [144], this could be an explanation for the low solubility of oxygen since the size of the octahedral voids in both phases is similar [144]. A possible explanation for preferred occupation of Ti₆ octahedral voids by oxygen in Ti₃Al is the “chemical environment” of these voids. DFT calculations of Bakulin et al. [148] show that the absorption energy of oxygen is substantially decreased (by 1.47 eV) if aluminium is present in nearest neighbour locations of the oxygen, what is the case in Ti₄Al₂ octahedral voids. Since higher absorption energy means stronger bonds between oxygen and matrix atom, this indicates that Ti₆ octahedral voids are energetically more favourable [148].

These results are in agreement with Wei et al. [149] who calculated the formation energy of octahedral and tetrahedral voids in TiAl and Ti₃Al occupied by oxygen. The negative values of the formation energy indicate that occupied voids are more stable than unoccupied ones. Also, Ti₆ octahedral voids in Ti₃Al exhibit the lowest formation energy, indicating that oxygen energetically favours the occupation of this type of voids [149], which is in agreement with experimental findings of Menand et al. [144] and Jones et al. [147]. From electronic structure calculations using the so-called “empirical electron theory of solids and molecules” method, Zhi et al. [150] concluded that impurities such as oxygen change hybridization states of Ti leading to a considerably anisotropic electronic structure.

This is in agreement with Bakulin et al. [148], who explained the decrease in absorption energy if aluminium is present with a decrease in charge transfer from Ti atoms to oxygen while charge transfer between Al atoms and oxygen is high. This results in a minimal charge transfer in Ti₆ octahedral voids which is caused by stronger localization of s-, d-states of Ti atoms compared to more delocalized s-, p-states of Al [148]. This leads to an increase of covalent electrons in the bond between impurity element and metal atom and a decrease in bond strength between Ti and Al atoms [150]. All these facts point to the conclusion that oxygen prefers the more stable Ti₆ octahedral voids and therefore solubility of oxygen is higher in phases such as Ti₃Al that provide this kind of voids.

In addition to the change in electronic structure, the lattice parameter along the [11-20]- and [0001]-axis of the elementary cell increases linearly with oxygen content. Along the [11-20]-axis, this change is one order of magnitude smaller than along the [0001]-axis as Jones et al. [147] concluded from their neutron diffraction experiments on different single-phase Ti₃Al alloys with different oxygen contents and constant Ti/Al ratio. The same behaviour has been observed by Dechamps et al. [151] in (α Ti) and the degree of lattice expansions in both phases are in agreement [147]. Jones et al. [147] explain the more pronounced increase along the [0001]-axis of the crystal structure by the fact that in Ti₃Al the octahedra share one face with each other and form rows along the [0001]-direction [147]. The increase of lattice parameters results in bond lengthening of Ti-Al and Ti-Ti bonds along the [0001]-axis as a function of the oxygen content leading to a distortion of octahedral voids [147]. This leads to the question how does this distortion of the crystal structure/octahedral voids influence the solubility of Nb in (α Ti) at 1300°C?

From Figure 48 one can see that with increasing oxygen content in the as-cast alloys, the position of the (α Ti) + (β Ti,Nb) + TiAl tie-triangle shifts approximately parallel to the Ti-Nb axis to higher Nb contents. This means that the solubility of Nb in (α Ti) increases and a higher fraction of Ti atoms can be replaced by Nb atoms due to the presence of oxygen. This agrees with DFT calculations of Holec et al. [89], who showed that Nb preferentially occupies the Ti site in Ti₃Al. Hence, some Ti₆ octahedral voids must become Ti_{6-x}Nb_x voids, which appears to be a favourable configuration of these voids.

The addition of a third element into the crystal structure has two effects: i) distortion in the crystal structure/voids, ii) the electronic structure changes. The calculations of Holec et al. [89] show that the main contribution of a third element is attributed to the change in electronic structure, while the different size of the atom has only a minor effect. This means that oxygen incorporated in Ti₆ octahedral voids most likely enhances Nb uptake in the (α Ti) phase. However, this effect is still far from completely understood. Some open questions are: i) How many Ti atoms are replaced by Nb atoms in the Ti₆ octahedra, ii) Since there are no superlattice reflections in XRD measurements it has to be assumed that the Nb atoms occupy the Ti sites randomly. This might lead to a variety of different Ti_{6-x}Nb_x octahedral voids, and iii) How do Nb atoms change the electronic structure in octahedral voids?

Regardless of these open questions, it is apparent that the impurity levels in our alloys are low and thus the influence on phase equilibria involving the oxygen-affine (α Ti) and Ti₃Al phase is very small. With the above discussed phase equilibria (Section 4.1 and 4.2), the determined phase transition temperatures (Section 4.3), and the discussed literature, a reaction scheme for the Ti–Al–Nb system can be determined, which is presented in the following section.

4.5 Reaction scheme

A reaction scheme, sometimes called “Scheil-Schema” after his inventor, is a graphical representation of all invariant reactions in a material system. This includes transformation type and temperature, as well as the phases involved in the transformation. In Figure 49, the reaction scheme of the Ti–Al–Nb system according to the form proposed by Lukas et al. [152] and usually adopted in the literature is shown. Since in the current work no reactions with the liquid phase (L) were studied, these reactions are based on the scheme presented by Witusiewicz et al. [84]. Reactions and reaction temperatures which take place in the temperature range from 700 to 1300 °C are based on the experimental results discussed in Sections 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3. The reaction temperatures in the binary systems are taken from the recent assessments of these systems [28, 29, 32, 63]. For consistency, the phase designation “(βTi,Nb)” is also used in the binary systems. The two phases TiAl₃ and NbAl₃ have the same crystal structure (Tables 1 and 5) and share a common phase field that connects both binary systems along a constant Al content of 75 at.%. Therefore, they are considered as equivalent in the reaction scheme (TiAl₃ ≅ NbAl₃).

Since the binary phase Ti_{2+x}Al_{5-x} is not considered an equilibrium phase by Schuster and Palm [28, 29], the transition reaction (L + TiAl ⇌ TiAl₃ + Ti_{2+x}Al_{5-x}) shown in the reaction scheme of Witusiewicz et al. [84] is not necessary and, therefore, excluded here. Moreover, the B2-order of (βTi,Nb) in the reaction scheme of Witusiewicz et al. [84] starts in the binary Ti–Al system. Since there is no experimental evidence for this [29], it is assumed here that the order begins in the ternary composition space in a composition range discussed in Section 4.3.1.1. As a consequence, three eutectoid reactions ec₁ to ec₃ are necessary at the temperatures where the ordered phase field contacts with a phase boundary of a two-phase field. The temperatures of these reactions are estimated based on the disordering temperatures listed in Table 17 and the isothermal sections and in Figures 17-19 and 34-37.

As it is apparent from the above presented results the Ti–Al–Nb is a very complex system, which is related to the complex phase equilibria and kinetics below 1000 °C as a result of the presence of two ternary intermetallic phases. Additionally, there are various factors, that can have influences on the phase equilibria. However, the phase equilibria in the Ti–Al–Mo system (Section 5) should be less complicated because there is only one, albeit completely different, ternary intermetallic phase reported. The experimental results in this system will be discussed in the next section.

Figure 49 Reaction schematic of the Ti–Al–Nb system from Liquid phase down to 600 °C. The reactions involving the liquid phase are based on the modelling work from Witusiewicz et al. [84], the reactions in the binary are taken from the respective literature [28, 29, 32], and all other reactions are based on the above discussed results.

5 Phase equilibria, microstructure, and solubility limits in Ti–Al–Mo alloys⁵

Interest in phase equilibria of the Ti–Al–Mo system dates back to the 1950s, when Ti was alloyed with Al and Mo to control and improve the properties and stability of the low- and high-temperature allotropes (α Ti) and (β Ti). During the 1980s, the potential of Ti–Al–Mo alloys as lightweight structural materials for aerospace and automotive applications was the main focus of research [153]. The (β Ti)-stabilizing effect of Mo is stronger than that of Nb [154], therefore it is an equally important alloying element in TiAl-based alloys [4, 5, 14]. Despite the large amount of literature available (summarized in Ref. [153]), there is still uncertainty about the phase equilibria with the ternary intermetallic σ phase (tetragonal, $tP30$, $P4_2/mnm$ [22]). This ternary intermetallic phase forms in a solid-solid phase transformation above 1100 °C and is stable down to room temperature. Similar to other Ti–Al–X systems, phase relations in the ternary system are very complex and can be difficult to study experimentally. Reasons for this are the temperature-dependent high solubility of ternary elements in (α Ti), (β Ti,Mo), and TiAl₃. For example, the (β Ti,Mo) solid solution dominates the system at high temperatures covering about 80% of the liquidus surface [155] and contracts in the Mo-rich corner at low temperatures. Additionally, phases originating from the binary boundary systems existing as isolated single-phase fields in the ternary system, mainly at temperatures above 1200 °C [153], and crystallographic similarities of several phases can lead to misidentified phase equilibria. Due to the addition of Mo, many additional phase equilibria with phases from the binary Al–Mo system [156] are observed, especially in the Al-rich region of the Ti–Al–Mo system. All additional phases are listed in Table 22 with their crystallographic information.

⁵ Section 5.1 and 5.4 are partially based on the critical assessment of the Ti–Al–Mo system in Ref.: [153] B. Distl, A. Walnsch, R.F.L. Mellor, L. Gomell, M. Noori, A. Gedsun, and F. Stein, *Al-Mo-Ti Ternary Phase Diagram Evaluation*, in *MSI Eureka*, Watson, A. (Ed.) by MSI, Materials Science International Services GmbH, Stuttgart, 2021, Doc-ID: 10.17143.3.2.

Table 22 Crystallographic information (crystal system, Pearson symbol, space group, and Strukturbericht designation) of the additional phases present in the Ti–Al–Mo system. These phases are observed in the microstructure, the isothermal sections, and reaction scheme as a result of the addition of Mo.

Phase designation	Crystal system	Pearson symbol	Space group	Strukturbericht designation	Reference
(Mo)	cubic	<i>cI2</i>	<i>Im-3m</i>	<i>A2</i>	[40]
(β Ti,Mo)		<i>cI2</i>	<i>Im-3m</i>	<i>A2</i>	[40]
(β Ti,Mo) _o	cubic	<i>cP2</i>	<i>Pm-3m</i>	<i>B2</i>	
MoAl		<i>cI2</i>	<i>Im-3m</i>	<i>A2</i>	[157]
Mo ₃ Al	cubic	<i>cP8</i>	<i>Pm-3n</i>	<i>A15</i>	[65]
Mo ₃₇ Al ₆₃	cubic	<i>cI2</i>	<i>Im-3m</i>	<i>A2</i>	[157]
Mo ₃ Al ₈	monoclinic	<i>mC22</i>	<i>C2/m</i>	-	[158]
MoAl ₃	monoclinic	<i>mC32</i>	<i>Cm</i>	-	[159]
MoAl ₄	monoclinic	<i>mC30</i>	<i>Cm</i>	-	[160]
Mo ₄ Al ₁₇	monoclinic	<i>mC84</i>	<i>C2</i>	-	[161]
Mo ₅ Al ₂₂	orthorhombic	<i>oF216</i>	<i>Fdd2</i>	-	[161]
MoAl ₅	hexagonal	<i>hP36</i>	<i>R-3c</i>	-	[162]
\sim Ti ₃ Mo ₃ Al ₄ , σ	Tetragonal	<i>tP30</i>	<i>P4₂/mnm</i>	<i>D8_b</i>	[22]

After discussing selected aspects of the available literature on the phase equilibria in the Ti-rich corner of the Ti–Al–Mo system (Section 5.1), the experimental investigations of this work are presented (Section 5.2). Based on these experimental results, partial isothermal sections of the Ti–Al–Mo system are determined and discussed (Section 5.3). These results are used to construct a revised reaction scheme (Section 5.4).

5.1 Literature review

Due to the vast amount of literature available, which is summarized and assessed in Ref. [153], only two specific aspects are discussed here in more detail. By adding Mo to TiAl-based alloys, the *B2*-ordered (β Ti,Mo)_o phase is stabilized. In alloys with compositions along the TiAl–TiMo section, Böhm and Löhberg [134] discovered *B2*-ordered (β Ti,Mo)_o after heat treatment at 1000 °C. Alloys with Al contents between 15 and 35 at.% along the TiAl–TiMo

section were found to be surprisingly brittle. Since no additional phase was observed in the microstructure, they performed XRD measurements, which revealed that the alloys have a $B2$ -ordered cubic structure. Böhm and Löhberg [134] also observed an intensity maximum of the $B2$ superstructure reflection between 20 and 25 at.% Al. This indicates a composition of maximum stability of Ti_2AlMo , which is different from that of the Ti–Al–Nb system (Section 4.3.1.1). The highest disordering temperature reported so far (1418 °C) was determined by DTA measurements in an alloy with this composition Ti_2AlMo [31]. *Ab initio* calculations by Alonso et al. [163, 164] indicate that for this composition, the $B2$ order of $(\beta Ti, Mo)_o$ should change to a Heusler phase type $L2_1$ order at very low-temperatures, which has not yet been verified experimentally.

A ternary intermetallic compound with a composition of approximately $Ti_3Mo_3Al_4$ was found by Hansen and Raman [22] in alloys containing 25 to 36 at.% Mo, 25 to 33 at.% Ti, and 42 to 48 at.% Al after a one-week heat treatment at 900 °C. Since the crystal structure of this phase is of the $\sigma CrFe$ polytype, it is usually designated as σ phase and forms in a peritectoid reaction at 1166°C in the $(\beta Ti, Mo)_o + Mo_3Al$ the two-phase field [155]. Its existence has since been confirmed by several studies [155, 165, 166]. In a recent study of the Ti–Al–Mo system based on investigations of five diffusion multiples and 29 bulk alloys, Huang et al. [166] determined several three-phase fields with the σ phase at different temperatures. Based on their results, they determined isothermal sections between 800 and 1200 °C including the $(\beta Ti, Mo)$ solid solution, which extends very far into the ternary composition range and has an unusual “thorn-shaped tip” as a result of phase equilibria with the σ phase at 1000 and 1100 °C (c.f. Figure 6a and Figure 8a in Ref. [166]). However, despite of these reported data, there is still great uncertainty about the phase equilibria including $(\beta Ti, Mo)$, $TiAl$, $TiAl_3$, and σ , especially at 1000 °C and below. Therefore, alloy TAM11 with a composition in the critical range between these four phases was synthesized to help to clarify the phase equilibria in this composition range. The results for this alloy and the other heat-treated alloys in the Ti–Al–Mo system are presented in the following section.

5.2 Results

The phase and alloy compositions obtained by EPMA measurements, of 12 ternary bulk alloys (Table 2 Ti–Al–Mo part) heat-treated between 800 and 1300 °C (Table 3) are summarized in Table 23 through Table 28 along with the phase fractions determined, from these measurements. Since the investigations of the alloys TAM5 to TAM10 at 900, 1000 and 1300 °C revealed that most of these alloys show the same type of $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo}) + \text{TiAl}$ microstructure, not all of these alloys were investigated at the remaining heat treatment temperatures. The compositions given in the following together with the alloy designations, are always those measured in the as-cast condition (Table 2 Ti–Al–Nb part). The actual overall compositions of the heat-treated samples are given in the respective Tables 23-28 and may slightly deviate from the as-cast values. Figure 50 shows the overall composition of the bulk alloys plotted in the ternary composition triangle.

Figure 50 As-cast alloy composition (Table 2) of the ternary bulk alloys (TAM1-TAM12, black stars) plotted in the ternary composition triangle.

Table 23 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–Mo alloys heat-treated at 800 °C for 1000 h. (n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)
			Al	Mo	
TAM1	Ti-13.8Al-2.3Mo	(α Ti)	14.6 ± 0.2	0.6 ± 0.3	74
		(β Ti,Mo)	10.8 ± 0.3	7.1 ± 0.8	26
TAM2	Ti-18.9Al-1.9Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	14.5 ± 1.5	5.5 ± 1.2	58
		Ti ₃ Al	20.7 ± 0.3	0.6 ± 0.1	42
TAM3	Ti-29.3Al-4.9Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	30.3 ± 0.4	9.4 ± 1.4	42
		Ti ₃ Al	28.3 ± 0.5	1.9 ± 0.8	58
TAM4	Ti-40.4Al-1.9Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	c	c	n.d.
		Ti ₃ Al	c	c	n.d.
		TiAl	c	c	n.d.
TAM6	Ti-44.7Al-2.2Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	37.1 ± 1.5	8.2 ± 1.0	22
		TiAl	46.9 ± 0.4	0.9 ± 0.3	78
TAM7	Ti-46.3Al-3.3Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	38.0 ± 1.8	11.1 ± 1.6	14
		TiAl	47.6 ± 0.5	1.9 ± 0.5	86
TAM10	Ti-44.3Al-9.6Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	39.4 ± 2.8	13.4 ± 2.0	53
		TiAl	49.9 ± 1.0	5.6 ± 0.8	47
TAM11	Ti-53.0Al-13.0Mo ^a	(β Ti,Mo) _o	b	b	n.d.
		TiAl ₃	b	b	n.d.
		σ	b	b	n.d.

^a Nominal composition

^b Equilibrium not reached, TiAl still present in the microstructure. Therefore, no phase compositions given, see Section 5.3.1

^c Phases are too fine-scaled to be measured by EPMA

Table 24 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–Mo alloys heat-treated at 900 °C for 650 h. (n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)
			Al	Mo	
TAM1	Ti-15.0Al-2.5Mo ^a	(α Ti)	15.4 ± 0.3	0.5 ± 0.1	n.d.
		(β Ti,Mo)	12.5 ± 0.2	4.5 ± 0.2	n.d.
TAM2	Ti-18.4Al-1.9Mo	(α Ti)	16.6 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.1	3
		(β Ti,Mo) _o	13.6 ± 0.3	4.9 ± 0.2	32
		Ti ₃ Al	20.8 ± 0.3	0.5 ± 0.1	65
TAM3	Ti-29.2Al-4.7Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	30.2 ± 0.4	8.6 ± 0.9	40
		Ti ₃ Al	28.6 ± 0.4	2.1 ± 0.8	60
TAM4	Ti-39.0Al-1.9Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	35.6 ± 1.2	5.2 ± 1.1	28
		Ti ₃ Al	35.6 ± 1.7	0.8 ± 0.3	38
		TiAl	45.7 ± 0.5	0.4 ± 0.1	34
TAM7	Ti-43.6Al-3.3Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	34.9 ± 0.9	10.8 ± 0.7	25
		TiAl	46.5 ± 0.6	0.8 ± 0.3	75
TAM8	Ti-44.3Al-4.7Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	36.8 ± 1.4	12.1 ± 1.0	32
		TiAl	48.0 ± 0.7	1.5 ± 0.5	68
TAM9	Ti-45.6Al-6.0Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	36.3 ± 0.5	14.7 ± 0.5	29
		TiAl	49.4 ± 0.5	2.7 ± 0.5	71
TAM10	Ti-45.2Al-9.0Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	36.7 ± 0.8	15.7 ± 0.6	41
		TiAl	50.9 ± 0.9	4.1 ± 0.5	59
TAM11	Ti-53.0Al-13Mo ^a	(β Ti,Mo) _o	b	b	n.d.
		TiAl ₃	b	b	n.d.
		σ	b	b	n.d.

^a Nominal composition

^b Equilibrium not reached, TiAl still present in the microstructure. Therefore, no phase compositions given, see Section 5.3.1

Table 25 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–Mo alloys heat-treated at 1000 °C for 400 h. (n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)
			Al	Mo	
TAM1	Ti-13.9Al-2.2Mo	(β Ti,Mo)	13.9 \pm 0.1	2.2 \pm 0.1	100
		(α Ti)	19.0 \pm 0.1	0.4 \pm 0.1	5
TAM2	Ti-18.8Al-1.9Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	17.2 \pm 0.1	2.7 \pm 0.1	65
		Ti ₃ Al	22.2 \pm 0.1	0.4 \pm 0.1	30
TAM3	Ti-29.8Al-4.8Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	30.0 \pm 0.1	6.3 \pm 0.1	72
		Ti ₃ Al	29.0 \pm 0.1	1.2 \pm 0.2	28
TAM4	Ti-39.8Al-2.0Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	35.8 \pm 0.4	5.1 \pm 0.4	30
		Ti ₃ Al	37.0 \pm 0.3	0.8 \pm 0.1	38
TAM5	Ti-44.4Al-1.3Mo	TiAl	46.9 \pm 0.3	0.5 \pm 0.1	32
		(β Ti,Mo) _o	34.7 \pm 0.3	7.2 \pm 0.2	10
TAM6	Ti-45.0Al-2.5Mo ^a	Ti ₃ Al	35.5 \pm 0.5	0.9 \pm 0.1	6
		TiAl	46.2 \pm 0.2	0.6 \pm 0.1	84
TAM7	Ti-44.5Al-3.6Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	34.7 \pm 0.6	8.8 \pm 0.4	16
		TiAl	46.6 \pm 0.4	0.8 \pm 0.2	84
TAM8	Ti-44.7Al-4.8Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	35.3 \pm 0.6	10.2 \pm 0.4	26
		TiAl	47.6 \pm 0.3	0.9 \pm 0.1	75
TAM9	Ti-44.7Al-6.9Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	35.9 \pm 0.7	12.4 \pm 0.8	30
		TiAl	48.5 \pm 0.2	1.4 \pm 0.2	70
TAM10	Ti-44.7Al-9.1Mo	(β Ti,Mo) _o	36.7 \pm 0.7	14.2 \pm 0.4	40
		TiAl	50.2 \pm 0.4	2.5 \pm 0.2	60
TAM11	Ti-53.0Al-13.0Mo ^a	(β Ti,Mo) _o	37.0 \pm 0.5	14.8 \pm 0.5	56
		TiAl	51.2 \pm 0.6	3.5 \pm 0.7	44
		(β Ti,Mo) _o	b	b	n.d.
		TiAl ₃	b	b	n.d.
		σ	b	b	n.d.

^a Nominal composition

^b Equilibrium not reached, TiAl still present in microstructure. Therefore, not phase compositions given, see Section 5.3.1

Table 26 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–Mo alloys heat-treated at 1100 °C for 200 h. (n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)
			Al	Mo	
TAM3	Ti-30.0Al-5Mo ^b	(βTi,Mo) _o	29.8 ± 0.2	4.8 ± 0.1	n.d.
		Ti ₃ Al	29.2 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.1	n.d.
TAM4	Ti-39.6Al-2.0Mo ^a	(βTi,Mo) _o	37.0 ± 0.3	3.3 ± 0.1	50
		Ti ₃ Al	39.2 ± 0.3	0.8 ± 0.1	30
		TiAl	46.8 ± 0.2	0.5 ± 0.1	20
TAM6	Ti-43.7Al-2.5Mo	(βTi,Mo) _o	36.4 ± 0.6	6.5 ± 0.2	32
		TiAl	47.2 ± 0.4	1.0 ± 0.1	68
TAM7	Ti-45.0Al-3.75Mo ^b	(βTi,Mo) _o	35.1 ± 0.4	11.2 ± 0.2	19
		TiAl	47.2 ± 0.4	1.7 ± 0.1	81
TAM11	Ti-56.7Al-10.6Mo	(βTi,Mo)	44.6 ± 1.0	23.0 ± 1.0	10
		TiAl	58.2 ± 1.0	9.4 ± 1.0	90

^a As-cast composition

^b Nominal composition

Table 27 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–Mo alloys heat-treated at 1200 °C for 30 h. (n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)
			Al	Mo	
TAM4	Ti-39.6Al-2.0Mo ^a	(αTi)	40.4 ± 0.3	1.1 ± 0.1	n.d.
		(βTi,Mo) _o	37.7 ± 0.3	2.8 ± 0.1	n.d.
TAM5	Ti-44.9Al-1.2Mo ^a	(αTi)	40.2 ± 0.3	1.3 ± 0.1	n.d.
		(βTi,Mo) _o	37.1 ± 0.3	3.4 ± 0.1	n.d.
		TiAl	46.1 ± 0.4	0.8 ± 0.1	n.d.
TAM6	Ti-45.0Al-2.5Mo ^b	(βTi,Mo) _o	37.6 ± 0.7	5.2 ± 0.2	24
		TiAl	47.3 ± 0.4	1.1 ± 0.1	76

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)
			Al	Mo	
TAM8	Ti-45.0Al-5Mo ^b	(β Ti,Mo) _o	38.3 ± 0.6	9.2 ± 0.3	37
		TiAl	48.8 ± 0.3	1.9 ± 0.1	63
TAM10	Ti-45.0Al-10.0Mo ^b	(β Ti,Mo) _o	39.5 ± 0.4	13.8 ± 0.2	56
		TiAl	51.2 ± 0.4	4.0 ± 0.2	44
TAM11	Ti-56.1Al-10.9Mo ^a	(β Ti,Mo) _o	46.9 ± 0.3	21.2 ± 0.3	8
		TiAl	56.9 ± 0.3	9.3 ± 0.2	92
TAM12	Ti-61.1Al-2.9Mo	TiAl	61.1 ± 0.3	2.9 ± 0.4	100

^a As-cast composition

^b Nominal composition

Table 28 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–Mo alloys heat-treated at 1300 °C for 20 h. (n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)
			Al	Mo	
TAM4	Ti-40.6Al-1.9Mo	(α Ti)	40.6 ± 0.2	1.9 ± 0.1	100
TAM5	Ti-44.9Al-1.2Mo ^a	(α Ti)	42.0 ± 0.7	1.2 ± 0.1	43
		TiAl	47.2 ± 0.8	1.0 ± 0.2	58
TAM6	Ti-45Al-2.5Mo ^b	(α Ti)	42.4 ± 0.6	2.4 ± 0.1	n.d.
		TiAl	47.2 ± 0.6	1.4 ± 0.1	n.d.
TAM7	Ti-44.6Al-3.7Mo ^a	(α Ti)	43.4 ± 0.7	3.0 ± 0.1	n.d.
		(β Ti,Mo)	38.4 ± 0.4	6.7 ± 0.4	n.d.
TAM8	Ti-45.0Al-5.0Mo ^b	TiAl	48.3 ± 0.5	1.7 ± 0.2	n.d.
		(β Ti,Mo)	37.7 ± 0.4	8.1 ± 0.3	32
TAM9	Ti-45.0Al-7.5Mo ^b	TiAl	47.9 ± 0.3	2.1 ± 0.1	68
		(β Ti,Mo)	38.3 ± 0.2	11.2 ± 0.3	44
		TiAl	49.5 ± 0.3	3.0 ± 0.1	56

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)
			Al	Mo	
			TAM10	Ti-45.0Al-10.0Mo ^b	
TAM11	Ti-54.1Al-12.9Mo	(β Ti,Mo) TiAl	46.3 \pm 0.4 57.5 \pm 0.1	21.6 \pm 0.5 8.6 \pm 0.4	19 81
TAM12	Ti-62.5Al-2.9Mo	TiAl	62.5 \pm 0.2	2.9 \pm 0.1	100

^a As-cast composition

^b Nominal composition

Alloy TAM1 (Ti-15Al-2.5Mo) was heat-treated at 800, 900, and 1000 °C. The samples quenched from 800 and 900 °C show a two-phase microstructure consisting of plate-like (α Ti) precipitates inside large (β Ti,Mo) grains. In addition, (α Ti) is also found at the grain boundaries (Figure 51a). At 1000 °C, the microstructure shows two different contrasts in the BSE image (Figure 51b). However, no differences in composition could be measured by EPMA. According to HEXRD measurements, the microstructure belongs to α'' martensite, which has formed from (β Ti,Mo) during quenching without changing the composition (see also Section 4.2.2). From these results it is concluded that this alloy must be single-phase (β Ti,Mo) at 1000 °C. This is confirmed by DTA measurements (Figure 51c), which show that the dissolution of (α Ti) is completed just below 1000 °C. Surprisingly, no exothermal peak which could be expected as a result of the dissolution of the metastable α'' during heating, is observed in this measurement.

Figure 51 BSE image of alloy TAM1 (Ti-15Al-2.5Mo) heat-treated at a) 900 °C showing a two-phase microstructure composed of (αTi) (dark) and $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ (bright) and b) 1000 °C showing α'' martensite that formed from $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ during quenching; c) DTA heat flow curve of alloy TAM1 heat-treated at 1000°C showing that dissolution of (αTi) is complete at $999 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 52a shows the three-phase microstructure of alloy TAM2 (Ti-18.8Al-2.0Mo) quenched from 1000 °C. A similar microstructure consisting of (αTi) , $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o$, and Ti_3Al is observed in the sample heat-treated at 900 °C. Since no experiments were performed for this alloy to determine whether $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o$ is ordered or not, the assumption that $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o$ is stable is based on the calculations from Witusiewicz et al. [155] (this also applies for all other alloys, if not indicated otherwise). At 800 °C, two different phase compositions could be determined by EPMA (Table 23). Due to the high Al content (20.7 at.%) of the Mo-lean phase, it is

concluded that (αTi) is no longer present in the sample and $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ and Ti_3Al are in equilibrium.

Figure 52 BSE image of a) alloy TAM2 (Ti-18.8Al-2.0Mo) quenched from 1000 °C showing a three-phase microstructure (αTi) (grey) + $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ (bright) + Ti_3Al (dark) and b) alloy TAM3 (Ti-30.0Al-5.0Mo) quenched from 900 °C showing big $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ (bright) grains with fine Ti_3Al (dark) precipitates and Ti_3Al at the grain boundaries.

Between 800 and 1000 °C, $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ and Ti_3Al are observed in alloy TAM3 (Ti-30.0Al-5.0Mo). At 800 and 900 °C, the microstructure consists of large $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ grains with fine-scaled precipitates of Ti_3Al and similar to TAM1, Ti_3Al is also found at the grain boundaries (Figure 52b). Measurements with a widened beam (\varnothing 10 μm) inside the grain yield compositions that are on the tie-line determined by the compositions measured at the grain boundary. This proves that these two phases are the only microstructure constituents. At 1000 °C, the same but coarser microstructure is observed. EPMA measurements show that the composition of Ti_3Al inside the grain and at the grain boundary is similar, which is also true for $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$.

Alloy TAM4 (Ti-39.6Al-2.0Mo) was heat-treated between 800 and 1300 °C. At 800 °C, the phases are too fine-scaled to be measured by EPMA. Therefore, no phase compositions could be determined. Between 900 and 1100 °C (Figure 53a), this alloy clearly is three-phase. HEXRD measurements identified the phases present to be $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$, Ti_3Al , and TiAl . At 1200 °C (Figure 53b), (αTi) + $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ are identified as equilibrium phases. After quenching from 1300 °C, a single-phase (αTi) microstructure, showing signs of decomposition, is observed.

Figure 53 BSE image of alloy TAM4 (Ti-39.6Al-2.0Mo) a) heat-treated at 1000 °C showing a three-phase microstructure consisting of $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ (bright), Ti_3Al (grey), and TiAl (dark) and b) heat-treated at 1200 °C showing a two-phase microstructure composed of (αTi) (grey) and $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ (bright) (despite various different contrasts only two different compositions were measured by EPMA).

Alloy TAM5 (Ti-44.9Al-1.2Mo) was investigated at 1000, 1200 and 1300 °C. At 1000 and 1200 °C (Figure 54a) the microstructure is three-phase and the phases present are $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$, Ti_3Al , and TiAl. The difference with TAM4 is the higher phase fraction of TiAl, which is due to a higher overall Al content. The sample quenched from 1300 °C shows a lamellar two-phase microstructure of (αTi) and TiAl after quenching (Figure 54b).

Figure 54 BSE image of alloy TAM5 (Ti-44.9Al-1.2Mo) a) heat-treated at 1200 °C showing a three-phase microstructure consisting of (αTi) (grey), $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ (bright), and TiAl (dark) and b) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing a two-phase microstructure between (αTi) (bright) and TiAl (dark).

At 1300 °C, a similar microstructure is observed in alloy TAM6 (Ti-45.0Al-2.5Mo). At 1200 °C and below, the alloy composition is located in the two-phase field $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o + \text{TiAl}$ (Figure 55a). Similar observations are made for alloy TAM7 (Ti-44.6Al-3.7Mo) between 800 and 1200 °C. At 1300 °C, the composition of this alloy is located inside the tie-triangle $(\alpha\text{Ti}) + (\beta\text{Ti,Mo}) + \text{TiAl}$ (Figure 55b).

Figure 55 BSE image of a) alloy TAM6 (Ti-45.0Al-2.5Mo) heat-treated at 1200 °C showing a two-phase microstructure composed of $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o$ (bright) and TiAl (dark) and b) alloy TAM7 (Ti-44.6Al-3.7Mo) showing a three-phase microstructure consisting of (αTi) (grey), $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ (bright), and TiAl (dark) after quenching from 1300 °C.

Alloys TAM8 (Ti-45.0Al-5.0Mo), TAM9 (Ti-45.0Al-7.5Mo), and TAM10 (Ti-45.0Al-10.0Mo) are composed of $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o + \text{TiAl}$ in the temperature range between 800 and 1200 °C (Figure 56a-d). Between 1200 and 1300 °C $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ disorders in these three alloys, which is confirmed by DTA measurements (TAM8: 1278 °C; TAM9: 1287 °C; TAM10: 1285 °C). Based on these results, the two phases present in the microstructure at 1300 °C are identified as disordered $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ and TiAl.

Figure 56 BSE image of a) alloy TAM8 (Ti-45.0Al-5.0Mo) heat-treated at 1000 °C, b),c) alloy TAM9 (Ti-45.0Al-7.5Mo) heat-treated at 900 and 1300 °C, respectively; d) alloy TAM (Ti-45.0Al-10.0Mo) heat-treated at 1200 °C all showing a two-phase microstructure consisting of $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ (bright) and TiAl (dark).

A two-phase microstructure is observed between 1100 and 1300 °C in alloy TAM11 (Ti-56.1Al-10.9Mo) (Figure 57a). Based on *in situ* HEXRD measurements, these two phases are identified as $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ and TiAl. At temperatures below 1100 °C, the microstructure is more complex. Figure 57b shows a BSE image of alloy TAM11 quenched from 1000 °C revealing four different contrasts. There is a dark TiAl matrix with TiAl₃ regions having a slightly brighter contrast. Inside these regions, $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ (grey) and the σ phase (bright) are observed. This indicates that the sample is not in equilibrium, because in a three-component system, four phases cannot be in equilibrium. Therefore, the sample was homogenized at 1300 °C for 48 h, as the alloy is in equilibrium at this temperature, as shown by Figure 57a. After the subsequent heat treatment at 1000 °C, a microstructure similar to the non-homogenized alloy was observed (Figure 57c). Similar observations are also made in samples

heat-treated at 900 °C (Figure 57d) and 800 °C. Therefore, no phase compositions for alloy TAM11 are given in Tables 23-25. A detailed discussion about the phases which should be in equilibrium follows in Section 5.3.1.

Figure 57 BSE images of alloy TAM11 (Ti-56.1Al-10.9Mo) a) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing a two-phase microstructure composed of $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ (bright) and TiAl (dark); b) heat-treated at 1000 °C; c) homogenized at 1300 °C for 48 h and subsequently heat-treated at 1000 °C; and d) homogenized at 1300 °C for 48 h and subsequently heat-treated at 900 °C showing $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_0$ (grey), TiAl (dark), TiAl_3 (light grey), and σ (bright) in their respective microstructures.

Alloy TAM12 (Ti-62.0Al-3.0Mo) is single-phase TiAl after heat treatment at 1200 and 1300 °C. The results presented here and listed in Tables 23-28 are used to determine the isothermal sections, which are presented and discussed in the next section.

5.3 Isothermal sections, phase fields, solubility and phase formation

Based on the experimental results presented above (Tables 23-28) and the discussion of these equilibria below, partial isothermal sections between 800 and 1300 °C (Figures 58-63) were determined. For the binary boundary systems, Ti–Al and Ti–Mo, the assessed phase diagrams reported in [28, 29] and [33], respectively, were used. The dashed phase boundaries and three-phase fields are taken from Ref. [153] where the complete Ti–Al–Mo system has been assessed. In the following, phase equilibria regarding the σ phase, ordering behaviour of $(\beta\text{Ti},\text{Mo})$ in the ternary composition range, and solubility limits of the ternary elements in the binary boundary phases are discussed. Finally, a revised reaction scheme is presented based on the reaction scheme in Ref. [153] and the results discussed here.

Figure 58 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Mo system at 800 °C based on the experimental results listed in Table 23. The measured overall compositions of the samples are indicated by black stars (unfilled stars: as-cast or nominal alloy composition, see Table 2), the yellow lines show the three-phase equilibria, and blue symbols and lines mark the results from bulk alloys and the resulting phase boundaries.

Figure 59 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Mo system at 900 °C based on the experimental results listed in Table 24 (symbols as in Figure 58).

Figure 60 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Mo system at 1000 °C based on the experimental results listed in Table 25 (symbols as in Figure 58).

Figure 61 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Mo system at 1100 °C based on the experimental results listed in Table 26 (symbols as in Figure 58).

Figure 62 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Mo system at 1200 °C based on the experimental results listed in Table 27 (symbols as in Figure 58).

Figure 63 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–Mo system at 1300 °C based on the experimental results listed in Table 28 (symbols as in Figure 58).

5.3.1 Phase equilibria with the σ phase

As mentioned above, four different phases are present in the microstructure of alloy TAM11 heat-treated at 1000 °C and below (Figure 57b-d), and attempts to establish equilibrium by long heat treatment times and by an additional preceding homogenization at 1300 °C were unsuccessful. However, the microstructure in the as-cast sample can give an indication of the phases in equilibrium. As Figure 64a shows, there is a Mo-rich primary solidified phase (Ti-45.3Al-19.5Mo) which, based on the liquidus projection presented in Ref. [153] is identified as $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$. This phase is enclosed by a region of grey contrast (Ti-54.7Al-11.3Mo) and the rest of the microstructure shows a dark contrast (Ti-60.2Al-7.2Mo). A bright contrast, corresponding to the σ phase, as observed in the heat-treated alloys (Figure 57), is not visible in the as-cast microstructure, indicating that the σ phase has formed as a result of the heat treatment and must be one of the equilibrium phases. This is consistent with the microstructures observed in alloy TAM11 after heat treatments at 800 to 1000 °C. (Figures 57b-d and 64). These observations at different heat treatment temperatures show that with increasing temperature from 800 to 1000 °C, the fraction of σ in the microstructure also increases. It is also observed that TiAl (dark contrast) is never in contact with $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ or σ at any point in the microstructure. It is concluded that between 700 and 1000 °C, $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo}) + \text{TiAl}_3 + \sigma$ are the equilibrium phases. However, due to the presence of TiAl in the microstructures, these samples are not in equilibrium.

Figure 64: BSE image of alloy TAM11 (Ti-56.1Al-10.9Mo) a) in the as-cast condition showing solidification of primary ($\beta\text{Ti,Mo}$) completely surrounded by a grey contrast and a dark contrast filling the left over space; b) the heat-treated sample quenched from 800 °C showing first indications of formation of σ (bright).

This poses the question of why TiAl does not dissolve. A possible explanation could be that TiAl is only in contact with TiAl_3 but not with the primary ($\beta\text{Ti,Mo}$). As can be seen from the isothermal sections (Figures 58-63), a two-phase field exists between TiAl and TiAl_3 . This indicates that they are locally in equilibrium and thermodynamically stable. However, for the sample to reach equilibrium, σ must form. This requires Mo, which must be provided mainly by the dissolution of TiAl. However, due to the local thermodynamic equilibrium between TiAl and TiAl_3 , the driving force for TiAl dissolution is small. Furthermore, these atoms would have to diffuse throughout TiAl_3 to reach the ($\beta\text{Ti,Mo}$)/ TiAl_3 interface, because σ can only form there, as phases in equilibrium must be in contact with each other. As the experiments show, this process is very slow in alloy TAM11 and the TiAl_3 phase acts a diffusion barrier. Even after heat treatment at 1000 °C for 650 h (homogenized sample) a considerable amount of TiAl is retained in the microstructure (Figure 57d). Therefore, it is unlikely that equilibrium will be reached in this alloy in any reasonable time frame, even at 1000 °C, where 650 h usually is a more than sufficient time for heat treatment.

5.3.2 Ordering behaviour of ($\beta\text{Ti,Mo}$)

As indicated by the dashed line in the isothermal sections (Figures 58-63), there is also a composition and temperature range in the Ti–Al–Mo system where ordering occurs in the ($\beta\text{Ti,Mo}$) phase. Coming from high temperatures, this B2-type ($\beta\text{Ti,Mo}$)_o phase appears for the

first time at a composition Ti-25Al-25Mo and a temperature of 1418 °C [31], which has been confirmed by own DTA measurements results yielding a respective value of 1420 °C (Table 29). The isothermal section at 1300 °C (Figure 63) shows that the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o$ phase field is connected with the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo}) + \text{TiAl}$ two-phase field. This requires a eutectoid reaction $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo}) \rightleftharpoons (\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o + \text{TiAl}$ (ec_1 in the reaction scheme, see Figure 65) to take place above 1300 °C. The composition of the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ phase at which this reaction initially takes place must lie between the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ compositions of TAM9 and TAM10, since these two alloys order just below 1300 °C at 1287 and 1285 °C, respectively (Table 29). The region in which $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o$ and TiAl coexist increases towards lower Mo contents with decreasing temperature, as suggested by the measured ordering temperature of alloy TAM8 (1278 °C). The calculations from Witusiewicz et al. [155] show that at 1253°C, the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o$ phase field on the Mo-rich side reaches the boundary to the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo}) + \text{Mo}_3\text{Al}$ two-phase field resulting in the eutectoid reaction $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo}) \rightleftharpoons (\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o + \text{Mo}_3\text{Al}$ (ec_2). As a result, the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ phase field is divided into two separate parts by the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o$ phase field as shown in the isothermal section at 1200 °C (Figure 62). At lower temperatures this separation is no longer observed (Figures 58-61) as a result of the reaction $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo}) \rightleftharpoons (\beta\text{TiMo})_o + \text{TiAl}_3 + \text{Mo}_3\text{Al}$ (Ec_1). With decreasing temperature the homogeneity range of $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o$ grows towards the binary Ti–Mo system.

Table 29 Disorder temperatures determined by DTA measurements for alloys TAM8, TAM9, TAM10, and TAM13 with the composition of the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ phase. For alloy TAM13 the nominal composition is give, for the other alloys the composition determined in the quenched sample for 1300 °C.

Alloy No.	Composition of $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ phase (at.%)			Disordering temperature (°C)
	Ti	Al	Mo	
TAM8	54.8	37.3	8.1	1278
TAM9	50.5	38.3	11.2	1287
TAM10	47.2	39.8	13.0	1285
TAM13	50.0	25.0	25.0	1420

5.3.3 Solubility of ternary elements in the boundary phases (α Ti), (β Ti,Nb), and Ti_3Al

As with the binary Ti–Al (Figure 1) and the ternary Ti–Al–Nb system (Section 4.2), the (α Ti) solid solution exists in two separated phase fields (Figures 58-63). At temperatures up to 1110 ± 10 °C, (α Ti) only exists in a narrow composition range along the Al–Ti boundary with Al contents up to >20 at.% and low Mo solubilities (~ 0.5 at.% in alloys TAM1 and TAM2). This is consistent with the equally low solubilities reported by Huang et al. [166], who found a maximum Mo content of ~ 1 at.%. At higher temperatures, another phase field of (α Ti) appears at higher Al contents, which extends further into the ternary composition triangle with increasing temperature (Figures 62 and 63). The maximum Mo content in (α Ti) is reached in the three-phase equilibrium with (β Ti,Mo) and TiAl . This value increases to ~ 3 at.% Mo at 1300 °C (at a corresponding Al content of about 43 at.%). The values measured at 1200 and 1300 °C (Tables 27 and 28) are in agreement with those reported in the literature [106, 166, 167].

The (β Ti,Mo) solid solution extends far into the ternary composition space and its phase field connects to the binary A2-disordered MoAl phase at temperatures above 1470°C [168]. The maximum solubility lies around 48 at.% Al at 1300 °C and decreases to ~ 42.5 at.% at 800 °C. The maximum Mo content also decreases with decreasing temperature reaching values of about 30 at.% at 1100 and 1200 °C (Figures 61 and 62) and 20 at.% at 1000 °C (Figure 60). At lower temperatures, the phase field shrinks further. The evolution of the (β Ti,Mo) phase field presented here is consistent with the general trends reported in literature and by modeling [155, 166].

Ti_3Al shows a similar low solubility for Mo as (α Ti). The solubility maximum reaches about 2 at.% (alloy TAM3 at 900 °C, see Figure 59). These observations are in agreement with Huang et al. [166]. Since the Mo solubility in alloys TAM1 ((α Ti) + (β Ti,Mo) + Ti_3Al) and TAM4/TAM6 ((β Ti,Mo) + Ti_3Al + TiAl) is always lower than in alloy TAM3, this leads to a curved phase boundary, showing a shallow solubility maximum around 30 at.% Al.

5.4 Reaction Scheme

Based on the results described above there is one change that needs to be made to the reaction scheme of the Ti–Al–Mo system presented by Distl et al. [153]. Since σ is in equilibrium with $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ and TiAl_3 from below 1100 °C down to at least 800 °C (see Sections 5.2 and 5.3.1), the temperature of the transition-type reaction $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o + \text{TiAl}_3 \rightleftharpoons \text{TiAl} + \sigma$ needs to be shifted to below 800 °C, which is possible. The reaction temperature of 980 ± 10 °C, which was assumed in Ref. [153], is based on the observation of Huang et al. [166] that the phases $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$, TiAl , and σ are in equilibrium at 900 °C. In their work, the identification of the phases was based on XRD measurements of the respective sample. However, there are a number of peaks that were not assigned to any of those phases (c.f. Figure 3e in Ref. [166]). Due to the crystallographic similarities of TiAl and TiAl_3 (Table 1) it may be possible that the phase equilibrium was not correctly identified, which would need to be verified by further investigation.

As the discussions of the Ti–Al–Nb and Ti–Al–Mo systems have shown, the presence of ternary intermetallic phases and their decomposition in the solid state can lead to very different, complex phase relations, making the determination of phase equilibria a difficult task. Furthermore, the two alloying elements Nb and Mo behave very differently with respect to the ordering behaviour of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb/Mo})$ and their solubility in the Ti–Al boundary phases. Another possible but not yet well investigated alloying element is W. It belongs to the same group in the periodic table of elements as Mo, and since alloying elements of the same group tend to result in similar phase equilibria, one might expect the Ti–Al–W system to be comparable to the Ti–Al–Mo system. If this is true will be discussed in the following section.

* MoAl forms a common phase field with $(\beta\text{Ti}_3\text{Mo})$ [168]. As below 1470°C the binary MoAl phase no longer exists, the designation of the phase field is $(\beta\text{Ti}_3\text{Mo})$.

6 Phase equilibria, microstructure, and phase stability in Ti–Al–W alloys

In the last decades, several TiAl-based alloys with W as an alloying element were developed for use in high-temperature structural applications. The so-called “ABB-alloy” (Ti-47Al-2W-0.5Si) was developed for investment casting and showed promising creep properties at 760 °C, but the ductility at room temperature was poor [19]. The alloy G4 (Ti-47Al-1RE-1W-0.2Si) [169] is a further development of the ABB alloy, which has even better creep properties, but whose liability to casting defects leads to very inhomogeneous and unpredictable mechanical properties [170]. Therefore, a spark-plasma sintering route has been explored for this alloy, showing promising results [171]. In addition, the IRIS alloy (Ti-48Al-2W-0.08B) has also been developed for this process route. This alloy shows promising mechanical properties to achieve application temperatures above 800 °C [171-176]. Given all these efforts in alloy development, it is surprising that not much information is available on the phase equilibria in the ternary Ti–Al–W system, especially for higher W contents. Compared to the Ti–Al–Nb (Section 4) and Ti–Al–Mo (Section 5) systems, there is no report of a ternary intermetallic phase or phase equilibria with phases from the binary Al–W [177] system. Therefore, only (β Ti,W) and the (W) solid solution are expected as additional phases in the alloys investigated. The crystallographic information of these phases is summarized in (Table 30). The available literature on phase equilibria is briefly summarized in Section 6.1 before the results of a systematic study of heat-treated alloys between 800 and 1300 °C is presented (Section 6.2) and discussed (Section 6.3).

Table 30 Crystallographic information (crystal system, Pearson symbol, space group, and Strukturbericht designation) of the additional phases present in the Ti–Al–W system and observed in the present investigations.

Phase designation	Crystal system	Pearson symbol	Space group	Strukturbericht designation	Reference
(W)	cubic	cI2	<i>Im-3m</i>	A2	[40]
(β Ti,W)	cubic	cI2	<i>Im-3m</i>	A2	[40]
(β Ti,W) _o		cP2	<i>Pm-3m</i>	B2	

6.1 Literature review

Despite the interest in W as an alloying element for TiAl-based alloys [5, 15, 19, 169-176], the information available on phase equilibria is limited to alloys whose compositions are close to the binary Ti–Al system. The Ti-rich corner of the Ti–Al–W system has been studied by Oleynikova et al. [178] at 600, 800, 1000, and 1100 °C in the 1970s with a series of alloys “highly contaminated with carbon” [178]. These studies reveal that (β Ti,W) shows a considerable solubility for Al at 1100 °C (~ 17 at.%). At lower temperatures, there are indications for different three-phase equilibria between the (W) solid solution and (α Ti), (β Ti,W), and Ti₃Al, but phase compositions were not determined for all phases. Additionally, (α Ti) and Ti₃Al show a very low solubility for W of about 0.4 at.% W between 800 and 1100 °C. Two vertical sections with constant W contents of 1.35 and 4.4 at.% respectively were reported [178]. Since then, there have been only a few further studies, all of which focus on specific phase equilibria in alloys with application-relevant compositions between 40 and 60 at.% Al above 1000 °C [106, 179-182]. These studies report phase compositions for (β Ti,W), Ti₃Al, TiAl, and in one case TiAl₃ [182], which contradict especially with the Al solubility in (β Ti,W) reported before [178]. Since all these alloys have fairly low contents of W there is not much known about the phase equilibria in the ternary composition triangle. In addition to that, there is a partial liquidus projection reported by Jung et al. [183] based on directional solidification experiments, confirming the (β Ti)-stabilizing effect of W. The scarcity of data and the contradicting results emphasise the need for further experimental investigations within this system in order to determine the phase equilibria over a wider composition and temperature range. The results of the present investigation on a series of heat-treated alloys are presented and discussed below.

6.2 Results

The phase and alloy compositions determined by EPMA measurements of 10 ternary bulk alloys (Table 2 Ti–Al–W part) heat-treated between 800 and 1300 °C (Table 3), are summarized in Table 31-34 along with the phase fractions determined from these measurements. As mentioned in Section 3.1.1, the intended W content was not achieved in the alloys, which is why compositions of alloys TAW3 and TAW4 as well as TAW5 and TAW6 are very similar. Therefore, similar phase equilibria are expected in the respective alloys and

only TAW4 and TAW5 have been characterized over the whole temperature range. The compositions given in the following, together with the alloy designations are always those measured in the as-cast condition (Table 2 Ti–Al–W part). The position of the alloys in the ternary composition triangle, are shown in Figure 66.

Figure 66 As-cast alloy compositions (Table 2) of the ternary bulk alloys (TAW1-TAW10) plotted in the composition triangle.

Table 31 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–W alloys heat-treated at 800 and 900 °C for 2000 h. (n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)
			Al	W	
800 °C					
TAW4	Ti-40.7Al-1.8W	Ti ₃ Al ^b	35.0 ± 1.0	1.0 ± 1.0	n.d.
		TiAl ^b	45.5 ± 1.0	0.5 ± 1.0	n.d.
		(W)	a	a	n.d.
TAW8 ^c	Ti-49.0Al-3.6W	TiAl	52.9 ± 0.6	1.2 ± 0.1	n.d.
		(W)	a	a	n.d.
TAW10 ^c	Ti-53.6Al-3.8W	TiAl	56.0 ± 0.1	2.4 ± 0.1	n.d.
		(W)	a	a	n.d.
900 °C					
TAW4	Ti-41.5Al-1.8W	(βTi,W) ^b	37.0 ± 1.0	6.0 ± 1.0	24
		Ti ₃ Al ^b	35.0 ± 1.0	0.5 ± 1.0	30
		TiAl ^b	48.0 ± 1.0	0.5 ± 1.0	46
TAW8 ^c	Ti-49.2Al-3.6W	TiAl	51.2 ± 0.3	1.2 ± 0.1	n.d.
		(W)	a	a	n.d.
TAW10 ^c	Ti-54.5Al-3.2W	TiAl	55.7 ± 0.4	2.3 ± 0.1	n.d.
		(W)	a	a	n.d.

^a Composition of (W) solid solution was not measured with EPMA or TEM.

^b Phase compositions determined with grid measurement, due to fine scale microstructure, see section 3.2.3.1

^c Microstructure looks similar as in the as-cast state. Therefore, most likely equilibrium was not reached, see section 6.3

Table 32 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–W alloys heat-treated at 1000 and 1100 °C for 650 and 400 h, respectively. (n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)
			Al	W	
1000°C					
TAW4	Ti-40.6Al-1.8W ^a	(βTi,W)	35.9 ± 0.4	6.6 ± 0.7	6
		Ti ₃ Al	36.0 ± 0.6	0.7 ± 0.1	3
		TiAl	45.7 ± 0.5	0.5 ± 0.1	91
TAW5	Ti-44.3Al-1.1W	(βTi,W)	35.0 ± 0.2	8.3 ± 0.3	6
		Ti ₃ Al	35.1 ± 0.4	0.7 ± 0.1	14
		TiAl	46.7 ± 0.3	0.6 ± 0.1	80
TAW8	Ti-51.0Al-3.1W	TiAl	52.4 ± 0.5	1.2 ± 0.1	n.d.
		(W)	b	b	n.d.
TAW10	Ti-55.9Al-3.0W	TiAl	57.4 ± 0.3	1.5 ± 0.2	n.d.
		(W)	b	b	n.d.
1100°C					
TAW4	Ti-40.6Al-1.8W ^a	(βTi,W)	36.1 ± 0.2	3.5 ± 0.1	42
		Ti ₃ Al	38.4 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.1	18
		TiAl	46.4 ± 0.2	0.5 ± 0.1	40
TAW5	Ti-44.5Al-1.1W ^b	(βTi,W)	35.6 ± 0.5	4.1 ± 0.1	n.d.
		Ti ₃ Al	37.7 ± 0.3	0.7 ± 0.1	n.d.
		TiAl	45.9 ± 0.2	0.5 ± 0.1	n.d.
TAW8	Ti-50.2Al-3.0W ^a	TiAl	50.8 ± 0.4	1.1 ± 0.1	n.d.
		(W)	b	b	n.d.
TAW10	Ti-54.4Al-2.9W	TiAl	55.4 ± 0.4	1.6 ± 0.4	n.d.
		(W)	b	b	n.d.

^a As-cast composition. This composition was also used to determine the phase fractions.

^b Composition of (W) solid solution was not measured with EPMA or TEM, see section 6.2 and 6.3.

Table 33 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–W alloys heat-treated at 1200 °C for 30 h (n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)
			Al	W	
TAW1	Ti-26.8Al-6.1W	(β Ti,W)	26.8 \pm 0.2	6.1 \pm 0.2	100
TAW2	Ti-28.8Al-13.1W ^a	(β Ti,W)	29.4 \pm 0.5	9.9 \pm 0.5	n.d.
		(W)	0.9 \pm 0.4	73.0 \pm 1.6	n.d.
TAW4	Ti-40.6Al-1.8W ^b	(α Ti)	40.6 \pm 0.2	1.0 \pm 0.1	47
		(β Ti,W)	37.1 \pm 0.3	3.6 \pm 0.1	30
		TiAl	46.5 \pm 0.2	0.7 \pm 0.1	20
TAW5	Ti-44.5Al-1.1W ^b	(α Ti)	41.4 \pm 1.4	1.0 \pm 0.1	29
		(β Ti,W)	37.3 \pm 0.8	3.7 \pm 0.1	10
TAW7	Ti-47.1Al-4.1W ^b	TiAl	47.2 \pm 0.8	0.7 \pm 0.1	61
		(β Ti,W)	36.0 \pm 0.3	11.0 \pm 0.2	19
TAW8	Ti-51.2Al-3.3W	TiAl	48.1 \pm 0.3	1.5 \pm 0.1	81
		(W)	c	c	n.d.
TAW9	Ti-48.4Al-8.4W	TiAl	52.4 \pm 0.3	1.4 \pm 0.1	n.d.
		(W)	c	c	n.d.
TAW10	Ti-54.9Al-3.3W ^b	TiAl	52.9 \pm 1.0	2.0 \pm 0.2	n.d.
		(W) ^d	0.7 \pm 1.2	80.8 \pm 1.7	4

^a Composition measured at 1300 °C. Therefore, phase fractions could not be determined.

^b As-cast composition. This composition was also used to determine the phase fractions.

^c Composition of (W) solid solution was not measured with EPMA or TEM, see section 6.2 and 6.3.

^d Phase composition determined by TEM-EDS, see section 6.3.1

Table 34 EPMA results on alloy and phase compositions as well as phase fractions of Ti–Al–W alloys heat-treated at 1300 °C for 20 h (n.d.: not determined).

Alloy No.	Composition after heat treatment (at.%)	Phases	Phase compositions measured with EPMA (at.%)		Phase fraction (vol.%)
			Al	W	
TAW2	Ti-28.8Al-13.1W ^a	(βTi,W)	30.7 ± 0.4	10.2 ± 0.2	96
		(W) ^d	0.9 ± 0.4	76.4 ± 1.9	4
TAW3	Ti-40.0Al-1.5W ^b	(αTi)	42.3 ± 0.2	0.9 ± 0.1	21
		(βTi,W)	40.4 ± 0.3	1.7 ± 0.1	79
TAW4	Ti-40.6Al-1.8W ^b	(αTi)	42.4 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.1	25
		(βTi,W)	40.0 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.1	75
TAW5	Ti-44.5Al-1.1W ^b	(αTi)	43.3 ± 0.6	1.1 ± 0.1	76
		TiAl	48.4 ± 0.5	0.9 ± 0.2	24
TAW6	Ti-44.8Al-0.9W ^b	(αTi)	43.0 ± 0.3	0.8 ± 0.1	71
		TiAl	49.5 ± 0.5	0.5 ± 0.1	29
TAW7	Ti-47.1Al-4.1W ^b	(βTi,W)	40.8 ± 0.3	7.4 ± 0.1	33
		TiAl	50.0 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.1	67
TAW8	Ti-51.3Al-3.2W	TiAl	52.1 ± 0.3	2.0 ± 0.1	n.d.
		(W) ^d	c	c	n.d.
TAW9	Ti-50.8Al-6.6W	TiAl	54.0 ± 1.2	2.2 ± 0.1	n.d.
		(W) ^d	c	c	n.d.
TAW10	Ti-56.0Al-3.6W	TiAl	57.4 ± 0.5	2.3 ± 0.1	n.d.
		(W) ^d	c	c	n.d.

^a Different composition compared to as-cast alloy, due to macroscopic inhomogeneity, see section 6.2

^b As-cast composition. This composition was also used to determine the phase fractions

^c Composition of (W) solid solution was not measured with EPMA or TEM, see section 6.2 and 6.3.

^d At 1300 °C there is no longer a miscibility gap in the binary Ti–W system between (W) and (βTi,W), therefore, a W-poor and W-rich (βTi,W) composition are in equilibrium. The notation '(W)' is kept here to indicate the W-rich composition.

Alloy TAW1 (Ti-28.3Al-6.1W) was heat-treated at 1200 °C only and shows a single-phase microstructure (Figure 67a). Based on the composition, it is concluded that this alloy is single-phase (β Ti,W).

Figure 67 BSE image of a) alloy TAW1 (Ti-28.3Al-6.1W) heat-treated at 1200 °C showing a single-phase (β Ti,W) microstructure; b) alloy TAW2 (Ti-32.3Al-8.6W) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing a two-phase microstructure between (β Ti,W) and (W).

For alloy TAW2 (Ti-32.3Al-8.6W), a two-phase microstructure between (β Ti,W) and (W) was observed at 1200 and 1300 °C (Figure 67b). The as-cast alloy was macroscopically very inhomogeneous, which is why the measured phase composition of the TAW2 sample after heat treatment (Table 33) do not fit to the as-cast overall composition given in (Table 2) (W contents are higher in both phases).

The microstructure of alloy TAW3 (Ti-40.0Al-1.5W) quenched from 1300 °C is composed of the two phases (α Ti) and (β Ti,W) (Figure 68a). Similar observations are made for alloy TAW4 (Ti-40.6Al-1.8W) at 1300 °C. Between 800 and 1200 °C (Figure 68b), this alloy shows a three-phase microstructure consisting of (β Ti,W) + Ti_3Al + TiAl. The phases have been identified by HEXRD measurements. In these measurements, no superstructure reflections, that would indicate a *B2*-ordering of (β Ti,W) were observed. Furthermore, DTA measurements of the as-cast state of alloys TAW3 to TAW6 also show no evidence of disordering. Based on these results it is assumed that no ordering occurs in the alloys investigated here.

Figure 68 BSE image of a) alloy TAW3 (Ti-40.0Al-1.5W) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing a two-phase microstructure (α Ti) (dark) + (β Ti,W) (bright); b) alloy TAW4 (Ti-40.6Al-1.8W), heat-treated at 1100 °C showing a three-phase microstructure composed of (β Ti,W) (bright), Ti_3Al (grey), and TiAl (dark).

Similar observations were made for alloys TAW5 (Ti-45.0Al-1.1W) and TAW6 (Ti-45.5Al-0.9W). Both alloys are two-phase (α Ti) + TiAl at 1300 °C (Figure 69a). Due to the higher Al content of the alloys compared to TAW3 and TAW4, TiAl is in equilibrium with (α Ti) instead of (β Ti,W). Large lamellar grains can be observed in the microstructure, which is a morphology typically observed in TiAl-based alloys. This indicates that (α Ti) was the stable phase at high temperature and has partly decomposed during quenching. Between 1000 and 1200 °C, a similar three-phase microstructure as for TAW3 and TAW4 is observed (Figure 69b), which again has been verified by HEXRD measurements of the quenched samples. Due to the higher Al content, the alloy compositions are located close to the TiAl corner of the (α Ti) + (β Ti,W) + TiAl tie-triangle. Therefore, the phase fraction of TiAl is very high as is well visible in Figure 69b.

Figure 69 BSE image of a) alloy TAW6 (Ti-45.5Al-0.9W) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing a two-phase microstructure consisting of (α Ti) (bright) and (TiAl) (dark); b) alloy TAW5 (Ti-45.0Al-1.1W) heat-treated at 1000 °C composed of the three phases (β Ti,W) (bright), Ti_3Al (grey), and TiAl (dark).

Alloy TAW7 (Ti-47.1Al-4.1W) was only heat-treated at 1200 and 1300 °C. The quenched samples show a two-phase microstructure composed of (β Ti,W) and TiAl (Figure 70a). The three alloys containing more than 50 at.% Al (TAW8, TAW9, and TAW10) show a microstructure mainly consisting of TiAl. Additionally, there are regions, where very fine scaled precipitates are observed. These precipitates are too small to be measured by EPMA and show two different contrasts and sizes in the BSE images (Figure 70b-d). In order to check whether additional heat treatment time leads to a growth of the particles sufficient to allow the measurement of the phase compositions, pieces cut from alloys TAW8 and TAW10 already heat-treated were subjected to additional heat treatments at 1000, 1100, 1200, and 1300 °C doubling the original times (to 1300, 800, 650, and 40 h, respectively). No significant change in the microstructure was observed (Figure 70c,d), and the composition of TiAl was found to remain unchanged. The values for TAW8 and TAW10 listed in Tables 31-34 are from the measurements made after the prolonged heat treatments. Some of these alloys were investigated using TEM and TEM-EDS. These measurements show that the bright precipitates (in BSE contrast) belong to the (W) solid-solution. A more detailed discussion of these results is performed in Section 6.3.1.

a)

b)

c)

d)

Figure 70 BSE image of a) alloy TAW7 (Ti-47.1Al-4.1W) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing a two-phase microstructure (β Ti,W) (bright) + TiAl (dark); b) alloy TAW9 (Ti-50.8Al-6.6W) heat-treated at 1300 °C showing a TiAl matrix with bright (W) precipitates; a,d) alloy TAW8 (Ti-50.2Al-3.0W) heat treated at 1100 °C for 400 and 800 h, respectively, showing the same microstructure constituents as in b).

6.3 Isothermal sections, phase fields, solubility and phase formation

Based on the experimental results presented above (Tables 31-34) and information from the literature discussed below, partial isothermal sections between 800 and 1300 °C were established (Figures 71-76). For the binary boundary systems Ti–Al, Ti–W, and Al–W, the assessed phase diagrams, as reported in [28, 29], [34], and [177], respectively, were used. In the Ti–W system, a miscibility gap exists in the (β Ti,W) phase field below 1250 °C. This leads to the formation of two separate phase fields in the ternary Ti–Al–W system marked as (β Ti,W) and (W) solid solution in the isothermal sections at 1200 °C and below. The dashed tie-triangle showing phase equilibria with TiAl_3 between 1000 and 1300 °C is tentatively drawn based on the results of Sparks et al. [182] at 1200 °C. In the following sections, the phase equilibria between TiAl and the (W) solid-solution as well as the solubility of the ternary elements in the boundary phases are discussed.

Figure 71 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–W system at 800 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 31. The measured overall compositions of the samples are indicated by black stars (grey stars for as-cast compositions), the yellow lines mark the three-phase equilibria, and blue symbols and lines mark the results from bulk alloys and the resulting phase boundaries.

Figure 72 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–W system at 900 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 31 (symbols as in Figure 71).

Figure 73 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–W system at 1000 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 32 (symbols as in Figure 71).

Figure 76 Partial isothermal section of the Ti–Al–W system at 1300 °C based on the experimental results tabulated in Table 34 (symbols as in Figure 71).

6.3.1 Phase equilibria with the (W) solid solution

As mentioned in Section 6.2, alloys TAW8, TAW9 and TAW10 show a microstructure consisting mainly of TiAl and very fine precipitates, which are too small to be measured with EPMA, even after doubling the heat treatment times. HEXRD measurements on the samples of alloy TAW8 heat-treated between 1000 and 1200 °C show that a cubic phase is present in addition to TiAl. This is consistent with the microstructures observed, which have similar appearance (Figure 77). The microstructure of alloys TAW9 (Figure 70b) and TAW10 are similar, therefore it is concluded, that in these alloys the same three phases are in equilibrium.

Figure 77 BSE image of alloy TAW8 (Ti-50.2Al-3.0W) heat-treated at a) 1000 °C and b) 1200 °C showing a TiAl matrix with bright (W) precipitates.

Alloy TAW7 quenched from 1200 and 1300 °C (Figure 70a) shows a two-phase microstructure between $(\beta\text{Ti,W})$ and TiAl. In addition, the tie-line data of alloy TAW2 at 1200 and 1300 °C suggest a phase equilibrium between a W-poor and W-rich $(\beta\text{Ti,W})$ phase (i.e., $(\beta\text{Ti,W}) + (\text{W})$) corresponding to the miscibility gap in the ternary system. From these observations, i.e., the existence of a $(\beta\text{Ti,W}) + \text{TiAl}$ and a $(\beta\text{Ti,W}) + (\text{W})$ equilibrium, it is concluded that there must be a tie-triangle $(\beta\text{Ti,W}) + \text{TiAl} + (\text{W})$ between 1000 and 1300 °C, if there is no ternary intermetallic phase. In addition, Sparks et al. [182] found a three-phase field between TiAl, TiAl_3 and “almost pure W” in an alloy with a nominal composition of Ti-63Al-12W. As a result, there are three-phase fields with (W) on the Al-lean and Al-rich side of these alloy compositions. This makes it likely that a two-phase field exists between $(\beta\text{Ti,W})$ and TiAl, unless there is a ternary intermetallic phase with a cubic crystal structure present in the ternary composition triangle. Since (W) also has a cubic lattice (Table 30) and a similar lattice constant to $(\beta\text{Ti,W})$, they are difficult to distinguish using HEXRD. Therefore, TEM and TEM-EDS was used to confirm that these precipitates are indeed (W)⁶. Figure 78a shows the BSE image of alloy TAW10 quenched from 1200 °C. As can be seen in the bright-field (BF) TEM image (Figure 78b) of this alloy, there are small precipitates with a dark contrast in this sample. In a high angle annular dark field image (HAADF) image (Figure 78c) these precipitates appear bright. This indicates that the concentration of heavy elements (most likely W) is higher in these precipitates than in the matrix. This is confirmed by the TEM-EDS

⁶ The TEM studies were performed in cooperation with Dr. Boryana Rashkova from Montanuniversität Leoben, Austria

mapping (W_{Ma} -line) in Figure 78d, which show that the precipitates have a much higher concentration of W compared to the matrix. Luckily, the TEM sample had a hole after sample preparation (Figure 78c,d), which made it possible to measure the composition of the precipitate (Ti-0.7Al-80.8W) without any influence of the TiAl matrix on the composition. Additionally, selected area diffraction experiments were performed to confirm the cubic crystal structure of these precipitates. As a miscibility gap is reported in the binary Ti-W system [34], it is concluded that these precipitates are indeed the (W) solid solution.

Figure 78 a) BSE image of alloy TAW10 (Ti-54.9Al-3.3W) heat-treated at 1200 °C showing a TiAl matrix with bright (W) precipitates; b) Bright-field image of TEM sample; c) HAADF image and d) TEM-EDS map with the W_{Ma} line showing that the bright precipitates are W rich.

The measured solubility of Al in (W) is very low. Therefore, to get an idea how this solubility changes with temperature, the alloys TAW8 und TAW10, heat treated at 1000 °C, were also examined by TEM. However, there were a lot of different compositions measured

within one sample for the (W) solid solution. These compositions and the composition of TiAl can be approximated by one straight line in the isothermal section (Figure 79a). From these observation, two conclusions are drawn: i) (W) must form during the heat treatment and ii) (W) has not reached its equilibrium composition yet.

Figure 79 a) TEM-EDS measurements of alloys TAW8 and TAW10 (dark arrows) superimposed on the isothermal section of Ti–Al–W at 1000 °C; BSE image of alloy TAW10 b) in the as-cast state showing TiAl and a primarily solidified phase with (~4 at.% W) and b) the sample quenched from 900 °C with a TiAl matrix and first indications of (W) formation.

These conclusions are confirmed by several experimental observations. The precipitates show both an intermediate and a bright contrast in the BSE images (Figure 70b-d and 77). This may be due to different compositions and/or orientation contrast as a result of different orientation relationships between the TiAl matrix and the (W) solid solution, which is reported in literature [184, 185]. Further investigations are needed to determine whether on or both of these possibilities are responsible for the different contrasts in the BSE images. Additionally,

there is no (W) observed in the as-cast microstructure (Figure 79b). This microstructure shows TiAl and a primarily solidified phase with around 4 at.% W (which must be $(\beta\text{Ti,W})$ solid solution) proving that (W) has to form during the heat treatment. Furthermore, compared to the initial heat treatment, the phase fraction of the cubic phase decreases in the HEXRD measurement of the sample with doubling the time, from 36 to 25 vol.%. Since there is no significant change in the composition of TiAl measured, this decrease of the phase fraction means that the W content of the cubic phase must have increased, which is just what is expected when the sample is on its way to reach the equilibrium state. This explanation is further supported by the microstructures of the samples after heat treatment at 800 and 900 °C (Figure 79c). These microstructures have a close resemblance to the as-cast alloys (Figure 79b). The first signs of the formation of (W) are visible from the appearance of the decomposed primarily solidified phase. This confirms the explanation given above and shows that the formation of (W) is a very slow, diffusion-controlled process.

6.3.2 Solubility of ternary elements in the boundary phases (αTi), ($\beta\text{Ti,W}$), Ti_3Al , TiAl, and (W)

As also observed in the systems with Nb and Mo (Sections 4.1.3, 4.2.3 and 5.3) (αTi) has a Ti-rich and Al-rich phase field. At 1200 (Figure 75) and 1300°C (Figure 76), the solubility of W in the Al-rich (αTi) phase is determined by the composition of (αTi) in the tie-triangle (αTi) + ($\beta\text{Ti,W}$) + TiAl. The solubility values obtained from the present experiments are 1.0 at.% W at 1200 °C and 1.1 at.% W at 1300 °C. The value from 1200 °C is consistent with the experimental results obtained by Kainuma et al. [106]. At 1300°C, they reported a solubility of 2.4 at.% [106]. Solubilities for the Ti-rich (αTi) phase field (0.4 at.% W) have only been reported by Oleynikova et al. [178].

The maximum Al solubility in ($\beta\text{Ti,W}$) at 1300 °C lies close to the value measured for ($\beta\text{Ti,W}$) in alloy TAW7 and is estimated to be about 40 at.%, which is consistent with Kainuma et al. [106] and Hashimoto et al. [180]. At 1200 °C and below (Figures 73-75) this value decreases down to 35 at.% at 1000 °C, which again is consistent with the results from Kainuma et al. [106]. These solubilities do not agree with the results of Oleynikova et al. [178], who reported a maximum solubility of 17.1 at.% Al at 1100 °C. Additionally, they found phase equilibria other than those presented here, which might be a result of the C contamination in their samples [178]. Since the results of Kainuma et al. [106] and Hashimoto et al. [180, 181]

are consistent with the results presented here, those of Oleynikova et al. [178] are not considered for temperatures above 1000 °C. At lower temperatures the solubility of Al in (β Ti,W) decreases rapidly, resulting in a very low solubility (~1 at.% [178]) at 800 °C (Figure 71). This decrease in solubility is a result of the two transition type-reactions (β Ti,W) + TiAl \rightleftharpoons Ti₃Al + (W) and (β Ti,W) + (W) \rightleftharpoons (α Ti) + (W) which must take place between 800 and 900 °C for the phase equilibria shown in the isothermal section (Figures 71 and 72) to be possible.

The solubility of W in Ti₃Al decreases slightly from 0.7 (1100 °C) to 0.4 at.% (900°C) (Tables 31 and 32) with the Al content also slightly decreasing (38 to 35 at.%). Similar low values for the solubility are also reported in the literature [106, 178, 180, 181].

For TiAl, Sparks et al. [182] reported a maximum solubility of about 4 at.% W at 65 at.% Al in a sample quenched from 1200 °C. The maximum solubility cannot be measured with the alloys studied here. However, the alloys TAW4, TAW8, and TAW10 (Figure 80) show an increase in W solubility with increasing temperature and Al content of the alloy, which is also observed in the literature [106]. Therefore, the value determined by Sparks et al. [182] appears realistic.

Figure 80 Increase of the solubility of W in TiAl as a function of temperature for the alloys TAW4, TAW8 and TAW10 in the temperature range of 1000 to 1300 °C.

The Al solubility in (W) is low, as the TEM measurements of alloy TAW10 quenched from 1200 °C (Table 33) show. The maximum values are given by the binary Al–W system

[177]. The phase boundary of the (W) solid solution in the isothermal sections is approximated such that the Al solubility decreases with decreasing temperature.

This concludes the investigations on phase equilibria in the three systems Ti–Al–X (X = Nb, Mo, W). In the following section, the conclusions drawn from all the experimental investigation presented above are summarized.

7 Conclusions

For the purpose of establishing phase equilibria in the Ti-rich corner of the three ternary Ti–Al–X systems ($X = \text{Nb, Mo, W}$), a series of heat-treated ternary alloys, several solid-solid and liquid-solid diffusion couples as well as two binary Ti–Al alloys were investigated by SEM, EPMA, (HE)XRD, TEM, and DTA. The heat treatments were performed in the application relevant temperature range from 700 to 1300 °C. Based on the results of these studies, isothermal sections for each system were determined.

The Ti–Al–Nb system is by far the most complex of the three investigated systems. Therefore, the investigations of this system were split into separate parts. The first part focused on the low-temperature phase equilibria between 700 and 900 °C, where the two ternary intermetallic compounds ω_o and O are stable and exhibit extended composition ranges.

The O phase extends parallel to the Ti-Nb axis between 15 and about 30 at.% Nb along an only slightly varying Al content of 24-28 at.%. The phase field of ω_o also extends along an approximately constant Al content. In this case, the Nb contents cover a range from 10 to 20 at.% and the Al content varies between 32.5 and 36 at.%. The homogeneity range of the ω_o phase does not include the composition corresponding to the formula Ti_4NbAl_3 normally used in the literature. Instead, this phase can be well described by the formula $(\text{Ti,Nb})_2\text{Al}$. This new formula fits exactly to the well-established crystal structure type (prototype Ni_2In , *hP6*) of the ω_o phase and, therefore, is suggested to replace the old phase designation Ti_4NbAl_3 . With increasing temperature, the phase field of ω_o becomes more and more constricted as the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ phase field, which forms as a result of a eutectoid-type reaction at 790 °C from TiAl and ω_o , grows. At 900 °C, the phase field of ω_o is split into two parts by the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ field. Based on DTA measurements and the observed phase equilibria, a reaction sequence is suggested that describes the splitting of the phase field and the evolution of the resulting phase equilibria.

The solubility of Nb in the (αTi) solid solution and in Ti_3Al is nearly constant in the investigated temperature range 700-900 °C. It amounts to (4.0 ± 0.5) at.% Nb at an Al content of 17.0-17.6 at.% for (αTi) and (12.5 ± 0.2) at.% Nb (Al content 24.9-25.5 at.%) in case of Ti_3Al . For the solubility of Al in the $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})$ solid solution, values of about 12 at.% were measured at 700 and 800 °C, while this value increases to about 17 at.% at 900 °C. Nb_2Al extends far into the ternary system, with the solubility of Ti reaching about 35 and 37 at.% at 800 and 900 °C, respectively.

Within the extended phase field of the disordered (β Ti,Nb) solid solution, *B2*-ordering occurs at 900 °C in a small composition range at the Al-rich boundary and Nb contents near 25 at.%. At 700 and 800 °C, no *B2*-ordering occurs because of the lower Al solubility.

In the second part of the investigations on the Ti–Al–Nb system, the high-temperature phase equilibria between 1000 and 1300 °C were investigated. The (β Ti,Nb)_o phase field, which forms at 790 °C, exists as an isolated phase field simultaneously with the (β Ti,Nb) solid solution up to 1100 °C. It extends parallel to the Ti-Nb axis between 11 and 18 at.% Nb at 1000 °C and 6.5 and 20 at.% Nb at 1100 °C, with Al contents between 32-36 at.%. These two phase fields of the (β Ti,Nb) phase merge above 1100 °C as result of a eutectoid reaction (β Ti,Nb)_o \rightleftharpoons Nb₂Al + Ti₃Al. The maximum solubility of Al in (β Ti,Nb) increases up to 40 at.% at 1300 °C. With increasing temperatures, the *B2*-ordered phase field shrinks and order is lost at a maximum temperature of about 1250 °C near a composition of Ti-33Al-17Nb (i.e., with one of the two lattice sites of the *B2* lattice occupied entirely by Ti, and the other one is shared by Al and Nb in an approximate ration of 2:1).

The Nb solubility in Ti₃Al is maximum at 1000 and 1100 °C reaching a value of about 15 at.%. The above mentioned quickly growing homogeneity range of the (β Ti,Nb)_o phase also affects the phase field of Ti₃Al and results in a local minimum in Nb content (6.5 at.%) around 35 at.% Al at 1100 °C. At temperatures above 1100 °C, the Nb solubility rapidly decreases and Ti₃Al is no longer stable above 1200 °C. The Al-rich (α Ti) phase forms from the binary Ti–Al system at 1120 °C and extends into the ternary composition triangle with increasing temperature as was also confirmed by DTA measurements.

In the investigated temperature range of 700 to 1300 °C, four different solid-state phase transformations take place in the Ti–Al–Nb system. The kinetics of these phase transformations plays an important role in determining the phase equilibria and designing the next generation of TiAl-based alloys. By systematic DTA investigations of one binary Ti-Al and 14 ternary Ti–Al–Nb alloys applying at least four different heating rates, the phase transformation characteristics of these solid-solid phase transformations in the Ti–Al–Nb system were investigated. From the viewpoint of the performed DTA experiments, there are two types of transformation.

The order/disorder transition of the (β Ti,Nb) phase from the cubic *B2*-ordered (β Ti,Nb)_o structure to the otherwise identical but disordered *A2* structure belongs to the first (heating rate independent) type of transformations. The observed heating rate independence of the measured

disordering temperatures is consistent with the second-order-type nature of this transition. The disordering temperature only changes as function of composition, and – as already mentioned above – reaches a maximum of about 1250 °C at a composition of Ti-33Al-16Nb.

The other three transformations Ti_3Al to (αTi) , ω_o to $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$, and O to $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ are first-order transformations, which is consistent with the observation that the measured onset temperatures of the transformation depend on the heating rate. This dependence is clearly nonlinear. To determine the equilibrium transformation temperature of solid-solid transformations with this characteristic, Zhu et al. [131, 132] developed a model resulting in a linear relation when the measured transformation temperatures are plotted over $(\text{heating rate})^{1/3}$. The present data can be very well described by this approach confirming the applicability of the model and allowing the determination of the equilibrium transformation temperatures, which are not accessible directly by a DTA heating or cooling experiment. The magnitude of the heating rate dependence increases with increasing complexity of the transformation. For the Ti_3Al to (αTi) transformation, there is only a weak heating rate dependence. In this case, both phases have the same hexagonal structure and the (αTi) structure can be regarded as the disordered variant of the ordered Ti_3Al structure. However, the transformation always also includes a (comparatively small) change in chemical composition and with that also a change in phase fractions. Therefore, there is a dependence on the heating rate, but this dependence is only weak. In case of the ω_o to $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ and O to $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ transformations, both the crystal structure types and the phase compositions (and phase fractions) change resulting in a more pronounced heating rate dependence. This dependence is stronger, possibly because of the high Nb contents in these two phases, resulting in slow diffusion, and/or the more complex crystallographic transformation path. The strongest heating rate dependence is observed for the O to $(\beta Ti,Nb)_o$ transformation.

Significant amounts of oxygen can be dissolved in the hexagonal phases (αTi) and (to a lesser amount) Ti_3Al . This could potentially also affect the phase equilibria and needs to be considered and understood. By reviewing the literature on phase equilibria in the ternary Ti–Al–Nb system at 1300°C and comparing them to own results, it could be shown that the amount of oxygen in heat-treated alloys can indeed have a significant impact on phase equilibria involving the (αTi) phase at high temperatures. This proves the necessity to carefully control the oxygen level in Ti-Al alloys and try to keep impurity levels as low as possible. As pointed out, oxygen atoms occupy Ti_6 octahedral voids which leads to a distortion of the crystal structure as function of oxygen content. The incorporation of Nb changes the electronic

structure in the crystal and since Nb substitutes with Ti, $\text{Ti}_{6-x}\text{Nb}_x$ octahedral voids might be formed. However, the exact mechanism that could explain how Nb atoms influence the electronic structure of octahedral voids and how oxygen promotes Nb incorporation is not clear and needs to be investigated further.

The presented reaction scheme for the Ti–Al–Nb system covers the range from the liquid phase down to 600 °C and considers all the discussed experimental results. It builds on the reaction scheme presented by Witusiewicz et al. [84] and now includes the *B2*-ordering of $(\beta\text{Ti,Nb})_o$ in the ternary system, the splitting of the ω_o phase field, and the equilibrium phase transformation temperatures determined with DTA measurements.

In the Ti–Al–Mo system, only one ternary intermetallic phase occurs. This is the so-called σ phase, which exists up to a maximum temperature of 1166 °C. From the present results, it was concluded that the σ phase is in equilibrium with $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ and, TiAl_3 between 800 and 1000 °C. As for the Ti–Al–Nb system, a *B2*-ordered $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o$ phase is stable in a certain composition range inside the homogeneity range of the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ solid solution. The maximum stability lies at a composition of Ti-25Al-25Mo (disordering temperature 1420 °C) and the composition range growth with decreasing temperature. Just below 1300 °C, the stability range of the *B2*-ordered phase connects with the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo}) + \text{TiAl}$ two-phase field, proven by DTA measurements, and the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo}) + \text{Mo}_3\text{Al}$ two-phase field. This splits the phase field of the $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})$ solid solution into two *A2*-disordered parts at 1200 °C. At 1100 °C, the maximum Al solubility (~50 at.%) lies at a Mo content of 30 at.%, and both values gradually decrease with decreasing temperature. As also observed in the Ti–Al–Nb system the *A2/B2*-transition temperature shifts to lower Al contents with decreasing temperature. A major difference to the Ti–Al–Nb system lies in the solubility of the ternary elements in (αTi) and Ti_3Al . For Ti_3Al a maximum of 2.1 at.% Mo at 900 °C is determined and for the Ti-rich (αTi) none of the reported values exceed 1 at.% Mo. The Al-rich (αTi) phase dissolves a maximum of 3.0 at.% Mo at 1300 °C. Based on the experimental results, a revised reaction scheme of the Ti–Al–Mo system is presented. The transition-type reaction $(\beta\text{Ti,Mo})_o + \text{TiAl}_3 \rightleftharpoons \text{TiAl} + \sigma$ is shifted to below 800 °C.

The phase equilibria observed in the Ti–Al–W system differ significantly from those of the Ti–Al–Nb and Ti–Al–Mo systems, because no ternary intermetallic phase is stable and no *B2*-ordering of $(\beta\text{Ti,W})$ was found experimentally. Due to a miscibility gap in the binary Ti–W system below 1250 °C, the $(\beta\text{Ti,W})$ phase field is split at 1200 °C and below. As there is no

ternary intermetallic phase in the system, this leads to a two-phase field with equilibria between the W-rich and W-poor ($\beta\text{Ti,W}$) phase as was proven by the presented experiments.

TEM and TEM-EDS investigations also confirmed phase equilibria between TiAl and the (W) solid solution. As the Al solubility in (W) at 1200 °C is very low (0.8 at.%), the two-phase field TiAl + (W) extends almost completely through the ternary composition triangle. Similar as in case of the Ti–Al–Nb and Ti–Al–Mo systems, the Al solubility in ($\beta\text{Ti,W}$) at high temperatures is very high (40 at.% at 1300 °C) and only slightly decreases down to 35 at.% at 1000 °C. As a result of the two transition type reactions ($\beta\text{Ti,W}$) + TiAl \rightleftharpoons Ti₃Al + (W) and ($\beta\text{Ti,W}$) + (W) \rightleftharpoons (αTi) + (W) the ($\beta\text{Ti,W}$) phase field shrinks significantly at lower temperatures and a solubility of around 1 at.% Al is assumed at 800 °C. The solubility of W in the (αTi) and Ti₃Al is equally low as reported for the Ti–Al–Mo system.

The data presented in this thesis on phase equilibria and phase transformation temperatures and kinetics in the three Ti–Al–X systems (X = Nb, Mo, W) are used to improve an existing CALPHAD database for TiAl-based alloys. This builds a sound foundation to facilitate the improvement of existing and development of future generations of alloys to reach application temperatures above 800 °C. This forms a solid basis to facilitate the improvement of existing and development of future generations of alloys to reach application temperatures above 800 °C. To achieve this goal further investigations are necessary. With Nb as the main alloying element and the fact that TiAl-based alloys consist of more than three elements, the influence of further alloying elements on the stability of the ternary intermetallic phases ω and ω_0 needs to be investigated. Besides manufacturability, oxidation and burn resistance as well as creep and fracture properties of these alloys need to be investigated under the harsh application conditions. Phase equilibria studies in combination with experiments under application condition enable the development of new generations of alloys for sustainable mobility in the future.

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Curriculum Vitae

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- **Distl, B.;** Stein, F.; Experimental Investigations of Phase Equilibria in Ternary Ti–Al–Mo and Ti–Al–W Alloys, Euromat 2021, Virtual (2021)
- **Distl, B.;** Stein, F.; ADVANCEs in TiAl based alloys systems – Phase equilibria and kinetics of phase transformations in Ti–Al–Nb alloys, Annual meeting of the technical committee “Intermetallic Phases” of the German Materials Society DGM, Virtual (2020)
- **Distl, B.;** Stein, F.; Phase equilibria in ternary Ti–Al–Nb alloys, 2020 Virtual MRS Spring/Fall Meeting & Exhibit; Virtual (2020)
- **Distl, B.;** Stein, F.; Phase equilibria in ternary Ti–Al–Nb alloys; 17th Discussion Meeting on Thermodynamics of Alloys (TOFA), Educational Center Kloster Banz, Bad Staffelstein, Germany (2020)
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Poster presentations

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